

Returning Home

A Creative Exploration of Self.

Submitted by

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Statement of Original Authorship

This thesis includes work by the author that has been published or accepted for publication as described in the text. Except where reference is made in the text of the thesis, this thesis contains no other material published elsewhere or extracted in whole or in part from a thesis accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma. No other person's work has been used without due acknowledgment in the main text of the thesis. This thesis has not been submitted for the award of any degree or diploma in any other tertiary institution.

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Below is a list of all publications that have arisen from this thesis to date:

Bardsley, L 2017, *Returning home*- an exhibition, held at Kinross Arts and Spirituality Centre, Melbourne, 12 October – 6 November, 2017.

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A Note on the Language Used

Throughout the body of this investigation I often refer to 'selves' as a means of alluding to the many self-narratives that appear to reside within our psyche. I also refer to the self at times with a capital 'S' to refer to the Self¹ in its most universal capacity. These concepts are unpacked further in the following chapters. As this is a practice-led exegesis, there is less room to provide a detailed analysis of the psychological and conceptual language utilised in the text; instead I have included a glossary of terms for clarification.

¹ As used by Jung (1976, pp. 460-461).

Keywords

Self-narratives, practice-led research, transpersonal research, auto-ethnography, life-writing, creative non-fiction, creative research, creative arts, documentary film, art novel, transformative research, organic inquiry, consciousness, embodiment, transcendence, compassionate action, collective unconscious, medical humanities, narrative medicine, Buddhist psychology, mindfulness, liminal, transpersonal psychology, memoir, art therapy, holocaust narratives, romantic love, trans-generational trauma, healing, Carl Jung, Stanislav Grof, inland, returning home.

Abstract

Postmodern theory indicates that a self-reflexive voice is a valid expression of cultural and temporal influences on language and meaning making. Transpersonal theories propose that 'self' is multiple and layered, some aspects of consciousness are more easily accessed, others, deeply held and previously unconscious. Narrative is intricately embedded in human experience and is a potent means of shaping self-identity, imbuing meaning, facilitating insight and transforming awareness. The creative arts form a unique, evocative means of investigating and expressing emergent narratives, conveying meaning and facilitating individual and collective transformation. This creative, practice-led investigation explores the question: *Who are we?* Utilising an embodied and transpersonal methodology, a woman, artist and depth psychologist investigates the nature of self. The creative findings include fine art, photography, life-writing, a short film, an art novel and an exhibition. The researcher's auto-ethnographic reflections discuss the impact of making the works, conclusions regarding their ramifications for understanding the nature of self, and their transformational potential. *Returning Home* alludes to the sense of cultivating a state of awareness where it is possible to compassionately witness the narratives of many selves, as well as the personal and global implications of doing so.

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Note: Unless otherwise stated, all images depict artworks or photographs created by the author.

Introduction

Overview

This investigation explores knowing the self through a practice-led, transpersonal methodology, utilising the arts (film, photography, fine art and life writing) as the language of expression. As the researcher, I am the lens through which the investigation takes place; it is coloured by my psyche, expressed through my own voice and shaped by the skills and limitations that I have as an artist, depth psychologist and woman with a rich life experience.

This section presents the aim and rationale for conducting this investigation, introduces the researcher (myself) and outlines the research question, investigative structure, and the theoretical models used.

About the Author

I began this research after a severe health crisis, one that forced me to terminate my practice as a clinician and trauma therapist after almost twenty-five years. It seemed time to offer a compassionate presence toward my own stories. These stories (some previously hidden) flowed into the spaciousness that this investigation evoked and became windows into my inner world, offering me the opportunity for integration and transformation. By employing a creative language, I hoped that what began as a personal exploration would offer a wider audience the means to reflect on the nature of self and potentially inspire people toward their own transformative process.

In my capacity as a therapist, I have helped provide an environment for healing and insight for hundreds of people, and developed a passion for understanding human consciousness. In my clinical practice, I have witnessed the capacity human beings have in shaping their own lives and those of others, through the way they relate to themselves, their intimate connections and the wider community. As my concern for Earth's ecological status has intensified, the potential for human beings to irrevocably change the planet and the experience of

all living things has become more apparent; I feel that for this reason alone, it is vital that we become aware of our selves, the stories that shape our actions, and the way we live.

My professional training is in creative arts, clinical, counselling and transpersonal psychology. After completing my initial clinical training, over twenty years ago, I sought to expand my understanding of the human experience and was drawn to transpersonal psychology where I underwent a further sixteen years' theoretical and experiential training². Transpersonal models of consciousness enhanced my understanding of the influence of personal, generational and transpersonal narratives on human experience as well as developing my appreciation of the immense capacity of humanity for transformation and creativity.

My career to this point has included a private psychology practice, working with people across their lifespan – individually, with couples, families, groups and institutions. I provide supervision for therapists at all stages of their career with a focus on the therapists' self-awareness and their presence with their own clients. I have continued my own exploration of self, including experiential training with transpersonal psychiatrist Stanislav Grof, studies in Tibetan and Theravada Buddhism, Systemic, Narrative and Existential therapeutic training as well as Jungian analysis. I practice daily meditation and mindfulness.

I find myself pursuing similar interests as an artist and psychologist, orienting toward transformative and transcendent states of consciousness, in the search for personal meaning. As an artist, I am professionally curious, asking questions about human experience without necessarily reaching definitive conclusions, using film, painting, photography and life writing as my creative language. In the therapy room, curiosity also governs my conversations; together, clients and I reflect on their response to life experiences, the choices made and the potential for personal growth. My role as a psychologist is as a curator of stories; I have the privilege of listening to the narratives that emerge within a safe space, witnessing as an attentive reflective listener. Time and again, I have seen transformations occurring through sharing our experiences and new perspectives

² This investigation includes a glossary, which includes the definition of transpersonal psychology and other psychological terms that are used.

that arise when we bring our narratives to awareness. As an artist, I create from an embodied response—a feeling of inspiration that captivates my attention, shapes the emergent work and the meaning I make of it. My art practice involves surrendering to emergent material and is often informed by my dreams, spiritual practice and environment. Each foray into the studio is an act of trust; I intuitively orient myself toward various mediums and materials in order to respond to feelings or inner directives as they emerge³. My experience both as an artist and transpersonal psychologist, as well as my personal narratives, informs my creative process.

This investigation is situated in the areas of creative and consciousness research as well as transpersonal psychology. The methodology is experiential, self-reflexive and led by my creative practice. The creative arts illustrate, inform and guide my personal exploration of the many layers of self, allowing for a personal, subjective and embodied voice to emerge.

Summary, research question, and investigative structure

This investigation utilises a practice-led and transpersonal methodology (*Organic Inquiry*) to explore the question: *What does it mean to know the self?* The investigation takes place primarily through the author's personal reflexive process, but also incorporates a wider contemporary audience. The findings consist of fine art images (paintings and photographs), a documentary film, life-writing accounts and auto-ethnographic reflections. The investigation culminated in an art exhibition, a short documentary film, and an art novel; these are incorporated or documented in the practice-led findings. In the following sections the theories that inform the investigation are introduced and 'narrative' is explored in terms of the meaning we make of our lives and the understanding of self.

³ My transpersonal and embodied practice is central to this investigation and is discussed in detail in subsequent sections.

The Stories of Our Selves

At a time when the actions of humankind dramatically impact the planet and all life upon it, perhaps it is most pertinent to ask: *Who are we?* In this research, I have asked myself this question and I waited for the answers, listening to responses from within my psyche, that have come in the form of feelings, sensations, images, memories, creations and ideas. The insights and creative outcomes, which have emerged through this investigation, have then been used in dialogue with a wider audience, encouraging them to reflect upon the same question.

Rich and complex conceptual streams underlie the question: *What does it mean to know the self?* These include theoretical frameworks for understanding identity, the structure of the human psyche and the nature of consciousness. Transpersonal, Buddhist and systemic frameworks have informed the method used in this research, and interpretation of the creative material produced. As the investigative language used is narrative (both visual and written), the fluid nature of memory and the mutability of 'truth', as well as cultural and temporal influences on perception are explored further.

Frameworks of the self have changed throughout history, influencing the way knowledge is gathered and presented. In contemporary psychology, under the influence of Kantian philosophy and positivism, the study of self has been oriented toward measurable human behaviour, identifiable personality traits and developmental patterns. The perception of who we are as human beings has become focussed on environmental, brain-based and genetic factors impacting biological, learned or inherited tendencies (Rohlf 2016).

Most recently, postmodern theory focuses on knowledge being shaped by the lens of the observer; our self-identity is fluid, plastic and ephemeral, shaped by our particular knowledge or experience, influenced by the culture and time in which they are alive (Vattimo 2002, pp. 8-9). Postmodernism indicates that there is no absolute truth; that instead all knowledge is political, interpreted through the dominant voice (one that is most often male, educated and well resourced); and that perception is skewed in ways that sustain the domination of the most powerful, literate and entitled (see Willett et al. 2016). In this prevailing

framework, 'selfhood' is irrevocably tied to the language in which it is expressed; all self-knowledge is a narrative identity, a testimony made by oneself or others on the self and past events (Ricoeur 2004, pp. 7-8). Memory is censored by the narrator, most often unconsciously, around blocked or manipulated memories, those altered to meet ethical and political obligations (see Ricoeur 2004, pp. 3-4)⁴.

How does one know 'self' if perception is inflected by factors such as culture, time, gender, even the life-experiences of those who are seeking know it? Perhaps the answer resides in valuing the testimony for its own unique yet informative voice. While a definitive truth in regard to knowing the self is inaccessible, the premise of this research is that an investigation of self (while mindful of the challenges presented) can be valid and productive.

Postmodernism has identified the validity of traditionally marginalized voices, giving rise to research methods that are feminist, embodied and value the experience of the individual (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 5-14). This investigation uses a voice that is creative, intuitive and values an emergent wisdom; the premise is that the process of exploring what it means to know our selves can be transformative, enhancing insight, informing the lived experience of the researcher, participants and a wider audience (Clements 2011, pp. 131-166).

In the fields of psychology, transformative healing and the creative arts, perception and felt-experience take precedence over the need to establish an indisputable actuality. Art is not necessarily judged in terms of the degree to which it realistically represents the natural world; what may be more relevant is its conceptual impact and how successfully it challenges or enhances the viewer's experience. The territory of the arts is subjective; it may be inspirational or political, transporting the viewer or reader to new domains both conceptual and felt (Medlock 2015, pp. 3-10). In the psychological field, the nature of truth and 'self' is also labile, equally impacted by dominant cultural and political agendas, the prevalent theoretical frameworks and their influence on understanding human consciousness or behaviour. Collective perceptions, embedded in our society and culture, may influence how we define who we are⁵, what is normal,

⁴ Also refer Pellauer & Dauenhauer 2016.

⁵ Laing (1960); Laing (1967) and Szasz (1961), for example, have written extensively about the myths that mitigate diagnoses of mental health or illness and their cultural and political origins.

healthy or worthy of our aspiration. Depending on the culture in which they emerge, the same symptoms and behaviours can be seen in remarkably different ways. For example, various perceptual experiences may be defined by western psychological paradigms as 'psychotic', diagnosed as mental illness and medicated; in other cultural frameworks that recognize shamanic initiations (see Abram 1997, pp. 35-39), the same experiences are seen to be a gift of spiritual inspiration, indicative of wise guidance calling for deep respect and minimal interference (Grof & Grof 1992, p. 36). My training in transpersonal psychology informs my understanding of self; within this framework, all aspects of the self are valid and integrating them into our conscious awareness can be an opportunity for transformative growth (Anderson & Braud 2011, p. 7).

This investigation into the nature of self will be built from narratives. The way we construct meaning in our life experiences is shaped by our early experiences with our care-givers (refer Bowlby 1988) and narratives inherent in our culture and community. In this investigation, I present my life writing as non-fictional accounts yet I am well aware that they are filtered through the lens of my personal and cultural perceptual biases. I hold my 'true' stories loosely, and in doing so, I am able to witness that in sharing them, my alliance to certain narratives has changed as I develop a capacity to attend to their nuances and the alternative perspectives of other characters.

Narrative and the self

Narrative researchers argue that we use story to imbue meaning, authoring our lives so that we are the heroes of our own myth. McAdams states that the subject matter of our self-authored stories varies over our lifespan, reflecting a developmental trajectory. Each individual narrates their own life-story, highlighting select characters, attending to select themes and not others, attempting to assemble meaning and cohesion (McAdams 2001, pp. 104-105). She suggests that our sense of identity appears to be oriented toward our relationships, first with our parents, then our peers, our profession, our roles, our

community and in the latter part of our lives, our contribution to society and the legacy we leave when we die (McAdams 2001, pp. 106-107).

Siegel and Bryson (2012, p. 60) suggest that our life narratives determine our feelings about our past, our understanding of why the major protagonists in our stories behaved as they did, and the meaning of these sub-plots in the overall stories of our selves. Meaning, however, is malleable, it changes over time, and our past can be re-authored in the re-telling. White determined that revisiting life stories containing events experienced as painful or traumatic enables these stories to be met in new ways (refer White & Denborough 2011, pp. 123 - 135). It may be our *perception* of incidents that is most indicative of their impact on our lives. There is considerable variability regarding the extent to which events are perceived to be traumatic, despite the unquestionable impact of childhood trauma on our sense of identity and wellbeing. To judge from the outside the impact of an event on another person does not create an environment conducive to healing; it is the *perception* of the individual that must be understood with clarity and compassion for transformation to occur (Bardsley 1993, pp. 53-54).

Narratives are central to the definition of who we are; however, such stories may change over time, they may be perceived in different ways and may reflect aspects of us previously hidden from our consciousness. By reflecting upon our self-narratives, we may review their meaning and their impact on the way we live. Parts of us are buried and hidden from our awareness, at least initially, so a singular mind or sense of self that follows a developmental trajectory throughout our lives is not an accurate model; instead, there are multiple aspects to our consciousness, which we may adhere to at any one time. These concepts are discussed further in the following sections.

A multi-layered Self

The notion that the self is layered and that each layer of self may offer particular insight and capacity for transformation, are central themes in a number of theoretical models that inform this research. Freud's theory of human awareness included both conscious and unconscious (hidden) aspects. His

description of the human psyche comprises biological drives and cultural stories as well as idealised aspects of ourselves and human behaviour measured according to the societal norms to which we have been exposed. Freud's theory of the unconscious consisted of instinctual drives—unbridled imperatives for life, death and sex—that he postulated are unwelcome in society, and therefore become buried, contained by our 'ego', the self we wish to show the world, and the part that engages with reality (see Freud 1963, pp. 116-151).

Freud's view of the unconscious was more like a receptacle for aspects of human consciousness that were disowned, perhaps too painful or confronting to be held in the conscious mind (Freud 1920, p. 18). Jung, however, considered that while the unconscious may contain repressed material, it was also the source of the unlimited potential of human beings, a vessel of knowledge, wisdom and creativity that was both unfathomable and profound (Jung 1963, p. 384). Jung posited an aspect of the human unconscious that linked all humanity, one he referred to as the 'collective unconscious'. The collective unconscious rests beneath the personal unconscious and is universal in nature, with contents common to all human kind, independent of race, culture and time; it is inherently present when we are born, as part of the structure of our brains (Jung 1981, p. 3).

Jung (1963, p. 529) considered that the greatest potential for human transformation could be achieved through a dialogue between the unconscious and conscious mind. He determined that consciousness itself was multi-layered and that 'all psychic development starts from one common stock whose roots reach back into all the strata of the past' (Jung 1970, p. 84). The nature of consciousness is to be organised into instincts or drives, which he described as 'archetypes':

There is good reason for supposing that the archetypes are the unconscious images of the instincts themselves, in other words, that they are patterns of instinctual behaviour. (Jung 1981, p. 44)

Knox re-defines Jung's archetypes as emergent structures in the human mind that result from the developmental interaction between individuals' environment and genetic makeup (Knox 2003, p. 7). She suggests that archetypes form 'image

schemas' that are experienced in ways that are 'non-verbal, implicit and embodied' (Knox 2003, p. 9). The primacy of particular schemas is shaped by the nature of our attachment with our early caregivers (see Knox 2003, pp. 103-117).

According to Jungian theory, consciousness is interpreted through a narrative structure. The narratives we form about who we are reference our personal memories and our inherited tendencies. They are formed in response to instinctual drives that are inherent in the structure of our psyche at birth as part of the schematic way our brains process information. Knowledge of the self involves bringing to conscious awareness personal and collective material, and in doing so, learning to relate in new ways. There is also an aspect to our consciousness that has an embodied, emergent wisdom, whose purpose is to guide the organism toward wholeness. Jung writes of this as the 'Self' (with a capital 'S'), an organising principle for the psyche, directing the individual toward wholeness (Jung 1976, pp. 460-461). He also refers to this Self as the 'transcendent function' with the purpose of evolving humanity toward a unified potential⁶ (Jung 1976, pp. 460-461). Jung's theory of the unconscious evolved through his own and his clients' experiences and was informed by dreams, artistic expression, visual imagery, intuitive feelings and life narratives. Jung considered the language of the unconscious to be embodied and indirect, revealing itself obliquely through creative play or dreams (Jung 1963, pp. 530 - 531). From this perspective, to engage in the creative process is to begin a potentially enlightening dialogue with the deepest aspects of who we are.

Grof further developed Jung's theory of the collective unconscious by exploring its relationship to the birth process and the subsequent life experiences of an individual. Grof (1998, pp. 13-17) delineates between a state of 'ordinary consciousness' or 'consensus reality' where we experience the world bound by time, shaped by our personal or cultural frameworks, and 'non-ordinary states of consciousness' (NOSC), states of awareness that are not usually experienced in everyday consciousness. NOSC are characterized by changes of sensory perception that include the intrusion of body sensations, visions and mythic and

⁶ The transcendent function was a central aspect Jung's theory of individuation, modified over forty-two years of research (see Miller 2004, pp. 9-18).

universal states of awareness. Grof considered that the emergence of unconscious material into our conscious awareness had the potential to be transformative if it occurred in an environment oriented toward integration and healing (Grof & Grof 1992, pp. 145-149).

From his own experiential research in NOSC as well as the reported experiences of the thousands of people who participated in his research over fifty years, Grof (2012, pp. 29 - 77) identified patterns in how unconscious material was organised. He concluded that particular types of emotional and physical experience were not stored randomly in isolated parts of the unconscious but appeared to be linked in complex constellations, which he referred to as 'systems of condensed experience' or COEX systems. Each COEX system, he surmised, comprised conscious and unconscious material linked together through a similar emotional resonance (see Grof 2012, pp. 29 - 77). For example, a COEX system may relate to feelings of shame, grief or terror; other COEX systems may relate to joy, bliss, and peace. COEX systems were comprised of personal, intergenerational, transpersonal and collective material; the tendency we have to orient our attention toward particular life narratives is guided by the potency of various COEX systems operating in our personal and collective unconscious (Grof 2012, pp. 38-41). COEX systems can also be passed through generations so that individuals' life stories are coloured by potent, inherited COEX systems (Grof 2012, p.38).

Previously unconscious COEX patterns can spontaneously emerge into our conscious awareness and are often accompanied by somatic symptoms, evocative dreams, unusual perceptual sensations and immense sensitivity. Grof (2015, pp. 68-69) considered the creative arts to be a potent means of understanding and integrating emergent unconscious material. Like Jung's notion of the 'transcendent function', Grof (2012, p. 42) perceived there to be an aspect of our consciousness that guides the process of integration and transformation, one he referred to as 'the inner healer'.⁷

⁷ Personal communication during my training with Stanislav Grof. Note Grof (2012, p. 42) also referred to this guiding principle as an 'inner radar'.

Schwartz (Schwartz & Falconer 2017, p. 94) presents another model of human consciousness that is multifaceted and layered with a 'Self' oriented toward integration and transformation. He suggests that we have many selves (described as 'sub-personalities' or 'parts'), each with particular memories, ways of understanding and relating to the world. Some of these selves form in response to traumatic events; they are vulnerable, hidden and deeply held (selves he terms 'exiles'), or they may have evolved as a means of protecting the more vulnerable selves ('protectors') (refer Schwartz & Falconer 2017, pp. 65-70). For Schwartz, healing and transformation take place through a dialogue among these many selves; therapy is oriented toward facilitating harmonious co-habitation between these many selves through engaging with each sub-personality (or 'part') in a compassionate manner and encouraging them to release the 'burdens' they carry (Schwartz 2004, pp. 1-9). 'Burdens' are 'trauma-based beliefs and emotions that drive parts' extreme roles', some of which are inherited, others possibly formed due to acutely painful experiences with key figures during childhood (Schwartz 2017, pp. 61-62).

Contrary to theories that indicate that existence of multiple selves is pathological, Schwartz (Schwartz & Falconer 2017, pp. 154-155) suggests that the nature of consciousness is inherently multiple and layered. Like Jung, and Grof, he refers to an organising aspect of consciousness (termed the 'Self') that is 'curious, creative, compassionate, calm, clear' and unified, assisting in the process of releasing burdens and witnessing parts, as well as compassionately and fluidly engaging with all aspects of self (Schwartz 2004, pp. 1-9).

Another framework that has informed this investigation is Buddhist philosophy, which posits that consciousness is the condition for life, that the physical body interacts with consciousness, but is not its source. Buddhist practice is oriented toward evolving consciousness rather than focusing on identity, the material world, or the physical body (see Kornfield 1993). Beneath our personal identity is a purified state of mind, referred to in Buddhism as 'the mind of clear light' or 'Bodhicitta', a Sanskrit word meaning 'noble or awakened heart' (Chodron 2008, p.3). Negative mental states are not part of the intrinsic nature of humanity; they are considered transient obstructions to our natural unified state of being (see Hanh 1998, p. 52). Buddhist practice is oriented

toward overcoming the mental and emotional afflictions that overlay our 'awakened heart' to realise our 'true' or 'Buddha nature' (Chodron 2008, p. 85).

There is a marked difference in the use of the terms 'self', 'identity' and 'ego' in Buddhist and western psychology. Clinical psychologist and once Buddhist monk, Kornfield (2009, p. 293) clarifies the contrasting use of the terms by suggesting that while western psychology equates the 'ego self' with resilience and strong boundaries, in Buddhist psychology, 'ego' is less favourably perceived and is used to refer to mental states that include delusion, arrogance and self-centredness (refer Kornfield 2009, p. 67). In many ways, western psychological practices aim to strengthen the ego, whereas Buddhist psychological practices, including mindfulness, aim to develop mental qualities such as wisdom, compassion, flexibility and tolerance (Kornfield 2009, p. 283) to loosen the focus on individualism.

Transcendence and Non-self

One of the basic principles of Buddhism is that the main cause of human suffering is our perception that we are separate from all other forms of life (Hahn 2010, p. 117). In our attempt to cultivate certainty in the face of existential uncertainty, human beings grasp at objects and roles to avoid the awareness that we live finite, fragile lives (Hahn 1998, p. 9). A Buddhist monk, Thich Nhat Hahn (2010, p. 132) suggests that the perception of interconnectedness can be threatening to people whose identity is formed through a culture built on individualism and the competition that it fosters. In contrast to materialism, Buddhism proposes that the path to healing and growth is through dissolving the ego and cultivating an awareness of 'non-self'. From this perspective, that it is by releasing identification with the ego (the 'small sense of self') and becoming 'self-less', it is possible to develop an awareness of life as a 'play of consciousness'; this bigger picture awareness is described as 'non-self' (Hahn 1998, p. 126).

The experience of selflessness or non-self may be blissful; it may evoke a deep sense of emptiness, one that is full of the potential of creativity rather than loneliness or loss (Kornfield 2009, p. 253). These experiences (also referred to as

Nirvana or enlightenment) may be spontaneous, or the result of meditation and mindful practice. Kornfield writes:

Sometimes the letting go is so deep our whole identity drops away. In these transformative moments nirvana is experienced as the void, dark and timeless, or as the luminous emptiness of all things. Sometimes the peace and happiness of nirvana is ordinary, a resting of the heart in awareness, undisturbed and steadfast as all things change. (Kornfield 2009, pp. 253 – 254)

A transcendent or void-like experience is a key aspect of transpersonal theory and investigation and transformative healing. For example, Jung refers to the process of transformation as being guided by the ‘transcendent function’ (or Self –archetype), culminating in ‘the One’ or ‘Primordial [wo]Man’ (Jung 1958, p. 265). Transformation (or ‘individuation’ as Jung terms it) is the ‘process of becoming human’ (Jung 1958, p. 262). Grof (1998, p. 42) refers to the unified aspect of Self as ‘the Divine’. In this research, such experiences are referred to as ‘unified’, ‘transcendent’, pertaining to ‘Self’, or as a sense of ‘returning home’. The unified Self is considered to be central to the human psyche, over which many of the narratives we use to define who we are, are layered. If a unified Self exists within each of us as an embodied wisdom, then the use of transpersonal methods can allow it to emerge; *A unique methodology* discusses the concepts of emergence, embodiment, and the creative arts as a means of integrating unconscious material.

Mindfulness as a means of attending to self-narratives

The practice of cultivating one’s awareness, so as to sink beneath the many self-narratives clamouring for our attention, is called ‘mindfulness’ (Hahn 1998, pp. 9-12). Mindfulness is a Buddhist practice directed toward cultivating an awareness that holds the space for a myriad of stories without defining them according to a dichotomy of value, as good or bad, right or wrong, without being excessively attached to an outcome or a particular state of being (Hahn 1998, pp. 9-12). Through witnessing our stories with mindful awareness, we can develop

our capacity to respond with equanimity and compassion to our narratives and lesson our tendency for harmful reactivity (Hanh 2010, pp. 9-15).

Summary and concluding remarks

Each of the theories that inform this investigation indicate that we have multiple aspects to our consciousness; some suggest that we have many selves, aspects that are buried and parts that are inherited. Our consciousness also contains pre-existing tendencies that influence the way we see the world or process information. Who we are extends beyond our memories, our culture or even the genetic or inherited narratives of our ancestors. The building blocks of our consciousness contain collective material, and the psyche of the individual mirrors that of the collective. There are also aspects to our consciousness that are difficult to comprehend or describe in language, those that are void-like yet full of creative potential. Each of the theories outlined suggest that there is a unified core to consciousness, one that orients us toward wholeness, and that is accessible to every human being.

There are, of course, infinite stories within the human psyche and it would be impossible to give voice to them all. This research explores the transformative potential of bringing mindful attention to potent emergent stories through a dialogue between conscious and unconscious aspects of our psyche using the arts as the vehicle of expression. The voice of our selves, heard in the stories of the contemporary everyday person, can be valid and informative (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 5-14), both individually and collectively; it is with this in mind that I commenced this investigation.

A Unique Methodology

This is a practice-led investigation of self; the methodology is experiential, self-reflexive and the creative arts form part of the language used to illustrate, inform and guide the experience. It utilises a transpersonal methodology and auto-ethnographic reflections to explore the research question: 'What does it mean to know the self?' The methodology allows for a personal, contemporary, and subjective voice to be heard through modalities that are embodied, intuitive and creative.

During this investigation, I have become aware that the boundary between conscious and unconscious material can dissolve, often during times of profound change or when surrendered to the flow of creative expression. I have explored this territory, supported by a methodology that embraces sacred, intuitive and transformative aspects of research, one that can give voice to both the personal and transpersonal stories—*Organic Inquiry* (Clements in Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 131-165).

A number of the techniques that I have employed use my own psyche as a tool in the research. My inspiration for this research has been to move through the layers of self-narratives to seek the Self in its most expansive form, a phenomenon that I have experienced as a sense of 'returning home'. I have documented my experience, guided by my creative expression comprising film, photography, fine art and life writing. I have also gathered the stories of others via the medium of documentary film.

In attempting to surrender the reins of the creative process and become the vehicle through which the voices of the self can be heard, I understand that, one can never really 'step aside'; the stories gathered will be coloured by the perceptions of the storyteller. For this reason, I have kept a journal that includes reflections in creating the works and the responses of those who have participated or witnessed it; this was the fieldwork for my auto-ethnographic reflections, which also offered the opportunity, as the narrator, to be known by an audience, and adjustments to be made for my personal biases.

I have sought to deepen my understanding of the self through reflecting on

personal experience and the stories of people I have interviewed. The films and creative works have become a means of investigating, communicating, and I hope, inspiring an audience to reflect on their experiences of knowing the self.

Overview

The following areas will be discussed:

- a) The narratives gathered in this research
- b) An introduction to transpersonal research methods
- c) The arts as a language for transpersonal narratives
- d) Auto-ethnography
- e) An outline of the intuitive research processes used
- f) Organic Inquiry as the research methodology
- g) My personal reflections on using Organic Inquiry
- h) Validity of the methodology.

a) The narrative threads gathered

While in the fields of film, psychology and creative arts, the term ‘narrative’ has been variously defined, there is a common thread—the making of meaning and the communication of experience. There are many narrative voices in this research; most obviously there are the stories told by the researcher, presented through the creative mediums of film, auto-ethnographic writing and visual art. There are also stories of the participants appearing in documentary interviews and in responses to the creative material. There are the narratives of the culture and community within which the stories were gathered—contemporary Australia—seen through the lens of a woman, educated, approximately fifty years of age, with a developed interest in psychological, spiritual and creative aspects of human experience. I am the lens; my artistic expression and auto-ethnographic reflections are the voices of this investigation. There are also transpersonal stories—ancestral, archetypal and mythological narratives as they push through from the numinous into everyday consciousness of the participants.

Consistent with Neilson (1990) who highlights their importance, I have attempted to attend to those voices 'less heard' in the dominant culture within which this research takes place: stories that are hidden, unusual, vulnerable or exceptional, voices often drowned out in the increasingly demanding noisy, time-poor and materially focused world in which we reside. Where possible, I have sought to make my own voice transparent, for it is the researcher's 'eye', shaped by her past experience, her training and her willingness to see and be changed by the research, that guides the design, the choice of methodology, the gathering and editing of the stories as well as the interpretation of the findings.

This investigation's multiple and varied voices, as well as the inclusion of transpersonal material, called for a sophisticated methodology, one that is expansive and mutable, rather than reductionist or fixed in nature; this methodology is discussed in the following sections.

b) Transpersonal Research Methods

Both the Buddhist and transpersonal theory frameworks that guide this research emphasise the existence of multiple intelligences and the need to facilitate transformative processes directed toward compassionate action to benefit both human and non-human life. Transpersonal psychology incorporates consciousness that extends beyond the limits of the ego and personality; it is concerned with transformational experiences, the study of humanity's highest potential, intuitive and transcendent experiences (Braud and Anderson 2008, p. xxi). The focus of transpersonal psychology is on inter-connectedness and universal stories, as well as the phenomenon of integration and wholeness. Transpersonal research delves into profound aspects of human experience, including unitive mystical experiences, meditative awareness, experiences of wonder, ecstasy and alternative or expansive states of consciousness (Braud & Anderson 2011, p. xxii).

Lajoie and Shapiro (1992, pp. 79-98) describe transpersonal methodologies as inclusive of personal and time bound states of consciousness while extending their orientation into areas that encompass personal reflection and felt-experience. Such methodologies utilise investigative techniques that reflect a

universal consciousness, one that often communicates through different languages including intuitive, creative and embodied knowledge. While reductionist methods test hypotheses and aim to establish truths through replicable and objective investigation of the material world, transpersonal methodologies reference an emergent wisdom, a knowledge and healing potential that pre-exists within the human psyche (Braud & Anderson 2011, pp. 5-14).

c) Creative arts as a transpersonal language

While intuitive, embodied and experiential investigation is not common in scientific research, it is central to creative practice and practice-led investigations. The arts are a symbiotic language for transpersonal states of consciousness; as Duxbury (2009, p. 97) states, creative work does not necessarily follow a linear process, nor adhere to objectivity and logic. The artist may become a means by which wisdom emerges through their creative practice in a manner referred to as 'flow' (Csikszentmihalyi 2007, 16-20), the 'emergence of wonder' (Medlock 2015, p. 5), or 'taking a leap of faith' (Duxbury 2009, p. 98).

Van den Akker (2014, pp. 751-765) describes the potency of art-making as a means of investigating the deepest aspects of self, engaging different ways of knowing, facilitating expression across disciplines and moving beyond the cultural or conceptual limitations of verbal languages. For this reason, art-based research is a potent means of exploring and communicating an investigation into self. The inclusion of visual, visceral and emotional expression can allow for the representation of intuitive and felt experiences in ways that are engaging and accessible to a wider audience (Hodgins & Boydell 2014, p. 6).

In his exploration of the creative process, Medlock (2015, p. 3) conducted first person interviews with twenty artists comprising writers, poets, performers, musicians, visual artists, filmmakers and multi-media practitioners. His focus was to determine their experience of the creative process, using a phenomenological and grounded-theory framework. Two key variables emerged from his qualitative analyses: 'emergence' and 'wonder'. Medlock (2015, p. 5) described 'wonder' as the felt experience of the artist when they have their attention

captured and they 'fall in love' with a particular image, idea or feeling. He concluded that it is 'wonder' that sustains the creative process to its successful completion, whereby it becomes embodied in the completed work, and transferred to the audience. The process by which 'wonder' becomes embodied in the work, and the stages the artist goes through, were attributed to a variable he termed 'emergence'.

From his analysis of artist interviews Medlock (2015, p. 8) concludes that the creative practitioners facilitate the emergence of their work, rather than force a work to fit a preconceived intention; while skill and knowledge influence the way the work emerges, a sense of wonder, embodied in the creative process, inspires and sustains an artist's creative practice. Consistent with the artists in Medlock's study, as a creative practitioner, I become 'wonderstruck' and the creative process itself becomes a means of transformation.

The writers and artists in Medlock's (2015) project frequently expressed the sense of acting as a channel for the creative work rather than being the source of it. The contextual consciousness from which the images and stories emerged was identified according to three conceptual threads: 1) the individual—the artist's life experiences and personal memories; 2) the collective—symbols and images from the history of literature, art, culture and collective social experience; and 3) transpersonal consciousness—a spiritual dimension, one that the artists referred to as embodied experiences of expansiveness, peace and unity (Medlock 2015, pp. 16-19). It is perhaps no coincidence that the emergent narratives in this practice-led investigation also congregate around these three themes: 1) personal, 2) collective, and 3) transcendent or unified aspects of self.

Medlock (2015, p. 10) concludes that as creative practitioners, we are wonderstruck by narratives, visual or felt, as they inspire and sustain our practice, that without wonder our creative projects may be abandoned and we move on. This research has been born out of wonder, curiosity and embodied experience of the self in its many forms; my experience as an artist is consistent with Medlock's findings: creativity is directed by wonder and an embodied experience, which frequently expands beyond my individual understanding or conceptual intent.

d) Auto-ethnography and self-reflexive practice

Auto-ethnography is a form of embodied writing practice and qualitative research (used in this investigation) that Ellis defines 'not only as a way of knowing about the world but also a way of living consciously, emotionally and reflexively' (Jones et al. 2013, p. 10). Custer (2014, pp. 1-13), writing of his own experience of auto-ethnographic writing, outlines its advantages. 'It changes time' (Custer 2014, p. 2): Like a dance without boundaries, it highlights the subjective nature of memory, allowing for a reformation of view and the possibility of the transformation of past events in the re-telling of them. It is transformative in that it offers an opportunity to reconstruct identity by re-interpreting and reconstructing the remembered event in the writing of it. 'It promotes vulnerability' (Custer 2014, p.3): The reliving of the events in embodied writing is orientated toward and encouraging of vulnerability, while engaging with the material as it emerges from our unconscious. 'It fosters empathy in the researcher and audience' (Custer 2014, p.4): In recognizing the lens in which we view life events is one of many, auto-ethnography invites the writer and the audience to reflect on the nature of truth and the meaning derived from the experience. This can encourage a sympathetic resonance in the audience as well as empathy for other characters involved as potentially having different perspectives, meanings and truths. 'It is innovative and creative' (Custer, 2014, p.6): As a unique individual experience told creatively and imaginatively, it allows the writer to slow down, to look for resonance in their own body, promoting deep inquiry and re-interpretation through introspection. It is a person-centered tool, inspiring change, offering multiple ways of seeing the world. 'It eliminates boundaries' (Custer 2014, p.7): Auto-ethnography uses metaphor, symbol and allegory to communicate across cultural divides, emphasizing a shared humanity through feeling and meaning making. 'It honours subjectivity' (Custer 2014, p.8): Auto-ethnography brings the reader into self-awareness and honours their potential to affect the world around them. By removing objectivity it facilitates authenticity. 'It provides therapeutic benefit' (Custer 2014, p.9): Working through and working with story it allows for a new understanding of self.

Raab (2013, pp. 2-4) refers to the link between auto-ethnographic and transpersonal research models particularly across the areas of self-discovery and transformation; both emphasise embodiment, spirituality, consciousness and self-renewal. The vivid voice and self-reflection that are part of the auto-ethnographic process enable the readers to make a connection with the stories told, explore the resonance of issues shared, and potentially provide a map for coping with them in their own life experience (Raab 2013, pp. 2-4)

Raab (2013, p. 13) and Ellis & Bochner (2000, pp. 733 - 768) also discuss the necessity for fieldwork—the notes, feelings, conversations had, and the artworks made while writing or creating through an auto-ethnographic process. These researchers argue that a personal narrative provides a first-hand interaction of lived experience within a particular culture, and is the best way to examine its underpinnings, motives, beliefs and behaviours. Field notes refer to aspects of the research that occur alongside the creative process, contributing to the researcher making meaning of the experiences, such as personal journaling, thoughts, ideas, intuitions, dreams and interactions with others (Raab 2013, p. 13).

My auto-ethnographic reflections accompany my creative process, forming the field notes for this investigation, speaking to the cultural and personal influences embedded in the self-reflexive research. Selecting and editing the written, film and visual narratives was an intuitive process, guided by a felt experience, a quality that Anderson describes as trust in an emergent wisdom and guidance (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 15 - 28). These auto-ethnographic reflections also speak to the intuitive process that guided this creative investigation, which are discussed in detail in the next sections.

e) The use of intuitive processes in research methods

Intuitive processes have been used extensively in this investigation in the formulation of the research topic, as well as the practices of data collection and analysis, adding experiential, subjective and right brain methods of knowing to the intellectual rigor and linear deductive methods of traditional scientific research. Intuitive methods utilise the psyche of the observer as a vehicle for

investigation, and challenge the conventional notion of a static worldview, separate from the researcher who observes it (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 15 - 28).

In his extensive research into intuition, Bastick (1982, pp. 350 - 352) identified a number of characteristics that were common to intuitive experiences; some of these include sudden or immediate appearance in awareness, feelings of wonder, luminosity, and empathy. Anderson (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 22-25) defined a further five intuitive processes as they pertain to transpersonal research:

1) *Unconscious, symbolic or imaginal processes.*

I am working from the foundation that individuals with strong intuitive processes tend to have rich symbolic lives; they may also be more introverted with a tendency to be nourished and guided by turning their attention inward. On introverts, Jung writes:

They are living evidence that this rich and varied world with its overflowing and intoxicating life is not purely external but exists within. (Jung 1976, pp. 404 - 405)

Cain (2013, p. 141) argues for the value of qualities associated with introversion (humility, reflective, deep thinking, empathy, and high sensitivity) in western society that tends to idealise the qualities of extroversion (aggression, dominance, sociability, outgoingness, high energy) (Cain 2013, pp. 186 -190). Aaron (2003, p. 8) discusses a potentially related quality 'high sensitivity', identified as a more easily aroused nervous system leading 'highly sensitive people' to be more acutely responsive to external and internal material. Similarly, Bernstein (2005, pp. 57-61) describes individuals who are very receptive to spiritual, embodied and psychic material, and postulates that such hypersensitivity is due to their ego state being particularly permeable to the 'Self'⁸ and the collective unconscious⁹ through dreams, archetypal or numinous

⁸ Refer Jung (1976, pp. 460-461)

⁹ Refer Jung (1981, p. 3)

experiences, and active imagination. Each of these qualities—introversion, sensitivity and permeability to the collective unconscious—are qualities that are not often employed in academic research but form central themes in transpersonal and intuitive investigations; they are traits with which I am most familiar¹⁰.

2) *Psychic or parapsychological experiences.*

Psychic or parapsychological experiences include clairvoyance, telepathy and pre-cognitive experiences (the ability to access information about a person or event though separated by space and time).

3) *Sensory modes of intuition.*

Sensory methods of 'intuitive knowing' are shared through the five senses: sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste. In addition to these, Anderson (2011, p. 25) adds two further intuitive modes: proprioception—the sense of orientation through space — and a visceral sense—information passed through the viscera, joints, ligaments and muscles that communicate subliminal sensory awareness, signaling, for instance, beauty, danger, novelty and significance.

4) *Empathetic identification.*

Empathetic knowing is described as the capacity to see the world through the eyes of the other, so that there is no 'subject' and 'object'. The researcher 'looks around from inside the experience and witnesses the essential qualities of the 'other' coming to life as the researcher's own experience' (Anderson & Braud 2011, p. 25).

¹⁰ Cain (2013, p. 130) and Aron (1999, p. xvii) include self-tests in their research for the qualities of introversion and high sensitivity; I scored the highest scores possible on both tests.

5) *Researching through our wounds.*

When referring to her thirty years of experience conducting and supervising research, Anderson states:

I am poignantly aware that a researcher's intuitive style tends to settle along the fault lines or wounds in the personality of the researcher in a manner akin to the concept of the wounded healer described by Catholic Priest Henri Nouwen (1990) and Roshi Joan Halifax (1983). For Nouwen, our human wounds are sites of both suffering and hospitality to the divine. (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 25-26)

In Jungian analysis, the 'shadow' parts of the psyche contain our greatest vulnerabilities, hidden in the unconscious. Through analysis, the act of bringing these hidden aspects to conscious awareness can lead to profound transformation (Van Eenwyk 2013, pp. 67-69). The unacknowledged or difficult stories that we carry within powerfully drive our lives; thus, integrating shadow aspects of the self can bring them to our awareness, facilitating an experience of wholeness (Grof 1998, pp. 216-217). An investigation grounded in transpersonal theory is a means of integrating stories that emerge, and if witnessed mindfully, offers a transformative opportunity.

The inquirer's voice, authentically revealing her body, mind and spirit, allows these to be interpreted by others (Anderson & Braud 2011, pp. 281-302). One of the desired qualities of a transpersonal researcher is to have the courage to sit with the tension of 'not knowing', of sustaining a conversation between hidden and revealed aspects of the research so that intuitive and emergent wisdom can guide the investigation.

f) Organic Inquiry Methodology.

The research methodology used in this investigation (*Organic Inquiry*) was developed within the field of transpersonal psychology and shares many of its goals, primarily, the transformative approach to research and the understanding of multiple intelligences including personal, intuitive and experiential

intelligences.

Clements (2011, p. 131) describes Organic inquiry as a 'living process' where the researcher's own psyche is the instrument of investigation in conjunction with liminal and spiritual sources, and the stories of participants. Organic Inquiry methodology is psychological and spiritual in nature; its validity is deeply intertwined with the transformative capacity of the research to elicit profound psycho-spiritual growth in the researcher, participants and an audience exposed to the research (Clements 2011, p. 157).

Using a metaphor reminiscent of organic growth, Clements describes the Organic Inquiry process in the following stages:

Sacred: the preparation of the soil through cultivating a sacred perspective.

Personal: the planting of the seed through the lived experience of the researcher's own spiritual growth and narrative.

Chthonic: the emerging root system. Like a living tree, the research process evolves and changes, fed by an underground life of subjective and spiritual sources.

Related: the tree grows. The 'branches' of the participants' stories inform the 'trunk story' of the research.

Transformative: harvesting the fruit. The fruits of the organic process are the potential for profound transformation of both the researcher and readers. Clements (2011, p. 134)

Organic Inquiry is a process that employs the heart as well as the mind, and involves the researcher repeatedly cycling through a three-step process: *preparation, inspiration* and *integration* with transformation as its goal (Clements 2011, p. 134).

Researching Liminal Stories

'Limen' is often used to refer to a threshold or doorway; the use of the word in contemporary research can be traced to Turner (1966) and van Gennep's (1960) work related to ritual rites of passage in indigenous cultures. Such rituals enabled a crossing of the boundary between everyday consciousness and non-ordinary states of consciousness. In this case, 'limen' was used to describe the in-

between, undifferentiated state that one enters when one's identification with the everyday reality gives way to the mythic or ritual states of consciousness (Turner 1966, pp. 94-95; van Gennep 1960, p. 189). Liminal stories are the realm of the symbolic, mythic and archetypal states of consciousness frequently explored by transpersonal research methods and rarely acknowledged in traditional scientific methodologies. In this research the term 'liminal' refers to the threshold between ordinary and transcendent states of consciousness *and* the state of awareness in which the transpersonal material can be accessed. This investigation is oriented toward transformation that can occur through such liminal encounters. It is my working hypothesis that there is merit in attending to stories of the self that include transcendent and liminal experiences; such stories may further develop our understanding of unconscious processes in the human psyche, offering the potential for individual as well as collective transformation, as well as a deeper understanding of human potential.

In working with research that includes liminal states of consciousness, the arts become a potent tool of expression and a powerful voice for liminal stories, numinous experiences and their transformative potential. Rothko wrote that art was 'an anecdote of the spirit and the only means of making concrete the purpose of the spirit's varied quickness and stillness' (Rothko 2006, p. 45). Rumi and Hafiz speak of a love affair with the divine, a transcendent longing to return to home to the source of all life through the language of prose (Barks 2004; Ladinsky 1999).

Liminal Research Methods

This investigation utilises liminal research methods to access previously hidden aspects of the self through an emergent, practice-led methodology, one that can transition from an ordinary state of consciousness (bound to concepts of identity, community, status, time, body and egoic definition) to the spiritual or transpersonal states of consciousness. Liminal information comes from such sources as meditation, spiritual experiences, dreams, heightened states of creativity and non-ordinary states of consciousness accessed through breathing techniques, focused physical practices, ritualised dance or movement. The integration of liminal states heralds an informative and expanded perspective

allowing for healing and transformation in individual and collective consciousness (Clements 2011, pp. 139-140). Accessing a liminal awareness is the first step in Organic Inquiry.

Step 1 - Preparation to enter the Liminal

Entry to the liminal space through Organic Inquiry can be either spontaneous or intentional, involving the following steps: 1) an intention or question; 2) a letting go of egoic identification; 3) adopting an attitude of respect, reverence, and cooperation with the spiritual (Clements 2011, pp. 141-145).

Clements (2011, pp. 144-145) proposes a number of exercises to assist researchers to access liminal states, including focused attention; meditation; contemplation on a particular text or topic; stories, utilising exploratory and fluid creative processes; sensory methods, such as dance, chanting, yoga, music, or breathing techniques; and intuitive methods (dreams, spontaneous insights and cultivating an openness to synchronistic opportunities).

Step 2 – Inspiration

Becoming immersed is the second state of Organic Inquiry. Within liminal, non-ordinary or transcendent states of consciousness, there are often sensations or signals that provide guidance and may include an expansive sense of identity, feelings of peace, unity, overwhelming empathetic sensations, lightness or tingling and the sense of ‘coming home’ or rediscovering what is already known (Clements 2011, p. 146). Confirming signals can guide one through the immersion phase of the research process, signaling the liminal and emergent material that requires attention and is significant in terms of the research question.

Step 3- Integration

The third and final step in the Organic Inquiry is ‘Integration’ and refers to the returning to an ordinary state of consciousness, contained by the boundaries

of the ego, informed by past research and academic knowledge. In Organic Inquiry, the research remains open to an emergent wisdom, one that can continue to evolve over time, informed by the experiential process in liminal consciousness. Clements (2011, p. 148) suggests that story becomes paramount during the integration process due to its capacity to refer to transpersonal experiences, which are universal and temporally unbound; through story, perspectives that were not apparent at the time can be revealed. I found this to be the case with the visual narratives created in response to intuitive and creative impulses; these narratives often held abstract depictions of felt states and their relationship with other creative works was often revealed long after they were originally made.

g) Personal reflections on the use of Organic Inquiry

In Organic Inquiry, the researcher is intrinsically and uniquely linked to the research, methodology, and outcome through the techniques used to access liminal states of consciousness. Methodologies that utilise intuitive processes require strategies that will contain the investigative process, and caution against the research being overtaken by the researcher's personal material. In this section, I outline the techniques I employed in order to 'step aside' from the investigation, reflect on my personal responses, follow my intuition, and remain as neutral a vessel as possible for the liminal material to emerge.

Empathetic Identification

As a practicing therapist, I often access an empathetic identification with a client, noticing feelings inside my own body that are related to the emotional pain and unacknowledged aspects of the client's psyche. Rothschild (2006, pp. 30-34) explored empathetic identification in her research on vicarious traumatisation and burnout in therapists; she proposes that some therapists feel clients' material within their own bodies due to heightened sensitivity. Mirror neurons (neural networks that are activated during the attachment process between human beings) create a reaction in the brain of one individual in response to

experience in another; this is the basis of empathy (Rothschild 2006, pp. 42-45). While the cumulative impact of reacting intensely to suffering in others can be detrimental to the therapist, those highly empathetic to their clients can often develop a deep insight into the unconscious material that is hidden within the stories being told in a session.

In this research, I utilised my sensitivity to guide participant interviews. For my transformational process, I gave myself permission to turn my empathetic awareness toward my own stories, to use it to identify the personal stories I needed to explore further, ones that held aspects yet unresolved and necessary for my healing, including stories from my journals, which elicited a felt-response that seemed worthy of further reflection.

Researching through our wounds

When this investigation commenced, I was suffering burnout and chronic health issues as a result of the cumulative impact of empathetic identification in twenty-five years as a practicing psychologist, which had led to a diagnosis of Chronic Fatigue Syndrome and its associated physical and psychological ramifications. In this organic inquiry, my sensitivity, the axis of my wounding, became something that guided and informed the creative practice in ways I found to be healing and clarifying.

Self-Inquiry

To the best of my ability, I observed my personal responses—somatic, emotional, intuitive and transpersonal — without excessive attachment, so that I could remain open to new information that came through the investigation. I noted vivid dreams, and spent considerable time reflecting on their symbolic content. I kept a journal concurrent with the research process, which became field notes, informing my auto-ethnographic reflections.

Cultivating Humility and Trust

Utilising a Buddhist concept termed 'a curious mind' (Kornfield 2003) I attempted to cultivate a humble, open-minded approach to the research, and to trust in the process. As the first year passed, I learned to become comfortable with 'not knowing' and letting go of my need to intellectually control the creative process, gradually developing a balance between a free flowing openness to experiences, and a witnessing aspect of my psyche that observed when I deviated from the topics being investigated. I attempted to walk the 'Middle Path', a state that alludes to the Buddhist practice of cultivating balance through the peaks and troughs of human experience and witnessing them without attachment (Kornfield 2009, pp. 141-43).

Solitude, Meditation and Compassionate Intention.

Over the course of the research, I began each morning with a meditation practice of one hour, followed by a walking meditation or yoga. These practices allowed me to cultivate a receptive and surrendered state of mind. At times, the practice was 'quiet' and left me with a feeling of deep connection and expansiveness; at others, I found there was a flood of insights and images, a bubbling creative flow that I allowed to 'do its own thing' for most of the morning. I would find form within the fluid psychic meandering in the afternoon, by writing at my desk, working with the emergent material creatively in my studio, or as the research progressed, employing a discerning and academic aspect of my mind toward editing and re-writing.

Meditation and focused attention allowed me to realign with my intention to investigate the ways that narratives of the self, particularly liminal and transpersonal aspects of the psyche, emerge in everyday lived experience. It was important to commit myself each day to a compassionate focus; my meditation practice had the expressed intention that the research provide a means for deeper insight, inspire transformational change, and inspire compassionate

action. I followed the Buddhist practices of mindfulness and compassion meditation¹¹ to assist with this¹².

Acceptance of an Underlying Unity

In his exploration of Jung's concept of *unus mundus*, Browne (2017) investigates Taoist, philosophical, cosmological, religious and scientific notions of what Jung (1981, p. 101) refers to as 'the latent unity of the world', identifying a common thread – a stream of consciousness that is mirrored in both internal and external realities. Browne (2017, p. 119) suggests that synchronicity occurs when internal and external worlds converge. The idea of an encompassing flow of consciousness that exists both inherently within and around all living things is imbedded in transpersonal research. I actively cultivated openness to this unity, engaging with liminal and emergent material as a source of guidance and inspiration by following the 'energetic thread' of various confirming signals, including a sense of resonance within my own body, emergent material in the form of dreams, images, symbols, and synchronicities. These synchronicities included chance meetings, opportunities that emerged at exact times when I needed assistance, information, and connections that appeared in my daily life, aligned with the areas I was investigating. Synchronistic opportunities continued to flow and guide my research; I began to see myself as a witness and vehicle for a process to work through, one that had its origins beyond my individual ego.

Csikszentmihalyi (2014, pp. 245-246), in his extensive research on creativity, describes 'flow' as the time when the creator and the universe become one, outside distractions recede and one's consciousness is expansive, unhindered by criticism or judgment and immersed in the joy of creating. It could be argued that the focus of my attention, coupled with chance, could account for some of the confirming signals I was experiencing. However, the regularity and extent of their

¹¹ For texts illustrating Buddhist practices of compassion refer Kornfield 2009; Hanh 1987; Chodron 2008.

¹² Please note that I am not stating that I was able to be one hundred percent effective in my practices and intentions, however, my aim was to pursue the research with as much sincerity and clarity that I could access.

occurrence when I was in the creative 'flow' of this investigation was something I experienced as reassurance that I was on the 'right track'.

Accessing Liminal Consciousness

My access to liminal consciousness was multi-dimensional, involving intuitive methods such as dreaming, spontaneous insights, images or feelings that came through meditation, creative flow and the use of evocative music; story was another well used point of access. I have kept written and creative journals for the past twenty-five years; some of these included my experiences in transpersonal states of consciousness and were points of reference for my life writing. Swimming, yoga, and walking in nature allowed me to become more open to liminal inspiration, as did creative play, where I would create works without a fixed intention or plan, using intuitive processes to guide the practice. My personal experience of flow was accompanied by ecstatic feeling states, which informed my writing and art making. Through developing a more surrendered approach, I sustained the experience of flow by following the feelings in my body. Pursuing an investigative thread because it 'felt right' became ingrained in my preparation and exploration process; I found that it was best to sit at my desk or enter the studio only when I was feeling deeply connected to the material.

h) Determining the Validity of the research

Story is integral to Organic Inquiry in three significant ways: 1) its capacity to facilitate the preparation to enter liminal or spiritual states of consciousness; 2) integrating liminal experience often encountered as symbol, metaphor or archetypal narrative; and 3) in exploring outcome and validity. The first two points have already been discussed. Outcome and validity are discussed further in *Outcomes and Transformative Validity*. I will outline how validity is ascertained in Organic Inquiry in the next section.

Transformative Outcomes and Validity

Clements (2011, p. 153) refers to three types of story that are part of the transformative validity and outcome of Organic Inquiry:

- i) Stories of self-*transformation*—a deepening self-awareness;
- ii) Stories of connection with Spirit;
- iii) Stories of service to all living things.

Before commencing the data collection, Clements (2011, p. 135) suggests the researcher write a baseline narrative from which to compare the subsequent changes that occur (refer *Outcomes and Transformative Validity*). I have used my auto-ethnographic voice to reflect on the self-transformative component of this research.

The second aspect of transformational validity, stories of connection with spirit, are the subject of *A Unified Self* where I reflect upon my experiences of ‘coming home’ to the Self. My film *Returning Home* (2017) also incorporates my own as well as participants’ stories of connection with spirit.

The analysis of *Organic Inquiry* provides an additional means for the reader or audience to engage with the research material, including participants’ stories, group story and transformational change experienced by audience members in response to the creative findings. In *Responses to the Exhibition (and Creative Works)* and *Appendix 2* the audience responses to the practice-led material, as well as my experience of the exhibition, are reflected upon in terms of their transformative impact. Group story is explored through key themes that emerge in participants’ stories when asked to respond to the question: *What does it mean to know our self?* These responses, gathered through documentary interviews, formed the body of my film (*Returning Home*, 2017). The third component of transformative outcome, service to all living things, is discussed in the sections: *Outcomes and Transformative Validity*, *Appendix 1*, *Discussion* and *Conclusion*. In the next section, I document the practice-led findings of this investigation, referring to key creative works, aspects of the film (*Returning Home*, 2017) and art novel (Bardsley 2017); the auto-ethnographic reflections discuss the

experience of creating the works and their meaning in light of the research question.

Prologue to the Practice-led Research

When Adler (1995) wrote a personal account of her spontaneous mystical initiation describing the longing she had to ‘write in a language that embodies the mysteries, to write the experience rather than to write about it’ (1995, p. xv), she offered her experiences as a witness, ‘without judgment, interpretation, direction or control’ (1995, p. xiii). There is a part of me that would like to do the same, to present my practice-led findings as an offering to a wider audience, to acknowledge that I was a vehicle for the creative works to emerge, but to let them speak for themselves, without my interpretation. Jung wrote:

Art is a kind of innate drive that seizes a human being and makes [them] its instrument. The artist is not a person endowed with free will who seeks his [or her] own ends but allows art to realize its purposes through him [or her]. As a human being [she/] he will have personal aims but as an artist [she/] he is [woman/] man in a higher sense – [she/] he is ‘collective [woman or] man’ one who carries and shapes the unconscious psychic life of [humankind] mankind¹³. (Jung 2001, p. 173)
[my corrections]

As this is an academic as well as a practice-led investigation, I use an auto-ethnographic voice to reflect upon the creative findings, their meaning and my experiences in creating them. In doing so, I also consider some of my choices as a curator and an artist; however, the phenomenon of using an embodied creative practice as a means of transformation was of primary significance. The creative product was integral, but secondary.

There were four significant creative outcomes of this investigation:

- 1) A collection of creative works including paintings, photographs and life-writing
- 2) A short documentary film (*Returning Home*, 2017)

¹³ I have replaced Jung’s predominant use of the male pronoun as indicated in the quotation by parentheses; I felt compelled to do so as, for me, it was inappropriate to reference my embodied experience as a woman, with a male pronoun.

- 3) An art novel, also titled *Returning home* (Bardsley 2017), which documents the majority of the exhibited creative works, some of the related narratives as well as the rationale for the investigation
- 4) A final exhibition (Bardsley 2017, exhibition), comprising a gallery exhibition of a selection of art works created during this investigation, the launch of my art novel and the Australian premiere of my short film.

(Note: as three of the creative works were titled *Returning Home*, I have used the different annotation different styles in the list above, throughout the following sections, to refer to the film, art novel and exhibition.)

It has always been my intention that the findings of this creative investigation into self would be accessible to a wider audience. By sharing my experiences in different forms, I hoped to offer a varied and evocative means for others to access the investigation outcomes and possibly to be inspired to reflect on the research question for themselves, and for the creative findings to be accessible beyond the duration of this investigation. In an attempt to address this, that the exhibition was documented (through film) to give the viewer an experience of walking through the gallery space. Both the virtual gallery tour and short film (*Returning Home*, 2017) are publically available online. The art novel *Returning home* (Bardsley 2017) is also available and can be ordered online in hard copy or electronic versions.

In the following sections, I discuss the practice-led findings, choosing select those images or life writing if I deemed them most pertinent to the transformative aspect of this investigation. All of the paintings or photographs that are documented in the art novel or appeared in the exhibition (Bardsley 2017, exhibition)¹⁴ are included in a number of separate visual galleries (constructed as power points); the links to these galleries appear in the overview for each sub-section and also within the text. Links in the footnotes access very high-resolution images of the paintings or files containing documentation of the creative works hanging in the gallery space.

The practice-led findings have been arranged into the following sections: *Beginning states*, *Biographical Selves*, *Liminal Selves* (including *Inherited Narratives* and *Mythic Selves*), and *A Unified Self*. I also include links to my film and art novel early in this practice-led section as both are referenced throughout the auto-

¹⁴ Refer *Returning home – an exhibition* for documentation of the exhibition (Bardsley 2017, exhibition)

ethnographic reflections. At the conclusion of the practice-led findings, I have documented the final exhibition (the virtual gallery tour) as well as my own and the audiences' responses.

Throughout this investigation, I have chosen particular investigative threads to explore, mediums to use and of the many artworks created over the past three and half years, which ones to exhibit and discuss. These creative and curatorial choices have been predominately intuitive. Each time I reflect upon the creative findings, I continue to have new insights. The emergence of the works has not been a linear process; the auto-ethnographic reflections were written then re-written at different stages over the three and a half year investigation and, at times, the life-writing referenced had its origins in journals kept many years earlier.

The creative findings (and my reflections on them) seem to spiral inward and deeper, moving into territory held by parts of my psyche that were vulnerable and initially hidden; when I return to these creative works, more material emerges.

Returning Home - a short film.

Returning home I, still image from *Returning Home*, 2017, short film, Vimeo, Melbourne, created by Lara Bardsley.

Perhaps what we are looking for is within us, waiting for us to come home to our selves. (*Returning Home*, 2017, tagline, Vimeo)

The film *Returning Home* (2017), evolved from my practice-led research, is both a documentary and a self-reflexive investigation in moving image that I narrate, contemplating the question: *Who are we?* *Returning Home* has a narrative arc that references personal, mythic and unified aspects of the self, documenting my investigation through interviews with others and my own auto-ethnographic reflections. *Returning Home* uses pace, the dreamlike qualities of the images, and editing to lead the viewer through an immersive experience. As the filmmaker, I invite the audience into an intimate world, the camera becomes my vision and the voice-over, my internal dialogue.

Returning Home (2017) premiered in Melbourne, Australia on October 12th, 2017 at the opening night of my exhibition and was also shown to audiences in scheduled viewings during the exhibition and on a loop in the gallery space over a four-week period. *Returning Home* (in various editions) has been screened at conferences in United Kingdom, Europe and the United States of America. The film can be viewed on the following links:

Returning Home (Teaser): <https://vimeo.com/234248876>

Returning Home (20 minute short film): <https://vimeo.com/238512790>

Returning home – an art novel.

Bardsley, 2017, *Returning home*, Blurb, image of front cover.

Two months before the final exhibition, I felt compelled to formally document my choice of images for the exhibition and some of the narratives associated with them, so that the audience could reference the works in the context of an emergent and creative investigation of self. I sensed that creating a publication would help me to contain and complete this aspect of the creative investigation. My art novel *Returning home* (Bardsley 2017), launched at the exhibition opening, became a testimony to the images and the companionship they provided over the years they had been in my home-studio. I used an online desktop publishing facility to create and design the novel and self-published one hundred copies. I later published the novel with Amazon. An electronic version of the novel can be viewed here: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1_oq_eE5YbNTSLW2Kwp61R00tOMhUqSjc

Beginning States

Overview

This section documents my creative and auto-ethnographic reflections while commencing this investigation and includes the following creative works:

Visual art galleries¹⁵:

Beginning states:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1d-1_c68AWkZzvuGjmVD-E4LOKNBkW4Ia

Arboreal narratives:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1mziDpPobwkzJq4JbHufhC4lhKY0DJEE2>

A Patchwork of Stories

A Patchwork of stories, 2016, oil and gold size on canvas, 129 cm x 210 cm

¹⁵ The very fine details of the paintings can be viewed in the TIFF files here (credit Dean Whitby photo documentation):

https://drive.google.com/open?id=111cL73yJzc2f54_Xyn7RASq4IjXcD9ah

As the title suggests, *A patchwork of stories* became a metaphor for this investigation. The work took shape as I began my PhD in 2015 and was completed in 2016. Gold size (used extensively in this piece) is a medium that I have creatively employed for over fifteen years, with varying degrees of success. More recently, I have become more skilled in using oil glazes and layering, distressing the surface of the works or adding line work over the gold leaf to highlight the texture and 'deepen' the perspective. Over the last fifteen years working with gold in many guises, I feel that I have moved from using it in a decorative manner and more towards my goal of visually referencing a sense of sacredness. In the art novel, I write:

Gold leaf...speaks to me of the sacred, elemental aspects of life. The use of gold in my work references a luminescence that exists beneath our narratives in the deepest layers of the Self...I use gold to invite the viewer to reflect on the miracle and beauty of life itself. (Bardsley 2017, p. 34)

Jung used the process of alchemy as a metaphor for the individuation process (1989, p. 556)¹⁶. Alchemy appears in many cultures as a philosophical and pseudoscientific process whereby base or mundane elements are transformed into the most precious metal, gold, referred to in alchemy as the philosopher's stone (Kauffman 1985, p. 6). For Jung, the philosopher's stone is the desired outcome of individuation, symbolic of a transformative process to produce unity, 'a physical and psychic reconciliation of opposing forces through which the transcendent can be glimpsed' (Jung 1989, pp. 554 -556).

The experience of creating *A patchwork of stories* was an alchemical process, one that was toxic and beautiful. There is an ethereal quality to the gold leaf; it is very delicate, taking flight easily. As I layered it on the canvas it tore, shaping itself in ways that intrigued me. Because of its size (210 cm x 130cm), *A patchwork of stories* has an immersive quality and it is the largest canvas I have worked on. Midway through creating this painting, I discovered my mother's paint box. Lydia had always longed to paint. As child I watched her struggle to find the space to pursue and develop her art. In my memory, the time she found to paint was edged with a grief

¹⁶ also refer Jung 1968

and disquiet that I understand now in the light of her relationship with her father, an accomplished artist.

I inherited my mother's paints when she died and by the time I used them they had remained undisturbed for 30 years. I applied the gold oxide to *A patchwork of stories* from a twisted and fragile tube of Lydia's (over 40 years old), which broke apart as I did so. The effect of applying the oxide as a glaze over the gold leaf was beautiful but the paint was toxic. Despite precautions I took in wearing gloves and a mask while working on *Patchwork*, the painting released its chemicals through the drying process and I became increasingly unwell; I was beset by migraines, dizziness and nausea. I was, however, delighted with the painting; its texture reminded me of flying over the central Australian desert, a landscaped scarred by ancient oceans and the ghosts of rivers long gone.

Beautiful, toxic, gold and earth, transmutation; my mother, my innermost territories.

I wrote these words in my journal; for now, I will leave these reflections unpacked as I share these stories later. Two other images then emerged from my creative practice, which acted as both confirmation and containment for entering the crucible of this investigation.

Olive Tree

Olive tree, 2015, oil pastel and gold size on Canvas, 120cm x 92cm.

In early 2014, I was travelling with my husband to visit my father in Mornington where I grew up. As we neared our destination we passed a plantation of olive trees and I asked him to pull over so I could photograph it. Apart from the beauty of their long flexible branches and the delicately curved leaves, I was struck by how these trees were organized into rows that stretched into the distance. I was reminded of a story from my early childhood, while attending a Christian Sunday School:

God was deeply disappointed in his creations and had decided to flood the Earth, erase all life and begin again. He chose Noah and his wife to build an ark and collect one male and one female of every living thing in readiness to re-populate the Earth. Noah was afloat on his ark when a dove flew back to him with an olive branch in its beak. Noah realized that land had reappeared from the floods. It was time to begin anew. (Journal entry, adapted from Genesis 8:11)

The olive tree is considered to be symbolic of peace, forgiveness and new beginnings. On that summer's day en route to my childhood home, a field of olive trees (hand planted by human beings) was a hopeful visual metaphor. Journaling, I wrote: *peace, planted by humanity. Olive tree* was created in 2015 during the time I was considering my next steps after taking an indefinite break from my clinical practice and when I began this investigation.

Bodhi Tree

Bodhi tree, 2015, mixed media and gold size on canvas, 70 cm x 96 cm.

I first embraced Tibetan Buddhism in my early twenties not long after my mother's death. Symbolically, *Bodhi tree* speaks to a place where a profound spiritual transformation occurs. Chodron (2008, p. 40) writes of the night Prince Siddhartha became the Buddha. Siddhartha sat in deep meditation under a Bodhi tree resisting seduction from the forces of *Mara*, the demons in Buddhist cosmology that personified the qualities of craving, aversion, attachment, overwhelming emotion and fear of death. *Bodhi tree* references my gratitude for the many years of Buddhist training and practice that I have had and how they have prepared me for this immersive investigation into self.

Olive tree and *Bodhi tree* became my anchors in this investigation as I began my circumambulation of my self, the spiraling inward of one's awareness in the individuation process. These paintings are two of three works that I cannot part with and continue to live with, reflecting upon them daily. The third painting is *Call to the desert*, which I will discuss subsequently. These works form a trinity representing hope, transcendence and unity.

Arboreal Narratives

The images documented in the visual gallery titled *Arboreal narratives*¹⁷ reference the organic and transpersonal methodology of this investigation. Trees became a subject that I felt compelled to explore through various media including capturing the chiaroscuro of their bold and twisted lines in black and white photography. I write in the art novel:

Trees are remarkably beautiful, intricate and unique. Hidden beneath the visible crust of the earth are root systems that nourish, support and sustain them. They breathe in synchronistic relationship with humanity and because they breathe, we live. Trees are symbols of transformation. Their form is long-lived, flexible and able to tolerate harsh or changeable conditions. They are in perpetual motion but exude stillness, stability and strength, renewing themselves most tenderly and remarkably

¹⁷ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1mziDpPobwkzIq4JbHufhC4lhKYODJEE2>

after destructive events. In my work they symbolize the beauty and dichotomy of humanity – the possibility to be grounded in the earth, embodied yet flexible, unencumbered, and able to dance in the weather of life. They unite both the unseen (the unconscious) and the obvious. (Bardsley 2017, p. 16)

In the recurring motif of trees as they emerge through my creative practice, I am reminded of the tree as a metaphor of organic growth that Clements (2011, p. 134) uses for *Organic inquiry*.

Biographical Selves

Overview

This section references the creative research that I have attributed to my biographical and inherited stories. It includes the following creative works:

Life writing:

Providence

Handpicked

Haunted

Death of the sun

Absence and presence

Visual art gallery¹⁸:

Childhood landscapes:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1FkELpQbjPLqUA8BUCf0rTDio5SbRElg>

Film - *Returning Home* sections:

A Message from Your Daughter

Weaving a Net of Perception

Introduction

In this section, I discuss my experience in creating and compiling *A Message from Your Daughter* and *Providence*. These biographical stories of the self were the first to emerge in this investigation; they reference my memories of my family and childhood. I made *A Message from Your Daughter* (2016) on a holiday with my husband and father. The voice-over was added when I reviewed and edited black

¹⁸ The very fine details of the paintings can be viewed in the TIFF files here (credit Dean Whitby photo documentation):

https://drive.google.com/open?id=111cL73yJzc2f54_Xyn7RASq4IjXcD9ah

and white footage. My life-writing *Providence* is compiled from journals I have kept for over two decades and centers on my childhood experiences. I have included it in this investigation as it references my growing understanding of how my parents' personal stories shaped my own.

A Message from Your Daughter

It's not always easy but sometimes the greatest relationships are those you grow into - a daughter's message to her father. (*A Message from Your Daughter*, 2016, caption, Vimeo)

I made *A Message from Your Daughter* as a stand-alone piece that was eventually included in its entirety, in *Returning Home* (2017). *A Message from Your Daughter* runs from the time 2.28 to 5.22 min of my film *Returning Home*. Because of its significance, I have discussed it as an independent piece.

A Message from Your Daughter I, 2016, still image from *Returning Home*

Somehow we have learned to accept our differences and our disappointments. Sometimes I am overwhelmed by the love I feel for you. It's a little careful but really strong, almost fierce, and the timing is right, for at this stage in our lives we can't

deny needing each other. (*A Message from Your Daughter*, 2016, excerpt from the voice-over)

A Message from Your Daughter II, 2016, still image from the film *Returning Home*

Time is precious. I know that now. I want to *live* these memories. I want to be present while we are together. You walk ahead of me Dad, and one day, I'll walk alone. (*A Message from Your Daughter*, 2016, excerpt of voice-over)

Making the film clip *A Message from Your Daughter* was an enjoyable, flowing experience, a celebration of my new canvas, film, and a new brush, an affordable but professional hand-held digital film camera. Film became a new language in my creative practice. With it I was able to investigate emergent stories through moving images, documentary interviews and movement applications over still photography. Film allowed me to be more observant of the narratives that existed around and within me and to convey them articulately and evocatively to wider audiences. By editing the rough cut of the film in a manner that was fluid and unscripted, I intuitively responded to the footage captured. This process allowed the apparent patterns in the narrative to emerge organically so that I could gradually shape the film as the themes became apparent.

The rough cut of *A Message* happened rapidly; the process was driven by intuition rather than planned intellectual consideration. The spoken narration was a spontaneous, unscripted response to the visual story that I saw emerging from the footage. My discerning and detached editor-self came much later, like a doctor whose role it was to salvage, contain and tidy the explosive, compulsive consequences of the creative act.

A Message from Your Daughter was aired to a number of people and used as part of two conference presentations¹⁹. The greatest strength of *A Message* is the universality of the story. I am yet to meet someone who has not struggled, at times, to hold the tension of a strong attachment (positive or otherwise) with their parents or the people who raised them. Artistic decisions that I made while creating and editing the film (while primarily intuitive) shaped the story; the use of black and white makes the stunning scenery in Lorne, where it was filmed, less distracting and highlights its reflective and vulnerable qualities. The fade to black between cuts is reminiscent of closing one's eyes and creates a sense of inward focus, inviting viewer reflection. The slow, rhythmic pace of the voice-over with its intimate pedestrian style also helps to evoke an immersive, hypnagogic experience. As information consumers in a culture dominated by technology, it is easy for us to become desensitized to visual imagery, especially when it is coupled with intense movement and sound. This piece, I think, was strengthened by the lack of it.

I have received feedback that my father never looks at or speaks to the camera; he actually does, briefly pulling a face and waving at the camera as he walks past me in the company of my husband and dog. *A Message* is an observational piece; I have not given my father a voice. I have pieced together the images, chosen the order of the shots, decided to use a wide shot or an extreme close up and made decisions about how long the image holds the eye and on which words of the voice-over the visual story changes. The power was in my hands; the story was the one that I (as the filmmaker) chose to tell.

¹⁹ Responses to *A Message from Your Daughter* are documented in *Responses to the exhibition (and creative works)* and *Appendix 2*.

Providence

Providence is a collection of four short memoirs. The stories reveal a mother haunted by her past. Her sensitive child becomes a woman, shaped by loss, deepened by the compassion for the suffering she has witnessed and a resilience that grew from it.

Lara and her mother Lydia, 2016 digital image; original photograph Stephen Bardsley, 1969

Perhaps it is the stories that we are not aware of, the hidden buried selves, the people we have loved and lost, that really define who we are. (*Returning Home*, 2017 excerpt of the voice-over)

Hand-picked

I made one hell of a choice when I peered down from my lofty cloud and chose my parents. My mother's beauty and vivaciousness made her a prime candidate. I saw her leave the orphanage and her adoptive parents to become the Brigit Bardot of Colchester, Essex. I was attracted to her spunk, intelligence, and her refusal to be a stay-at-home sandwich maker. I felt proud when she insisted on learning to drive at eighteen years old, when many of the women in her parish hadn't ever sat behind a steering wheel. I stood beside her, unseen, rubbing my palms together delightedly as she began her independent life in her own apartment, shaking off her childhood like a bad dream. I watched as she blossomed into a gorgeous princess with no past, only a future fit for one so intelligent and glamorous. I too, fell in love with the young man from a reputable family who was stiff with pride at her side. He had a lot to be smug about. He had won my mother over suitors who would ride fifteen miles for a cup of tea in her presence.

Despite the high heels and makeup that inspired both admiration and disapproval from different members of the community, Lydia was undoubtedly innocent. She was gorgeous. Her skin was slightly olive, her eyes were dark and intense like her Jewish father, but her face was broad and strong jawed like her mother. As she became older, her hair changed from rich auburn to light golden which highlighted her Teutonic features. She was (as most fairytale princesses are) a remarkable mix of courage and naïveté, strength and fragility, the world she belonged to was one of epic quests for love; of virgins, knights and magic.

Lydia was not going to be hemmed in by the judgments of her church community when it came to feminine etiquette. Although she was considered to be worldly and hence unchristian by some members of her church, her heart was on fire with a passionate love of Christ. When I joined her on the planet, the fire of her devotion was a sweet smoulder that I barely noticed, but when death breathed upon her, the flames of her faith warmed her in her last moments.

So what of the man we chose? Stephen was ambitious, unusually intelligent, commanding and handsome — a husband and father who had all the signs of success, security, loyalty and devotion. Sometimes you don't realise what really guides your choices. It is only when your limbs are tightly wrapped

in the web of your relationships that you realise you may have bitten off more than you can chew.

People would notice when Stephen walked into a room. When he was younger, his hair was dark and some say he has an olive complexion, but I've seen his skinny pale British legs in the days of short shorts, long socks and sandals, and I cannot believe he had a great grandmother who was Spanish with skin so dark that she appeared African-American in the photos his cousin sent him. He has a quick temper, and as a younger man, an intense sexuality of which women were acutely aware. He was born under the western astrological sign of the lion, as was my mother, and he had all the characteristics reportedly bestowed upon Leos. Stephen's eyes are grey / green, flecked with gold. He had his face rearranged when he fell off a ladder in college, breaking his skull and both arms. He has almost always worn a beard; my mother insisted he did so to hide what she saw as a weak chin. Now, at eighty, his face has softened, and his hair, downy and soft, covers the scars of skin cancers recently removed. He is heavier than he was as a young man, but undeniably still in possession of a handsome dignity.

My parents met at a crusade. My father's family came from the restrictive religious community of the Brethren Assemblies. My mother's foster parents were also devout members of a Christian movement aptly named 'The Peculiar people'. In 1956, they both attended group of Christian youth travelling from their parish to attend a festival of praise. Their lives were soon to change. According to my father, they had both been brought up with much 'hell, fire and damnation'. Instead of finding the Lord, they found each other, a relationship that was to sustain them for the next thirty-two years.

I could ask Dad about his first impressions of my mother but he is a pragmatic man, and although he feels deeply, romantic tales are not in his repertoire. I remember what he said when we scattered her ashes to the sudden sea breeze that whipped the dust back into our faces so that we breathed her in: 'I will always remember your beauty'.

Stephen and Lydia soon formed a tight bond. They were seventeen years old with their birthdays in late July and early August, five days apart. Stephen had recently lost his mother and Lydia was an orphan with a loneliness hidden beneath her

gregariousness. At twenty, Stephen joined the Royal Air Force, trained in electronics and was stationed firstly in Norfolk, and then Suffolk for three years, returning to Essex to be with Lydia on the weekends. Their relationship flourished and they were married, both twenty-two years of age. One year later, they escaped Colchester for the Great Southern Land with its warmth and endless possibilities.

My mother decided that Australia would be our lucky country. Within her were the kernels of the past, the souls of her father's family that lay as fragile seedlings still curled within their pods, the ghosts of the 100 Jewish ancestors who perished in the Holocaust. Inside her was the story of her mother as a Czech refugee, fleeing with two small children to Scotland, homeless, speaking the enemy's language and abandoned by Lydia's father. Australia was far enough away from her past to give Lydia a sense of safety. The couple fled the disapproving church community with its Missionaries and 'Our Savior is coming' sandwich board-wearing members (their relatives) to embark upon a new life.

With the courage and determination that I witnessed many years later, they cashed in their British National Pension, paid ten pounds each, boarded an ocean liner and crossed the Pacific. After five weeks at sea, they disembarked in Port Melbourne, surrendering their passports for two years as required by the Australian Government, only to immigrate to America in order to study Chiropractic, two years later.

While at a chiropractic college in Kansas City the couple topped their classes. Despite working full-time during the day and on weekends while attending classes in the evenings, they could barely make ends meet. Unexpectedly, and quite inconveniently, it was at this time that I chose to make my grand entrance.

I know barely anything about my birth. Mum did say that it was responsible for her varicose veins, her stretch marks and the fullness of her abdomen and thighs in her middle age. Asking Dad about my birth has proved rather futile; I believe he was asleep in the waiting room for most of the event (as things were done in those days). The brief conversation I had with my mother while she was alive was full of maternal guilt about not breast-feeding me, and the shock of trying to juggle a child, a marriage, work and a degree. I asked my father who took care of me when I was very young, he said: 'for the first few years, we farmed you out to anyone we could find.'

Returning to Australia from the United States with a baby proved to be a challenge. I was nine and a half months old and nearly died from an allergic reaction to

the vaccinations. After what must have been a harrowing journey with their critically ill child, my parents settled in Melbourne, a city with seemingly endless space, narrow city beaches, cafes filled with well-dressed men and women and colours reminiscent of England. A few years later, they left the city for a quiet coastal town on the Mornington Peninsula, where yellow sand beaches lined the gentle moods of Port Phillip Bay and the branches of tea trees were gnarled and twisted with sea spray.

I vaguely remember the dark and pokey little flat in Mornington that my parents rented, we had crates for furniture and my mother sewed curtains for the windows. The lampshades were paisley designs, red or purple velvet with gold tassels, with the frames made out of coat hangers and the bases, bottles thickly covered with plaster of Paris, painted gold with fragments of glass and shells pressed into them. They looked like the decorated icing on the cakes I saw at other children's birthday parties.

I would ride up and down the concrete path that led to the front gate where the metal letterboxes were perched four across and two down in a pillar of red brick. I remember the elderly faces of the other residents who would call 'hello' from behind their wire screen doors, some of whom looked after me while my parents worked. I remember the smell sausages and onions, the sound of the news on the television and the many hours I spent playing alone on the lawn, which sometimes exploded into a mosaic of coloured daisies.

My parents both worked in a chiropractic practice on Main Street. At that time, Chiropractors were commonly known as 'quacks' but Lydia and Stephen persevered and built a very successful practice. By the time I was six, my parents were able to buy a large block on the corner of Nepean Hwy and Herbert Street, a few kilometres out of town. Into it were excavated two huge spaces in which the clinic and our residence were set, separated by an internal courtyard. These two buildings became my universe. We were on the same block as the local hospital and the funeral parlour. Although we had illness on our right and death on our left, we only used the hospital twice in the twenty years we lived there, once when my father was bitten by a Redback spider. The second time it was my mother who at forty-nine, entered hospital for a brief time in acute care before returning home to die, then make her way to the funeral parlour a few doors away.

Our home had been designed to fit snugly behind the clinic. My parents' treatment rooms had windows that would open on to a beautifully landscaped courtyard full of deciduous trees, ferns and rhododendron bushes. The front of our residence was set deep into the earth so that patients in the clinic could not see into the house, but if she pressed herself close to the glass, my mother could catch a glimpse of my bedroom window. I would watch for her there and be elated when she left her patient on the treatment table to walk to the jar of Vaseline she kept on the windowsill, as she worked the paste into her palms she would look for me and when our gaze met, she would blow me kisses. These moments of connection would infuse my solitude with sunlight.

I had the most beautiful room in the house. I could see a cherry tree from the window opposite my bed that reflected the changing seasons. My room was luxuriously carpeted with cream shag-pile set in a pattern of grass-like threads and tight loops that I would study regularly. I would lie on my stomach and pull the woolen loops apart with my fingers to check for little insects. Sometimes, I would spend an hour preening my carpet for fleas, as would a primate her mate. I had an intense awareness of detail, noticing anything that was visually awry. I frequently spent time ordering my tomato-red 'Encyclopedia Britannica', making sure that the spines of all the books were in line. A few times a day, I would rearrange my ornaments and use my nails to scrape the dust out of the corners of my window frames. When I wasn't obsessed with order, I would lie on my soft cream shag-pile and stare up into the wooden ceiling where the knotted shapes would morph into faces that would speak to me of philosophy and meaning. Together we would ponder the purpose of life, the motivations of the human race and the mystery of death. These benevolent friends would watch over me as I played alone, drew, painted and wrote long love letters to my mother to which she would reply the next morning, passing a note on a folded piece of paper under the sliding door that led down a dark hallway to my bedroom. Each morning, when I awoke, I would run up the hallway and find my mother's note with her favourite endearment for me written in her generous handwriting. The contents would be a testimony to our love, which I would read and re-read throughout the hours that separated us. Although we would see each other for a

short time in the evenings, we would never refer to our correspondence, ours was a clandestine affair.

As she aged, Lydia filled more of her skin. It meant that there was more of her to love. I was a sunflower who turned my face toward her sun, hungry for her light, humbled by her magnificence. I spent my waking hours celebrating my devotion, making her sculptures from twigs, moss and leaves that I collected in my wanderings in the native garden on our half-acre block. When I would go to 'the wilderness' - the empty paddock that stretched across seven house blocks behind our property, bordered by a creek, I made her drawings of the eucalyptus trees whose limbs I would embrace in her absence, the soft dust of their bark sticking to the wetness of my lips. Sometimes I wrote poetry for her on thin strips of bark that I would collect from the trunk of a paperbark tree.

When I began school, I was unprepared for the world that confronted me. Kindergarten had been a time of warmth and creativity, of playing under the protective gaze of my teacher with whom I had bonded deeply. By contrast, my memories of school are infused with a sense of alienation and anxiety. By Second Grade, some of the kids were calling me names, facilitated by my practice of bringing to school flowers or hand made gifts for my teachers. The bullying I experienced through early primary school was not aided by my mother's morning ritual of braiding my waist length hair into loops around my head (in a manner reminiscent of Princess Leah in Star Wars), setting it into place with hair spray and curling wisps against my forehead with saliva. I was desperately shy and barely spoke in class, when I did it was in a whisper so people strained - neck stretched, ear cocked - to catch what I was saying. The school playground was a zoo with scores of wild animals. My earliest friendships consisted of my hanging onto the hand of another little girl and being pulled along by her exuberance. I was teased, not just because of my hairstyles and protruding front teeth (winning me the title of 'Bucky Beaver'), but because I was so deeply introverted, sensitive and precocious. I was a child with a deep thirst for knowledge and spent many hours on my homework each night even at an early age, illustrating my writing with drawings and gold paint. I displayed a capacity and understanding well beyond my years, which attracted the acknowledgment of my teachers, who frequently singled me out. There were occasions when teacher attention was in the form of accusations that the work wasn't my own. These times were humiliating, unnerving and inflamed a

response from my mother who flounced into the classroom indignant. My response was to become more timid and self doubting, folding in on myself to retreat further into my inner world, one that was rich with a feeling of peace and safety.

When I was eight, I began to compulsively scratch into the plaster wall beside my bed at home. My mother would ask me how the marks appeared and I said that I didn't know. Thus began an agonizing ritual, night after night, when my light was turned out, I would lie in my bed and try and fight an unbearable urge to scratch another mark in the wall. I became so consumed by this urge that I was beset by elaborate fantasies of the dreadful consequences of my failure to perform this act, believing that if I scratched the wall I would not suffer from the nightmares that had begun to haunt my nights and the beings that seemed to materialize from the far wall of my bedroom to make ghoulish faces at me before I fell asleep. As the nights passed, my mother continued to question my involvement in what was becoming a tiny cavern in the wall. I continued to deny responsibility. I don't remember either of us speaking honestly about what was happening, only the terror and agitated excitement I experienced each night as, against my will, my hand scratched away on the white plaster. Eventually, for my ninth birthday, my parents put up a mural of the Austrian Alps, a lush green valley with purple ice capped mountains in the distance. In the foreground, among the pale green fields was a small church, overhead the sky was a brilliant azure. In my imagination I would run fearlessly on these fields and meet myself in the little church, there, I would find heaven.

In my art novel *Returning home* (Bardsley 2017, p. 10) I note that I was a highly sensitive, reflective and solitary child and perhaps these aspects of my personality contributed to my being deeply impacted by the events in my childhood and the stories my parents carried within them.

Blairgowrie coastal bush, 2016, digital print.

The visual gallery *Childhood Landscapes*²⁰ alludes to the narrative territory that shaped my early years. In the images I have chosen, and the way I have edited them (of which *Blairgowrie Coastal Bush* is an example), I aimed to depict the beauty and expansiveness of the coastal landscape where I grew up, but also the longing, loneliness and grief that permeated my childhood.

²⁰ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1FkELpQbjjPLqUA8BUCf0rTDio5SbREIg>

Haunted

*My mother's face was as wary as a wild bird...
'Don't ever tell anyone you have Jewish blood.'
'Why not?' I asked her.
'Bad things happen to Jews, those people may only be pretending all is forgotten. You must keep it a secret.'*

I wanted to ask her who 'those people' were, but my mother's potent defiance and distress caused the questions to remain in my throat. I lapsed into bewildered silence, watching as a veil was once again pulled across her face. I accepted the drink that she had made me, the thick crust of chocolate powder floated heavily above the white milk. As I began to spoon the moistened chocolate mixture into my mouth, the slight unease in my belly and chest gradually subsided. I was distracted by chocolate delight. How was I to know what she held within her? I was just a child.

If my mother was the sun, I was the moon. I basked in her brilliance. She illuminated my surface and pulled me to her, giving me a location in the universe of endless space that surrounded me. In return for this, I carried her emotional depths and uncharted inner territory. As a child, I held it safely for her like a broody chicken perched upon a mysterious egg. In some ways, I thought one day, when she was ready, I could hand it back to her, unblemished, intact and she could explore its contents with the maturity of her superior years. Even then, I sensed that whatever was inside that shell, it was too big for a little girl to handle. Things didn't really go to plan. Before my mother was ready, there was murmuring from within the shell, I found my task too immense and before either of us had a chance to talk about the faceless beast that controlled us both, she left me alone, barely through my teens, with the monster of her past.

Lydia was convinced that more of her relatives must have survived the gas chambers. For years I remember being squashed into foreign phone booths as she nervously called anyone in the phone book with her father's surname or derivatives of it. At first, she would talk to my father about these calls but his exasperated silence and frustrated outbursts meant that these jaunts were made

in secret between breaks in the day's proceedings as we toured international Chiropractic conferences.

Looking back now I can see that my mother was a time bomb. Under the veneer of a beautiful and confident woman was an orphan with immense fears of being abandoned by those she loved - with the skeletons of suicide and the genocide of the Holocaust simmering beneath the surface. She managed to bury the stories she carried until her mid life when ghosts from her own and her ancestors' past began to haunt her. Her dream diaries (which I discovered after her death) were filled with faceless tormentors, empty wastelands, mass graves and people who would abandon her as a child in sterile rooms. I believe she reached a stage where she could no longer deny her inner torment and she reached out to her husband for support. My father was ill-equipped to weather my mother's inner storms, so the two of them performed a dance toward and away from each other while I watched, devastated and impotent.

Stephen had been born into a reputable British family who were formal, strict and reserved in their child rearing. His father, a lay Christian preacher, was a pillar of the community but less able to meet the emotional needs of his only son as his wife's health declined. My father's mother succumbed to bowel cancer when he was sixteen after being critically ill for most of his young life. He spent much of his childhood under the care of relatives and other adults, but remained very close to his ailing mother. I have a photo of him as a young boy. He is sitting awkwardly in the photographer's studio, short pants revealing knobby knees, his vulnerability enhanced by his wary smile as he looks toward the camera, his ears protruding inelegantly from a face that shows that he's seen too much already. It was with this little boy I formed a relationship of care and forgiveness that sustained me through my adult life.

If my mother was a sun, then my father was a comet that would blaze across my sky leaving a trail of fire, dust and smoldering wounds. My relationship with my father was complex; if I look at him through the eyes of myself as a little girl, I feel immense adoration, fear, fascination and bewilderment. From the same window where I waited for my mother's kisses, I watched for my father, listening for the approach of his sure solid steps when he returned from the banking in Main Street. He would traverse the concrete steps

as if they were islands in a sea of green grass and with each of his footsteps my heart would reverberate with joy that he was coming home to me. I quickly learned that he was uncomfortable with the immensity of my love, so rather than face rejection, I would be a spinning top on the inside but maintain an exterior of detachment that matched his own.

Death of the Sun

There is a dark cloud in my belly, so dark that I can't see what it is made of nor why it obscures a sunny day - a day that is still an empty page, without a story. I don't remember the last time I had a day without a story, one that stretched beyond where I stood and was open for the celebration of the moment. For too long each day has been grown from the seeds of the past.

This cloud, this dark poison, has always settled in my guts, swelling my belly so that my clothes strain against it and I stand, like a confused Napoleon, with my hand tucked under the left lip of my trousers. Last night I shook and sobbed. The cloud caught up with me and I lost the light. I felt wrong, shameful, vengeful, and ready to fight for my right to live. Waves of terror alternated with waves of revulsion, and I did not understand. That is the most difficult thing for me to cope with - not understanding.

When I attempt to write of this time, the darkness comes. I am thrown on a foul ocean and I feel sick, giddy, disorientated. My nights are restless and there is a thick mat of grief in my throat. And I still don't understand. Twice before I have come to the edge and had to turn away. I have been too nauseous and fatigued or in too much pain to continue writing at my desk. At times I have been fighting to remain conscious, I have wanted to complete something by putting my story to paper, but I couldn't. I physically couldn't do it. This time I want to make it through. I have been writing intensively for four years, but I first began to invent myself with language when I was just a child. I write because I am the means by which the stories can be born. In some ways, I feel that the past has implanted its splintered fragments in my present and I have to write in order to salvage my future.

There is a curtain that separates me from colours and people. I react with teary rawness at patterns in my relationships that I have tolerated in the past with much more clarity. I stand awkwardly in front of acquaintances at a loss for polite conversation. It is as if I harbor a secret engagement with a silent lover, one that fills my most intimate world and to which I long to return. I want to put this story to rest yet in order to do so I feel that I must write it. I sense this story holds a special gift - my own permission to let things be, to let bodies decompose and bones to become dust, to liberate myself from the gnawing and dissecting, to dance at the wake, and to live. In honour of those who have perished, I want to be fully alive, and for those who lived with the burden of their pain, I wish to carry nothing.

I have my mother's hands. I walk on her feet with their bunions, long second toes and thickened callused heels. I have my father's cheekbones, chin and the vulnerability of his mouth. I have been given so much more, though, inside I have an heirloom, one that was carried dutifully by my mother to her death and one that called my grandmother to the grey freezing depths, clutching her two young children.

The women in my family have bowed to this force — like virgins to a ritual sacrifice. I have run from it. Like the wind it has shifted the sands where I have built my home and I have had to move on, again and again. Clutching at freedom, I was a dare devil skipping in front of an approaching battalion. Now something has changed, gradually I have slowed my pace and the battalion has approached. I can hear the battle cries and the steady marching. Twice I have been overwhelmed and retreated but now I feel that I am ready to stand my ground. This is the time; within and around me are the resources to weather this storm.

The mind is a fickle bedfellow. It will seduce you one moment with the smoothest of concepts and when you are disarmed, wet and wanting, it will deconstruct you. This world offers us the full smorgasbord — the sweetest fruits and the most bitter, the healing balms and the poisons. We have a choice, there are parts of us we can nourish and they will grow stronger. If we invest in our inner richness, it may flourish.

A fine line exists between working through one's pain and wrapping it around us as a comfort blanket. Pain can be a way to know ourselves; we can be defined by our suffering. We can also deny our pain, shove it sideways and it can seep through our veneer, making us sick and wounding those closest to us. To let go there must be trust and trust is a feeling, a state of being that comes from within us.

Absence and Presence

When someone dies they are immortalized — a snapshot whose nuances fade, their character is summarized into a sentence or two. And when a beautiful woman dies young, they are iconized - Grace Kelly, Princess Diana and my mother. Lydia's beauty was still in full bloom when she died. Her skin was not crisscrossed with the latitude and longitude of her experience. She escaped the great equalizer of ageing. If you are still a child, or a young adult, you cannot leave a dead parent behind, they come with you as you continue through life's twists and turns — a mythological figure, silently passing judgment at your decisions, a missed embrace at your successes. It is very hard to rebel against your mother when she is dead. Letting go is even harder when you can't argue or re-write the past together. From the time your life is punctuated with death, you live with the knowledge that the only thing we can really have is our own life.

Now, as an adult, I can understand how Lydia was devastated by the trauma that infiltrated her life. She was like a kite, whose guiding cord had been severed, floating recklessly in a sky - still bright and colourful - but with no real means of direction or control. I always thought my relationship with my mother defined me but it is my father who has remained with me. Our paths diverged; we lost years to misunderstandings and disappointments. Seasoned by grief, rifts were deepened by our stubbornness and our awkwardness in reaching out to each other. Despite this, my father stayed with me, we have been able to clasp each other in forgiveness, putting to rest the stories that haunted us both.

My mother was like a large beautiful tree, on either side of which my father and I grew in opposite directions, shaped by our need to access our own light. When she toppled, our roots tore, two saplings that had grown twisted away from each other with an empty space between us. The gulf between us did not really become reforested for a good twenty-five years after Lydia's death. There were toxins in the ground that seemed to kill any new growth before it had a chance to flourish. When I returned to Melbourne eleven years after her death, I began to reach toward my father and, after some time, he slowly began to grow toward me. *A Message from Your Daughter* tells the story of our developing relationship. I see it as a testament to how far we have come.

Providence came about through cobbling together and rewriting extracts of a diary that I had kept diligently from 1995 to 2002 and, less vigilantly, over the past 10 years. Compiling *Providence* was a fully immersive and rather unravelling experience. I reflected on my diary entries with a presence that I had not previously been capable of and the stories began to resonate within my body, stimulating a flood of thoughts, images and dreams. At this time the creative process was like having dysentery; my inner world became bloated and distended with stories from my childhood that were all clamoring for attention. Nights were frequently short bursts of dream-filled sleep with long hours of insomnia. I would lay awake, obsessively turning details and creative possibilities over in my mind. I had to stem the urge to rush to my studio and paint, write or edit my film at 2 am, and again at 3am, 4am and 5am. Words seemed to tumble onto the page, downloaded as if by ear.

I have not always found the creative dance to be as manic as it was when creating *Providence* and the artworks that came from revisiting these childhood experiences. Many times, with previous works, I could contentedly chisel away delighting in the slow emergence of the detail. I have come to understand that there is a unique intensity when creatively referencing material that is evocative and deeply held in the unconscious, these potent stories hold parts of our soul that are rarely, if ever, exposed, whose birth into the observable world can be hard work. I feel that I had no choice but to

be led by these stories once I invited them into my creative practice. My role, it seemed, was to become the crucible as they took form from the liminal space, as a designated midwife who mopped up the mess of their birth.

I was very anxious about showing the *A Message* to my father. Having learnt the benefit of creating space around strong emotions in our relating, I rang him and said that I would send him an email with something I wanted to show him, gently suggesting that I would be most appreciative if he could respond after watching the film (via text if he preferred) and relieve me of my anxiety regarding his response.

One hour later he replied via text:

'It's great! A real tearjerker, shame about the old git in it'.

To which I replied, via text: 'I love that old git deeply'.

Nothing further was said about it. A few weeks later, I shared *Providence* with him, again via email. Over the past few years, since he was widowed for the second time, I have rung him every second day. We have an unspoken rule that I will ring him and not vice versa. The day after I sent him *Providence*, he rang me, very excited, the first spontaneous call in as long as I can remember. After giving me feedback regarding the chronology of reported events and some further information about his parents, what became the focus of our conversation was his pride and delight in my telling the story. He remarked how my writing had given him a completely new perspective on my experiences. Now, as I write this section, almost a year later, I recognize that it was after sharing both *A Message from Your Daughter* and *Providence* with my father that our 'growing together' accelerated. Through sharing these stories, we have learned to witness each other in a way that was previously unprecedented. When I tell him that I am presenting at a conference, he often asks: 'Are you going to show *my* film?'

Approaching the Limen

As I reflected on my childhood narratives, images and sensations began to seep through from my psyche into my awareness; some of my hidden and most vulnerable stories began to reveal themselves. In the studio, I returned to some photographic images of two professional artist models six months earlier. Of the eight hundred and forty photos, I selected and edited only a handful; these appear in the following sections and the visual galleries, *Death and rebirth* and *Descent of the feminine*.²¹

Descent, 2016, Digital Print.

In *Descent* and the sister image, *Rebirth* (Bardsley 2017, p. 14), the colours of the woman's figure are subdued. There is a blue tone to the naked flesh that alludes to bloodlessness and the presence of death further reinforced by the thick darkness

²¹ Refer *Liminal and Mythic Selves*.

that surrounds the figure. The nudity here represents vulnerability, humility and surrender. She has chosen to enter the underworld.

Liminal and Mythic Selves

Overview

In this section, I present the creative findings that I have attributed to liminal or mythic selves. It comprises the following creative works:

Life writing

Living at half mast in a hurricane.

Visual art galleries²²:

Descent of the feminine:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1LhHw9PzeI8b8CA2ziTjsiSH0rZ9g-jK>

Death and rebirth:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ylUdphz6FZyoc7jch0_bLBpbfDKHbn36

Liminal narratives:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=19appPYP17Rbrv_xPSO5n1kfb25wqEVIZ

Film - *Returning Home* sections:

Discovering our Mythic Selves

Myths of the Western World

Introduction

I have categorised the following material as relating to *liminal stories* as they, at least initially, reside beneath the limen of the conscious mind. I have used the term 'liminal' to refer to aspects of the self that are less readily accessible, unconscious and possibly hidden. Liminal stories may include buried or exiled parts of ourselves that are hidden within the unconscious because they were formed in response to traumas too difficult to be consciously held (refer Schwartz 2004, p. 6).

²² The very fine details of the paintings can be viewed in the TIFF files here (credit Dean Whitby photo documentation):

https://drive.google.com/open?id=111cL73yJZc2f54_Xyn7RASq4IJXcD9ah

Narratives relating to my illness appear here, acknowledging its hidden psychological aspects. I also reference the parts of the self that I see as mythic or archetypal, as well as idealised aspects that appear in my film (*Returning Home*, 2017).

I understand the liminal space to be non-linear and not time-bound; liminal stories often emerge from beneath the threshold of everyday consciousness appearing in different guises until they can be brought forward and integrated through the individuation process (Jung 1989, p. 196). The materials that emerged during a particularly evocative time in this creative investigation were stories that had been carried through the generations, my maternal legacy.

As I was completing *Providence*, I had a powerful dream:

I am walking alone through an extensive garden that leads to a shrine at the top of a hill. No one else is around and it seems to be outside the usual visiting hours. As I enter the shrine and walk toward the heart of the building, I notice a box with a flip lid inside which is a treasured artifact. I recognize the artifact as a pendant my mother wore on a long fine chain around her neck that would hang above her heart. The pendant is gold, shaped like an oval, within which is another oval section (like an egg inside an egg) and my mother always wore it when she was alive. I find myself standing in front of a woman who is a senior member of the group responsible for maintaining the shrine. I say: 'I am the daughter of the woman who wore the pendant'. I am rather shy and a little uncertain - will she accept me as the 'descendant', the prodigal daughter who has finally returned? I then realise that the shrine is a building of remembrance, one that has been there for a long time, but it is only now that I have come to claim my place.

The dream of the daughter in the shrine filled me with a sense of centeredness and belonging, I felt that I had belatedly come home and was somehow ready to reconnect to my mother and all she represented for me when she was alive. With her powerful trauma stories, Lydia left me a potent

inheritance, one that I held from a young age and, paradoxically, from which I had spent much of my life trying to escape. In the dream, the pendant symbolically represents this legacy (the egg within another egg), a burden that Lydia had perhaps held for her own mother. Almost three decades have passed since my mother's death, but only during this investigation have pieces of her story been revealed, and in understanding them, I have deepened my own recognition.

In a sense, my ancestors were the archetypes²³ that shaped my life: the writer and academic (my great uncle, Heinz), the lover, artist, bohemian and free spirit (my grandfather, Kurt), the women tormented by grief and destabilized by demons from her past, desperately seeking home and love (my grandmother, Charlotte, and my mother, Lydia). I came to see that my stories were their stories.

As I became further immersed in the creative process, my dreams and creative practice continued to offer new material; previously unseen narratives emerged to be held and digested. As I descended into these deeply held stories, images emerged, which seemed to reference my inherited narratives or 'legacy burdens' (Schwartz 2004, p. 6).

An image emerged during the creative investigation at this time, one I called *Shared wounds*.

²³ Jung writes of encounters with 'archetypes' as narrative patterns or tendencies, images or energies that are universally present within the human collective unconscious, that reside within us from birth (Jung 1976, p. 348).

Shared wounds, 2017, oil and gold size on canvas, 102 x 76cm

Shared wounds is complex and striking both symbolically and artistically. It consists of layers of gold size over a canvas that had many previous lives, the surface is textured by brush marks and impasto, hinting at the narratives beneath its surface. Gold size has responded to a glazing process that included tinted oils as well as acrylic gloss. Over this surface, I have applied thick lines of vermilion oil paint squeezed directly from the tube, that seem to form scars, alluding to deep wounds healed, but raw. *Shared wounds* heralded the emergence of my most potent liminal narratives, which came to light in subsequent months.

Inherited Narratives.

On May 5th, 2017, for the second time in two years, I was asked to open a festival celebrating arts, wellbeing and spirituality. Speaking to an audience of one hundred community members, I shared a shorter version of *Returning Home* (2017) and reflected on the way creative play can offer an opportunity for our liminal stories to speak to us through the language of the arts.

I have always had a terror of public speaking, one that I have had to manage in order to share this creative research and its capacity to heal and transform. During the festival, I co-facilitated what proved to be an evocative group process using the arts to explore individual and community story.

Two of my girlfriends, both Jewish, met me after the workshop. It was two o'clock in the afternoon in a small coastal town where the festival was held. My body was already screaming with a neuralgic pain, something that happens regularly when my nervous system is overtaxed emotionally and physically²⁴. As the three of us set off to have a late lunch together, one of the women, my co-facilitator in the workshop, was giving herself a very hard time in regard to her performance in the workshop. The other is a close friend, a psychologist, and someone who has spent many years unravelling the impact of the holocaust trauma she inherited from her family. After much deliberation, we settled on a café and ordered our lunch from the proprietor, whose smile became increasingly forced as each of our orders required thorough and time consuming investigations of ingredients due to our food allergies or preferences, and each of the dishes we ordered needed to be modified at our request. The kitchen was closing and the staff were exasperated. I was reminded of how stressful ordering food was with certain friends, most of whom are highly sensitive for various reasons.

When I returned home I started to investigate the correlation between high sensitivity and food intolerances, particularly in the light of my own autoimmune condition as well as the patterns I had noticed with particular friends and their responses to 'digesting life'. My research led to the

²⁴ I have been diagnosed with a cluster of autoimmune responses that include Fibromyalgia, Chronic Fatigue Syndrome, Adrenal fatigue, Irritable Bowel Syndrome and Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome.

phenomenon of prolonged sympathetic nervous system dominance and its impact on health. I understood that the sympathetic nervous system triggers the human brain's 'fight or flight response', a reflex that alters the functioning of human body, one evolutionarily adapted to ensure survival in high-risk situations (Todd 2015, pp. 38-39). The activation of the sympathetic nervous system results in extensive physical, neurological and biochemical changes. The functions of resting, repairing and renewing are replaced with the suppression of the immune, digestive and reproductive systems in order to prepare the organism for possible attack or to mobilize energy reserves should a person need to flee. Apparently, in some of us, sympathetic nervous system activation can become the predominant nervous system response (Todd 2015, p. 39). Chronic sympathetic dominance can result in food intolerances, immunological suppression, hormonal difficulties, adrenal fatigue, autoimmune conditions, inflammation responses, anxiety, and depression, among other symptoms (Todd 2015, pp. 43-44).

As a trauma therapist, I have noticed that some of my clients who have experienced overwhelming trauma as well as chronic stress also had challenges in digesting life both metaphorically and literally, suffering gastrointestinal sensitivity and, at times, struggling to manage the emotional impact of challenging events in their lives. Sympathetic nervous system dominance is correlated with experiences of trauma, as well as with being a descendent of those who had been exposed to severe trauma such as the Jewish Holocaust (Yehuda et al. 2016, p. 372). It was becoming clearer to me that my sensitivity, my illness and my heritage were possibly linked.

I made the decision that the time had come to determine whether my maternal grandmother was, in fact, Jewish. There had never been any doubt my grandfather was Jewish but my mother had always been uncertain of her mother's ethnic background. As a child I was not exposed to any cultural or religious aspects of Judaism, and the possibility of being Jewish was not a part my childhood identity. For her own reasons, of the many religions and spiritual philosophies Lydia exposed me to, Judaism was not one.

I began a search by typing my grandmother's surname into the google search engine; I asked: '*Is Dindas a Jewish name?*' In the social media material

that appeared, a Jewish genealogy group caught my attention. This group was a philanthropically funded collection of genealogists and scholars who offered their assistance in tracing families impacted by the holocaust. The next morning, I asked my father for all my mother's records. That afternoon he scanned and emailed her Czechoslovakian birth certificate as well as documents relating to her residency in the United Kingdom. The evening of the same day, I posted my grandparents' names and my mother's Czech birth certificate on the Jewish genealogy site requesting assistance.

Lara Bardsley's request for assistance, 'Jewish Genealogy Portal Facebook Group', Computer screen shot, 8 May 2017.

As I slept, the group traced the threads of my family's story. The correspondence that ensued between group members and myself was flooded with images and links to holocaust databases, refugee records and interpretations of historical events that were occurring at the time. My interchange with the group members read like a gripping and tragic script as each piece of the puzzle came to light.

Lydia Leuner's Czechoslovakian birth certificate, digital image.

According to the translation of Lydia's birth certificate, she was born in Prague to Charlotte Dindas, who was born in Breslau, now known as Wroclaw, Poland. Breslau, it appears, was the last town held by the Nazi regime in the closing months of World War Two. I read that eighty thousand civilians lost their lives in the vicious and bloody street fighting before Nazi surrender, in addition to members of a large Jewish population in Breslau who were exterminated (Hargreaves 2014). My relatives were among them.

Kurt Leuner, my grandfather, and his brother Heinz were also born in Breslau. The two brothers left Breslau for Prague, Czechoslovakia where, according to my recent communication with Marion (Heinz's surviving daughter) they enjoyed the intellectual and cultural richness of the city. Heinz worked as a journalist and later wrote a number of books including one titled *When compassion was a crime* (Leuner 1966), which documented the courageous acts of Germans who had risked their lives to save the Jewish people in World War Two. Kurt had lived a colourful bohemian life in Prague

amongst the intelligentsia. Marion (although she was aged five at the time) describes Kurt as a handsome, enigmatic man, a gifted artist who was frequently employed by the Prague opera as a set designer and painter. Kurt held painting classes for the upper-class women of Prague and drew caricatures of Hitler for a subversive magazine. He was known to be a lover of women. Marion recounted the story of my grandparents meeting, Kurt was dazzled by my grandmother's beauty as she washed a shop front window, her fair hair catching the mid-afternoon light. Thus began a relationship into which two children were born, my mother and my aunt.

My grandparents did not marry; I am unclear as to why. Perhaps it was because Jews were forbidden to at that time, or because they were an inter-racial couple, or maybe they did not want to. Although Marion implied that Charlotte was not Jewish, my mother intuitively sensed that she was. There was much deliberation by Jewish genealogy group members regarding my grandmother's ethnic background and the data they found is inconclusive. According to Marion, Charlotte was one of many women loved by Kurt. They were lovers for over four years as the ages of their children reveal. Despite his noticeable absence on Lydia's birth certificate, Kurt's family recognised Lydia and my aunt as his. I have not been able to locate any of my grandmother's living relatives. In a Czech refugee database documenting refugees who escaped Prague at that time, Charlotte is listed with her maiden name but the children had their father's surname.

Through the trail of notifications that appeared in my inbox over the next three days, details that eluded my mother when she was alive revealed themselves. Heinz had fled with his wife Alice and their daughter Marion to the United Kingdom where he eventually renounced Judaism and became a Christian Minister. Before he left Prague, Heinz implored his brother and Charlotte to come with him. Kurt refused, strongly identifying as a German citizen. Charlotte, however, followed a few months later with their children; her youngest, my mother, was 5 weeks old and my aunt was three. Charlotte made a desperate journey alone across Europe to Glasgow, Scotland where Heinz had relocated with his family. On her arrival in the United Kingdom, she was classified as an enemy alien and granted exemption from internment.

My mother's residency papers (when she became a ward of the United Kingdom) reveal that Charlotte and her two young children eventually found accommodation at the Douglas Castle Gatehouse, Anworth, where they resided for two years in exchange for Charlotte's services as maid.

My grandmother became increasingly distressed. Marion said she remembers Charlotte's visits when she had appeared to be terrified and miserable, begging not to have to return to her employer. I can only imagine what it was like for her; she did not speak English and was bound by her poverty and her two dependents to work in circumstances that may well have been oppressive. In my mind's eye she waits for her lover Kurt to join her, but he never comes.

I located the address of the cottage through my mother's residency papers and by chance, I found it advertised for sale on a local real estate website. In this video, eighty years after my grandmother and her children were there, it is a picturesque two-story stone cottage beautifully renovated, surrounded by lush pastures and golden daffodils. In my mind's eye I can see my grandmother moving through the hallways, cleaning and cooking in the kitchen, stoking the magnificent fireplace and, no doubt, cleaning the many window panes that overlooked the garden to the pastures beyond. Perhaps the children shared the tiny upstairs attic space. In the video (see the link below) a cheerful soundtrack plays adding further nuance as the viewer is led virtually through the residence. This is inconsistent with what I know of its history for it was here, Marion revealed, that Charlotte attacked her employer with a kitchen knife.

Williamson & Henry, Solicitors and Estate Agents, *Anwoth Cottage*, Still images from *Anwoth Cottage, Anwoth, Gatehouse of Fleet on Vimeo*, viewed 10 May 2017 <https://vimeo.com/163225261>.

Lydia's residential papers record that she and her sister were taken from the cottage and placed in emergency care, a Salvation Army Hostel in Glasgow, where they stayed for eight months. My mother was two years old and her sister, five when they were relocated to an orphanage in Newbury, England. It is unlikely that they ever saw their mother again.

As I tried to digest this information, the Jewish Genealogy group sent a link to Kurt Leuner's documented fate. The holocaust victim database reveals a comprehensive trail of information, fingerprints, headshots and page after

page of detailed (yet to be translated) hand written notes. *Horror, seemingly sanitized by efficiency*, I write in my diary.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the profile of Kurt Leuner on the Holocaust.cz database. The browser's address bar shows the URL: www.holocaust.cz/en/database-of-victims/victim/105426-kurt-leuner/. The page layout includes a left-hand navigation menu with options like 'BACK TO HOME PAGE', 'HISTORY', 'SOURCES', 'EDUCATION', 'DATABASE OF DIGITISED DOCUMENTS', 'DATABASE OF VICTIMS', and 'ABOUT HOLOCAUST.CZ'. The main content area features a portrait of Kurt Leuner, a 'Print' button, and a 'Last change' timestamp of 12. 01. 2016. A 'HISTORICAL CONTEXT' section provides statistics for two deportation routes: 'Ba (10. 08. 1942, Prague -> Terezin)' (1474 deported, 1302 murdered, 172 survived) and 'Bb (20. 08. 1942, Terezin -> Riga)' (1001 deported, 1001 murdered, 0 survived). Below this, a 'RELATED DOCUMENTS' section displays four scanned documents with captions: 'Leuner Kurt: Vybavění', 'Leuner Kurt: Žádost o povolení pobytu', 'Leuner Kurt: Žádost o povolení pobytu', and 'Leuner Kurt: Žádost o povolení pobytu'. Social media sharing icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn are visible in the bottom right corner.

Kurt Leuner's record on database of holocaust victims, screenshot, holocaust.cz, Database of victims, viewed 10 May 2017, <<https://www.holocaust.cz/en/database-of-victims/victim/105426-kurt-leuner/>>

The information that is written in English reveals that on the 10th of August 1942 Kurt was taken to the concentration camp Terezin, and ten days later was transported to Riga, Latvia where he was exterminated. It is perhaps synchronistic that the documents detailing my grandfather's fate came to my attention around the time of his birthday on the 21st May. Kurt was born in 1909, 108 years ago as I write this. He died a few months after his thirty-third birthday. At the time he was murdered, he was married to a woman called Maria Leuner.

My grandfather's wife, Maria, is reported to have died few months earlier, the previous June, aged twenty-six. I have not been able to find her name on any of the holocaust victim databases. As far as I can tell, her maiden name indicates that she may have been Jewish, but then, so does my grandmother's. The records provided by the Jewish genealogy scholars reveal that Kurt married Maria the year after Charlotte fled the Nazi regime with

their two daughters. Charlotte arrived in Scotland on December 12th, 1939; Kurt married Maria in Prague in November, 1940.

Over a late night Skype conversation a few weeks later, in response to my reassurance and repeated requests, Marion cautiously revealed the missing pieces of information, ones that her mother Alice had disclosed as she neared the grave. Charlotte had attempted to jump from a bridge in Glasgow with a child in each arm. Stopped by a bystander, she was eventually put in a sanatorium. Her two daughters were placed in emergency care, then in an orphanage. They remained in institutions for the next three years. Two years after attempting to take her life on the bridge, Charlotte committed suicide.

Charlotte Dindas's refugee record, screenshot from Jewish Genealogy Portal, Facebook group, Screenshot, viewed 10 May 2017.

An image from a website (findmypast.com) shows a yellow scrap of paper with perforated holes on its left hand side so it can be filed in a minute clip file. Charlotte is identified as female enemy alien born on the 27th August, 1909. In a hand-written script across the top are the words: 'Died on 27.8.43'. It would have been her 34th birthday.

Those who survived the holocaust waited in the agony of uncertainty for word of their loved ones. As the official records of people who had perished in the holocaust made their way to across the globe, hopes were shattered and relationships forever torn apart. Marion's mother Alice learned

that almost all of her relatives in Europe had been exterminated, almost a year after they had died.

I met my Aunt Alice twice, once in my late teens and again in my early twenties. She was a very slim, elegant woman with an intense presence, strong opinions and an aversion to sentimentality. In our frank conversations, Alice had made her contempt for my grandmother and my mother known. She also revealed that she had been in love with my grandfather Kurt as well as his brother Heinz but recognized Heinz as a more secure marriage partner and married him. She explained that she had wanted to adopt my aunt but not my mother who, she said, reminded her of Charlotte. Heinz, the children's legal guardian, refused to separate them and after almost three years in State care, he arranged for them to be fostered by a couple in Colchester, Essex to whom he had been introduced through his church affiliations. By this time, Lydia was five and her sister eight years old. The girls had a reportedly miserable childhood and adolescence, always glossed over by my mother and aunt when I asked about it. When my aunt wanted to marry she needed Heinz's permission because she was underage, and through this event, Heinz reconnected with his nieces. Immediately after she was married, my aunt left for Australia. A few years later my parents followed as 'ten pound poms'. Heinz, in his capacity as a Christian minister, presided over both of their marriages.

Hung

Hung, 2016, digital print.

In *Hung*, the body of a naked woman is hung like a blood-drained carcass in a cool store. Through the sepia tones and editing techniques that I have employed, the image seems to hold 'the trace of the real' (Adams 2000, p. 4), suggesting that it archives an event long past. *Hung* (2016) was taken almost a year before these holocaust narratives came to light.

Hung is part of the visual gallery *Descent of the feminine*²⁵, which appears to reference the narrative arc of the hero myth as described by Campbell (2008, pp. 23-28) in his writing on mythic narratives as they appear throughout different cultures. Various myths refer to a descent into unknown territories and a return home, forever altered²⁶. There may come a time when a heroine is stripped of all by which she has been previously defined; her finery is removed, her identity shed, and in many cases (before she meets her true self) she is stripped of her skin and her life itself. The trials of the heroine are many; before she can emerge from the crucible of her liminal initiation, she must surrender, be humbled and her power disintegrated. To return to the world, the heroine must face her darkest elements and turn away from the temptation to remain in the undifferentiated stateⁱ. If she survives her reckoning in the underworld, she may return, her wisdom enhanced by the experience.

The Sumerian poem *The descent of Inanna* (c 1900-1600 BC) resonates with the visual liminal narratives that *Descent of the feminine* embodies. The poem reveals a woman, who is humbled, forced to enter the underworld naked where she is dismembered, hung upon a meat hook and left to rot.²⁷

²⁵ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1LhHw9PzeI8b8CA2ziTjsiSH0rZ9g-jK_

²⁶ Returning Home after a quest that traverses unknown territory, battling monsters and surviving temptations from one's true and noble path is a theme in Ancient Greek literature referred to as *Nostos* where the hero returns to his place of origin, altered, wiser and often immortalised. In this sense, 'home' is a place for which the protagonist longs (the origin of the term nostalgia) and seeks to return (Bonifazi 2009, pp. 481-510).

²⁷ Inanna is the Queen of heaven. Beautiful, arrogant and powerful, she has an insatiable sexual appetite, consuming and destroying her consorts, ruthless in her disregard of them. In the Sumerian poem, we meet Inanna as she journeys from heaven to the underworld to visit her recently widowed sister, Ereshkigal, Queen of the Dead. Dressed in her finery—her crown of heaven, her sceptre and wonderful jewels—Inanna stands at the threshold to the underworld. She proclaims to Neti (the gatekeeper) that she is the Goddess of heaven, demanding entry to see her sister and attend the funeral of her sister's husband Gugalanna. Neti delivers the news that Inanna is waiting entry to Underworld, to Ereshkigal. In what appears to be a fit of jealousy Ereshkigal demands that Inanna be stripped of her royal garments at each gate she passes through in the underworld. As she descends further into the unknown, Inanna enters the throne room of her sister 'naked and bowed low'. Here she is judged and Ereshkigal, enraged, fastens the 'eye of death' on her sister, striking her, turning her

The sense of being dismembered, hung and left to alone in the underworld is a narrative that lay waiting for me when I descended into the liminal space. Through this investigation, I experienced the wounded feminine, the fault lines that shaped the lives of the women in my family. *Hung* seems to visually reference my mother's suffering, her early childhood trauma—the loss of her mother, father, home and most of her family—as well as her immense physical suffering, that my father and I witnessed when we nursed her as she was dying. *Hung* speaks to my grandmother's suffering and her suicide, and most potently to the racial extermination of the Jews in the holocaust. *Hung* also seems to reference my own suffering – my emotional distress, grief, losses and chronic illness.

At the time of writing this, I had a dream from which I awoke, shaken:

I am buried alive in an underground cavern. Carefully I try to manoeuvre my arm so as to keep a small tunnel of earth through which the air from the outside world is flowing from collapsing. This is my link to survival but it is not only my life that I am sustaining. I can hear the voices of my ancestors who are buried in the layers of earth below me. I am struggling to allow the air to flow in from the outside world while also attempting to attract the attention of anyone who may be moving through the destruction on the surface. Will someone notice that I, in fact all of us, are still alive? Will they hear me calling for help, dig us out and free us?

It has been remarkable for me to discover, through this investigation, how my family's narratives of trauma and loss have shaped my life. The dream suggests that buried within me are the voices of my ancestors; by releasing them from beneath liminal space and bringing them to the surface, all of us may live and breathe in new life.

into a corpse and leaving her hung on a hook on the wall where she is left to rot (Wolkstein & Kramer 1983).

Postscript

Charlotte Dindas with Lydia (infant) and Sylvia Leuner, Photographer unknown, circa 1939, photographic film print.

A few weeks after I completed the first draft of this section of the investigation, I discovered this photograph hidden in a large box at the bottom of a cupboard I was cleaning out. It is the only photograph I have of Charlotte. She sits on a bench in front of a stone cottage, holding my mother, a plump baby asleep in her arms. Beside them is my aunt, a toddler in a hand-knitted dress, a rag doll in her small grasp and grinning shyly. My grandmother smiles warmly at the camera; she is beautiful, dressed in a worn dark suit jacket, fitted skirt and a light blouse with a long, loose collar. In the black and white photograph, her hair appears to be blond, her face open and broad, her cheekbones pronounced. She and my aunt turn their faces toward the sun and gaze at the photographer who remains unknown. I see in her eyes relief and perhaps hope for future. In the bottom left of the image, her shadow appears in dark relief distorted by the stone wall of the cottage behind her. I cannot help but wonder at whom she is smiling so warmly. I do not sense her suffering, so immense that within four years of this day, she took her own life, leaving behind her two small children.

Journal entry, May 14th, 2018

I am struggling to complete this part of investigation but impending deadlines call for me to contain it as best I can. I want to do so authentically, without forcing a resolution that currently eludes me. In the systematic shaping and editing of these practice-led findings, I find myself amongst these most evocative stories on Mother's Day, at the same time of year when I wrote them, a year ago. I still feel nauseous as I read the material; the re-writing process is laborious because I keep losing myself in the story. Parts of me rage at Alice and Heinz for abandoning first my grandmother, and then her young children, to their fate. There is a mother within me who longs to embrace my own mother and aunt as young children, to love and protect them and adopt them as my own. I want to give my grandmother the psychological care she deserved, to help her find her way through the loss and trauma she experienced. Toward my grandfather, I am ambivalent. I recognize myself in his creativity and free spiritedness, and (for much of my life) his search for love with many different lovers. He did not choose to leave Prague with my grandmother and the family they had created together, and because he didn't, he prematurely lost his own life.

I remember confronting my aunt about her disappearance from my life after my mother died when I was twenty-one years old. At the time of our conversation, Lydia had been gone for twenty-five years. We were in the hallway of an acute care ward of the hospital where my stepmother (my father's second wife) was dying. My aunt tearfully apologized, acknowledging that it was too hard for her to be close to me as I reminded her of her sister, the loss of whom had been devastating for her. Now, I feel I owe my aunt an apology, as the elder child, her memories of these events I have written about would have impacted upon her in ways I could not possibly imagine. Each character in our shared stories has only been able to digest what they were able. There were consequences for the way we sought to survive.

My husband and I are preparing a Mother's Day lunch for my father and mother-in-law. My husband has cooked a beautiful meal; I have cleaned the house and tended the garden. On impulse, I search for the photo of Charlotte with my mother in her arms and my aunt beside her. I have placed it in an album full of miscellaneous photos. Beside it I find the photo of my father as a young boy looking vulnerable and gangly as he attempts a slight smile for the photographer. On the same page is a

photo of my mother, perhaps seven or eight years old. Lydia glances warily toward the camera, she is in a field, her hand rests gently on the head of a dog, whose eyes are contentedly closed, panting, mouth open in a canine smile. Lydia looks so like myself at that age that I catch my breath.

The sun is streaming through the window of the room in which I meditate, paint and do yoga each morning. There is a bookcase here, the shelves are already full of photos but as I gather together these images, I know I will find room for them.

Mythic Selves

Inside each of us is the hero, the saint, the goddess. Perhaps, if we all scratch a little deeper, we'll find the trickster, the tyrant, even death itself. These mythic beings can work through us. Some say, that if we know these selves that lie hidden within, we can become whole. (*Returning Home*, 2017, excerpt from voice-over)

As I moved further into this creative investigation, the narratives that emerged (mine and those of the people I interviewed) seem to be concerned with epic tales, idealized aspects of the self, and instinctual drives or myths. In this investigation, I refer these aspects as 'mythic selves'.

Jung determined that mythic narratives emerge from liminal sources to leave their deposit on collective life, appearing in religion, symbol, culture and art (Jung 1989, p. 336). He refers to the connection with mythology and archetypes in the following manner:

The archetypes...are not intellectually invented. They are always there and they produce certain processes in the unconscious one could best compare with myths. That's the origin of mythology. Jung (1976 p. 348)

In the film interviews (*Returning Home*, 2017), some participants appear to be embodying such mythic or archetypal aspects of themselves. For example, the

young woman dressed as 'Robin' explains the transformation of the character she is embodying (Carrie Kelly) as an ordinary girl who became the heroine 'Robin' when she was rescued by Batman— 'inspiring [Kelly] to become more than a victim' (*Returning Home*, 2017). 'Robin' had designed and created her own costume and wore it 'because it inspired a part of me that wanted to be more than just an ordinary person' (*Returning Home*, 2017, 'Robin'). In doing so, she is illustrating the transformative potential of mythic narratives - to actualize archetypal drives and mobilize our hidden potential. Houston writes of the power of myth in assisting us to know who we are, or the potential of who we may become:

When we descend into the forgotten knowings of earlier or deeper phases of our existence, we often find hidden potentials, the unfulfilled and unfinished seedlings of what we still contain...to gain access to our inner storehouse of capacities and use them to prepare ourselves for the greater agenda... (Houston, *in* Dunne 2015, p. 19)

As Houston (2015) suggests, our mythic selves guide us toward evolving our potential as well as referencing collective unconscious narratives. In another interview (*Returning Home*, 2017), the young man dressed as an avatar monk refers to mythic aspects of the story he embodied and its collective associations. He says:

It goes right back to Greek Mythology and all the Shinto mythologies...even though they are stories, they do have a real morality to them that is still relevant today— even after thousands of years of years—and even though it's new, it's still the very basic human ideas. Even though we are all different, it's kind of what makes you the same...isn't it? (*Returning Home*, 2017, 'Avatar Monk')

The function of our mythic selves in guiding us toward our highest potential or anchoring us in challenging times, is also evident in my interview with Louise - the woman who appeared as a *Star Trek* crew-member in my film (*Returning Home* 2017). Louise refers to the inspiration she found in the narrative content of the *Star Trek* television series, one that guided her through difficulties in her childhood,

helping her to understand human potential, temper emotion with logic, recognise the value of all life and begin to trust her own intuition. She concludes:

Star Trek is me, *I am*. And what I've gone through in my life...but right now I'm boldly going where Louise has never gone before²⁸ and I'm going to leave a wake in my path while I'm doing it. (*Returning Home*, 2017, 'Star Trek crew member')

Tea Time

The function of mythology in defining the sense of who we are is perhaps most intimately revealed in *Tea time* (Bardsley 2017, p. 15).

Tea time, 2015, digital print

A middle-aged man dressed as the super hero *Captain America* sits in a darkened suburban home sharing a cup of tea with an elderly woman. The

²⁸ *Star Trek* was created by Gene Roddenberry and premiered on television in 1966. The voice-over of the television episodes and the subsequent feature films refers to voyages of the starship with its mission to 'boldly go where no one has gone before'.

man's eyes are downcast and the woman stares into the middle distance; there is a sense of disconnection between them.

I interviewed this man (who is my husband) in *Returning Home* (2017). He recounts:

My idea of what was right and wrong comes from characters like *Captain America* who really embody what is right and that acceptance – that it's ok to be flawed, that it's ok to experience loss, it's ok to make mistakes but ultimately, it's more about your intention... your intention to do what's right.

(*Returning Home*, 2017, 'Captain America')

In the uncut documentary interview, my husband talks about growing up, how to be a better person, and learning about morality from mythic narratives rather than from his home environment. As I am able to witness his relationship with myth, I believe that these mythic characters allow him to reconnect with idealized aspects of himself, and as a primary school teacher, he will embody them (as often as possible) to assist him to educate young people regarding their own positive qualities. *Tea time* speaks to me of a man who has found a way to transcend the challenges of his youth and engage with his family as an adult, perhaps not fully seen yet able to share a cup of tea in companionship.

Romantic Love as a Myth.

Throughout much of my adult life, my most potent mythic narrative was to search for wholeness in romantic love. If this investigation had commenced fifteen years earlier, the emergent material would have been saturated with narratives concerned with my experiences in my romantic love affairs.²⁹

²⁹ I did, in fact, commence an investigation into the healing potential of non-ordinary states of consciousness fifteen years ago that was hijacked by the potent (and dramatic) narrative content, which emerged through my romantic relationships.

After the kiss, 2016, digital print.

The visual gallery *Death and rebirth*³⁰ visually references my life narratives in romantic love, the mythic arc of intoxication, unraveling and descent into suffering, integration and transcendence³¹, one that I repeatedly cycled through as I searched

³⁰ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ylUdphz6FZyoc7jch0_bLBpbfDKHbn36

³¹ As discussed in the hero mythic narrative, to which I have previously referred – see Bonifazi, (2009, pp. 481-510) and Campbell (2008). Campbell (1988, p. 121) describes myths as referencing things that cannot be named; they are metaphors that transcend thought. There are definitive stages in a

for unity and peace in the arms of someone else. *After the kiss* speaks to the beginning of this cycle, the promise hidden in a first kiss. I refer to my developing insight regarding the myth of romantic love and the function it played in my life as a younger woman, in the film *Returning Home* (2017):

Many of us search for ourselves in the arms of another. We seek the perfect person to complete us. Like a dance we weave in and out of love. I've come to suspect that what I'm looking for is a special sort of love. (*Returning Home*, 2017, excerpt of voice-over)

The journal I kept at the time suggests my awareness of how the mythic elements of wholeness and belonging were being projected onto my romantic relationships:

Perhaps the more reason we have to escape our own life, the tighter we hold to the magic of Eros and the longer we seek our union with the divine through his exotic embrace. My thirst for inner peace and fulfillment seemed to drive me ever deeper and ever further to edges I never thought I would traverse. It was as if I had sat myself in a pot of cold water on top of a low heat and not until I began to cook did I realise that the water was boiling.

If I were to tell a story of the dissolution of a romantic love affair I would have so many to choose from that I would be paralyzed by indecision. Although each story begins as non-fiction, even now, reading the excerpts of my own diaries from years ago, I see my younger self's interpretation of fact as frequently narcissistic and often flawed. Where I believed my actions justified, I now see the pain that I caused in pursuit of everlasting love.

mythic narrative, according to Campbell (2008), that follow the hero's journey through an arc to return to everyday life, forever enriched. The hero's journey follows the protagonist from ordinary reality, to hearing the call, embarking on a quest, descending into the liminal space, wherein the hero is tested, reckons with his darkest fears, and eventually transcends from the liminal underworld to the everyday with a prize, one that is transformative, allowing him to live a life enriched by the dark territory he has traversed.

I believe there are times in our lives when our unconscious selves take over the wheel of the life stories that transport us. One minute we are admiring the view of the passing scenery and the next we have lost years to a deeply buried self that has emerged and surreptitiously taken over the navigation of our vehicle. We may come back to ourselves years later only to shake our heads at the tracks that tear their way across the landscape of our world and wonder: 'What the hell happened there?'

There had never been room in my romantic scenarios for human imperfections on anyone's part and I did not seem to notice that the names and faces of my heroes changed with relatively rapid succession over the years. The dramatic backdrop of these love affairs also varied, with tales of love and loss set in the wind torn coastal splendor of The Great Ocean Road in Victoria, the steamy tropical tension of Darwin, and the beautiful lush paradise of Northern New South Wales.

In this investigation, the drive to know myself and become whole through my romantic relationships is less apparent than in my earlier creative investigations and life-writing. Many of the experiences that I documented in my late twenties and mid-thirties make for engaging reading, particularly those I wrote when I was training with Stanislav Grof in altered states of consciousness and was most permeable to the emergence of transpersonal material in my lived experience. Passionate love affairs were punctuated with vivid and prophetic dreams, visions and synchronistic events. For almost twenty years, the narratives of my self were oriented toward what I now see as archetypal impulses and inherited patterns around seeking transcendence and bliss through romantic love. I have been tempered by age; my expectations have changed along with my experiences. A year into this investigation, I wrote the following in my journal:

Now I am the age my mother was when she died of cancer when I was twenty-one and she was forty-nine. In terms of the stories of my forbears, I am both wise and ignorant. I have discovered that stories that shape our lives need not be told around a campfire or shared tenderly at bedtime, they may never be voiced but can still wind their way through the fabric of our cells, enter our genes and drive us unconsciously forward. A rhythmic beat, a lost thread seeking resolution through the generations, a tapestry of heartbreak and survival. My dreams, my pain and stupid decisions have told

me much about the women in my family and the legacy left by the men. Their talents, doubts and demons are also mine. We are have all been swept along by rivers that have flowed through us all.

In retrospect, I see my patterns of seeking wholeness through romantic love as part of a more multifaceted narrative pattern or COEX (Grof 2012, pp. 38-41). This axis of my self-narratives may represent an unconscious drive to resolve the loneliness of my childhood, with the loss of my mother, as well as my inherited narratives — my mother seeking belonging and safety after her immense losses, my grandmother's loss of her lover and her immense pain. These stories centred on searching for love and belonging stretch into the distant past, beyond my capacity to know their origins; they may have become one of the inherited schemas (refer Knox 2005, p. 9) through which three generations of women have viewed their lives.

It is not uncommon to orientate one's life toward romantic love. Jungian analyst Johnston (1989) suggests there is a tendency in western culture to project the mythic symbolism uniting opposites onto our everyday relationships. As little girls, we are told stories of handsome princes who come to the rescue of incarcerated princesses, offering them freedom and bliss through marriage. From these stories (echoed in Hollywood romantic films), we are encouraged to seek spiritual completion in another. The human desire for companionship becomes diverted into a search for a perfect mate, someone who will embrace the aspects of ourselves that even we find abhorrent. This projected fantasy 'other half of us' offers endless love (even if we are incapable of offering it to ourselves); she or he will complete us, fulfil our desires and bestow upon our lives the perfect mix of excitement and security (Johnston 1989, pp. 30-31). If we are able to bring to consciousness the idealized or wounded male and female aspects that may exist within our own psyche, we may move toward integrating these parts of us instead of seeking them in another. As I have done so, I have been able to enjoy the companionship and care that a loving relationship can provide without projecting upon it the expectation of perfection (which, in the past, led to tragic consequences).

When I met the model who appears in the movement sequence of my film (*Returning Home*, 2017, 'Myths of the Western World') and the visual gallery *Death*

*and rebirth*³², she seemed to embody a liminal, dream-like quality. I spoke to her of my research and my desire to explore what it means to know our selves through the language of the arts. She was intrigued, and while politely declining my request to interview her in the documentary (stating that she would not know what to say), she offered to share her inner narratives in an embodied way for the camera. During the half day we worked together, there was a strong sense of trust that developed between us; the visual images that I have included in the gallery *Death and rebirth* and in the film *Returning Home* are the most intimate and evocative outcomes of our collaboration. When working with someone creatively in a safe and accepting environment, it has been my experience that there can be a symbiosis, a merging of liminal material. As I documented the model's embodied expressions of self, she appeared to give voice to my own narratives depicting a feminine archetypal expression of sensuality, love, longing, suffering and renewal.

³² *Ivory Flame* (the model's working name) is a professional art and photographic model based in the United Kingdom who frequently works on international creative projects. I had the opportunity to work with her through a contact of mine who had booked her as well as the other model (who appears in my gallery *Descent of the feminine*) and offered me the opportunity to work with each of the models when he was otherwise occupied. Both models gave their permission for the images and details of our collaboration to be used in this investigation.

Untitled (later titled Reckoning)

Untitled, 2016, digital print.

Untitled became a pivotal visual image in this investigation. I selected it to hang in the entrance of the gallery during my exhibition (Bardsley 2017, exhibition) and also on the printed invitation³³. There is an ambiguity regarding the emotional mood of the portrait; the young woman appears to be distracted by her internal state. She is sensual and vulnerable, her hair wrapped around her neck like a noose. As I reflected upon this image, it seemed to speak to the suffering of the women in my family, and particularly my own life experiences in searching for love through romance, prior to my marriage; it references my mother in the disquiet that sat beneath her beauty, and my grandmother, in her distress and eventual suicide.

Vulnerability.

In his theory of human consciousness, Schwartz refers to parts of us that have been exiled because of the trauma we have experienced, or carry the 'burdens' of our ancestors' trauma. According to Schwartz these exiled parts are deeply vulnerable and often hidden from our conscious awareness and other parts of us evolve to protect them (Schwartz & Falconer 2017, p. 37).

The image *Vulnerability* speaks to a deeply held part of me, one that was initially hidden but came to my awareness through this investigation. *Vulnerability* appears in the visual gallery *Death and rebirth*³⁴; however, when I exhibited this image (Bardsley 2017, exhibition) I drained the image of its colour.

³³ Exhibition, invitation, and media release etc:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1kc7Q8HtZEd0mw1SnJQUrBDSY-4rCAMTy>

³⁴ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ylUdphz6FZyoc7jch0_bLBpbfdKHbn36

Vulnerability, 2016, digital print.

A young woman folded in repose, the edges of the image are blurred as if she is viewed from far away; perhaps she was forgotten and recently discovered—*lonely, isolated, waiting*. This image represents a most sensitive and vulnerable part of me, one that resides beneath many other self-narratives. I sense her burden is my ancestor's trauma and the loneliness I experienced as a child; maybe she attempts to communicate her needs for gentleness and nurturing through the somatic symptoms of my illness. I feel I need to continue to form a loving connection with my vulnerability, to listen, to care for this aspect of myself and, in doing so, perhaps release this part of me from her isolation.

Illness as a liminal narrative.

In 2000, I became chronically ill and experienced a number of psychologically and physically traumatic events including contracting a potentially fatal tropical illness (*Leptospirosis*) as well as Ross River Virus. My immune system had

previously been weakened by childhood illnesses. At this time, I was thirty-three and my health and immune system were severely and permanently (I was informed) compromised. I was later diagnosed with Myalgic Encephalomyelitis (also known as Chronic Fatigue Syndrome) and Fibromyalgia. When I am not careful, chronic pain sabotages my enjoyment of life. I have included my illness as a liminal narrative as I have come to understand that despite it being unquestionably a physical illness, there are psychological components to it, many of which are subconscious. If I do not adjust the pace of my life, and be mindful of the sensitivity of my immune and nervous systems, then this aspect of my self will ensure I lose three days to a migraine, neuralgia or fatigue. In my life-writing, *Living at half mast*, I reflect on the way my illness has influenced the way I live my life.

Living at half-mast in a hurricane

The machine winds backwards for a while. Edges soften slowly. Sometimes I feel as if I am falling into somewhere deep while still aware of the noisy rush of colour on the surface.

When I no longer try to grasp at how things were, if I cease to battle or collapse into distress, then everything begins to change. Life and time begin to come in discreet moments - precious droplets, each one complete and perfect.

A beetle struggles, unable to get traction in a puddle of water. I feel the prickling sensation of its tiny legs on my fingers as I transfer it to safety, watching it extend its wings to dry.

People have stories in their eyes. With my perception more innocent, my gaze often meets theirs and we acknowledge each other's humanness with a little smile, a nod, and perhaps a brief chat about the weather.

I know the future dreams of the man who makes my coffee each day. We acknowledge each other by name and offer daily encouragement or commiseration.

Leaves have tiny veins that divide like tributaries. Bark on trees is rough, or soft and powdery.

Neighbours have rhythms like the tide. Retirees share fragments of themselves with me. When it rains, they slide my mail under the door because my mailbox is open to the weather. I have spare keys to their 'castles' in the drawer where I put 'important stuff,' and they have mine. When I emerge from my cave, sometimes looking worse for wear, they greet me. I admire their plants and they don't mention the family of possums I feed each night.

The man who lives on the corner block has promised me the first fruits from the fig, plum, lemon and olive trees that he's planted in the little pockets of soil cut into the bitumen on the nature strip. He says the manure he uses comes all the way from Greece. Many times a day he weeds and tends his tiny orchard, a helicopter of concern and pride.

Dogs smile at you and gift you with their joy.

When the days are long and lonely, when the pain seems to be winning, there is an unseen web of connection that gently tugs at me, it reminds me that I am intricately woven into the fabric of a story much larger than myself.

Hope

Paradoxically, my 'illness self', should I see it in this way, has allowed me to witness and engage in life in a new and more spacious way. I titled the painting, which references my illness, *Hope*.

Hope, 2017, oil and gold size on canvas, 122cm x 92cm.

In my art novel *Returning home*, I write:

Hope is a painting that stands alone – it is an atmospheric piece of fluidity and vibrant colour, a small area of gold leaf floats within a cloud of deep purple... *Hope* heralds a future still unknown, it is part of a story that is unfolding and shaping me as I live. (Bardsley 2017, p. 35)

Hope was the final piece I created before my exhibition (Bardsley 2017, exhibition) and signals a return from the nebulous territory beneath the limen of my

consciousness. In the final stages of this practice-led investigation, I refer to a less personal and more transcendent aspect of the self, one I have called 'a Unified Self'.

A Unified Self

Overview

This section references the creative research that I have attributed to the self in its most expansive sense, and comprises the following creative works:

Life writing:

Heartland (see Bardsley 2017, pp. 21-32)

Visual art gallery³⁵:

Heartland:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1RsBmMDxqIVZZ32zpTzrh1mgcSShCBKIm>

Film - *Returning Home*, sections:

Stories of Coming Home

Finding My Way Home

From Little Things Grow Big Things

Introduction

A unified aspect of self is a consistent theme in the theories of consciousness that have informed this investigation. Jung refers to the Self as an aspect of our psyche that brings cohesion to its multiple parts through the individuation process:

Self-reflection, or – what comes to the same thing – the urge to individuation, gathers together what is scattered and multifarious and exalts it to the original of the One...In this way our existence as separate beings, our former ego nature, is

³⁵ The very fine details of the paintings can be viewed in the TIFF files here (credit Dean Whitby photo documentation):

https://drive.google.com/open?id=111cL73yJZc2f54_Xyn7RASq4IJXcD9ah

abolished, the circle of consciousness is widened, and because the paradoxes have been made conscious, the sources of conflict are dried up. (Jung 1958, p. 265)

Similarly, Schwartz (2004, pp. 1-9) refers to a unifying aspect within a multiple consciousness; this 'Self' is differentiated from all other parts or 'selves', resides within each person and radiates a sense of wholeness, calm, curiosity, compassion, presence and wholeness (Schwartz & Falconer 2004, pp. 154-157). The related Buddhist concept of 'bodhichitta' is both a unified and divine aspect of human consciousness; the Sanskrit term is defined as 'an awakened heart of loving kindness and compassion' and is considered to be the natural state of human beings - their inherent 'Buddha Nature' (Chodron 2008, p. 207). The aim of the Buddhist practice of mindfulness is to reconnect with one's Buddha nature and bring compassionate awareness to all aspects of the self (Chodron 2008, p. 85).

I am limited in my capacity to reference this expanded Self. When moving from an embodied feeling of presence to engaging a logical, rational mind and a conceptual language, something is lost in the process. It is possible to allude to this experience of the Self through prose, images, sound, movement and sensation; creative Self-reflection can become a resonance of the embodied feeling it references. I have used the landscape of the Central Australian Desert as a creative metaphor for this central aspect of my Self.

Many years ago, on a flight from Melbourne to Darwin, I felt the call of the desert from 30,000 feet above. The window of the airplane framed the vast expanse, scarred by the footprints of ancient stories; I visually refer to this vista of the desert with its ancient oceans in *Ancient oceans*. As my youthful narcissism suddenly dropped away, I recognised that I was no more significant than a grain of sand on this landscape over which I was suspended; in that moment, I felt that I had come home to myself.

Ancient oceans, 2017, Mixed media and gold size on canvas, 102cm x 76 cm.

I write:

The proximity of the desert then with its breathtaking beauty punctuated my life story, dispelling my restlessness: taming, humbling, softening and soothing as it has each time I have made the pilgrimage to Uluru and Kata Tjuta, two of the sacred sites for the Yankunytjatjara and Pitjantjatjara people. Like the red dust that makes its way into everything, I breathe in the presence of this land, it becomes part of me and I remember who I am. Each time I return, the part of me that is unchanged and unchangeable is always there to greet me. Powerful. Infinite. Simple. Full. (Bardsley 2017, pp. 26-27)

Call to the desert, 2016, oil and gold size on canvas, 102 cm x 76 cm.

A gold leaf curtain parts to reveal a swirling cloud of reds, oranges, blues and purples; *Call to the desert* was created over a five-year period, the gold leaf applied to a painting that had lain fallow for years (in various guises). In July

2016, as I was working on this painting, I felt compelled to return to the central Australian Desert, for a week of solitary retreat. The visual gallery *Heartland*³⁶ documents this pilgrimage and speaks to my embodied experience of 'coming home' to this central unified Self.

Red earth path, Uluru, 2016, digital print.

At the time, I wrote:

Proust said that the real voyage of discovery is not in seeing new landscapes but in having new eyes. I have rediscovered the landscape that opens my eyes anew. Immersed as I have been in writing my stories, seeing the parallels of narratives I share with my female ancestors, I decided to take them with me. Today would have been my mother's 77th birthday if she had lived. I rode around Uluru on a pushbike (with my camera in the basket); I wore Lydia's locket, a wedding ring of my father's mother, my stepmother's scarf and a small golden heart-shaped ring belonging to

³⁶ Heartland visual gallery:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1RsBmMDxqlVZZ32zpTzrh1mgcSShCBKIm>

my husband's grandmother. I was held within a web of the feminine, extending back into the past and disappearing into the future.

I have found an unlikely home in the desert. I am not indigenous, I wasn't even born in Australia, but I am bonded, deeply and without doubt, to this landscape - to Kata Tjuta and Uluru - here, I find my heartland, my stillness, my Self. I cannot imagine the connection with place of another culture, but I do understand that this landscape also transports me somewhere deep within myself. When I return to the city, I feel out of sync, like the frame rate of my lived experience is too quick; in this 'heartscape' there is no separation between what lies within and without, I can rest.

Dusk, Kata Tjuta, 2017, oil and gold size on canvas, 129cm x 210cm.

Heartland, 2017, oil and gold size on canvas, 129cm x 210cm.

The gold leaf in the paintings *Dusk*, *Kata Tjuta* and *Heartland* references my feeling of unification and wholeness, overlaid by the vibrant palette of central inland Australia. Both paintings are extremely large (1.3 by 2.1 metres) and they dominate a space with an immersive and expansive presence.

Buddhist monk Thich Nhat Hahn wrote of transcendence the night before he was exiled from his beloved Vietnam in 1966, uncertain whether he would survive the next morning:

This love arises from the individual psyche, and yet the gradual eroding or sudden destruction of that psyche cannot diminish this love. It is a transcendent, ultimate love. Ordinary love can go up in smoke when confronted by your lover's faults or betrayal. Transcendent love can never diminish, because transcendent love and the objects of that love are both empty of a separate self. (Hahn 1999, p. 199)

I reference this transcendent self in *Returning Home* (2017):

... For me that true self lives in the heart...everything else is just description, it's words, it's a separation. It's not a direct experience...talking about it can be helpful to a point but it's like saying to a Martian, does he know what a raisin tastes like? You have to taste the raisin to really know what the raisin tastes like.

...The willingness to enter this state of 'grace', you can call it, where you can be open, you can 'not know' and you can just touch energetically something inside you that is already there, waiting for you. (*Returning Home*, 2017, Leanora)

Our home is inside us where the peace lies...I encourage people to learn and acquire as much education as you can but also learn, how to come back home...whatever we call [it], 'heart', whether we call [it] 'inner existence', these are the different ways that so many great people have explained it...but the experience is beyond words. Where the words end, there the experience begins.

(*Returning Home*, 2017, Charan Anand)

And in my own reflections:

...Personally, what I have learned is that in order to be aware of the preciousness of the stories both within and around me, I need to connect to a stillness, a feeling inside, for me, this feeling is 'returning home'. (*Returning Home*, 2017, excerpt of voice-over)

Looking back, I wonder whether my curiosity about human consciousness and transcendence came from an early discontent with the stories I inherited; the nature of my childhood, expansive and solitary, and the scars my mother earned, contributed to my search for peace and contentment in the arms of others or in my career, blinding me to something that was much more subtle and immensely precious - a unified feeling. When I eventually stopped running, the stories that had haunted my family caught up; I did my best to embrace and contain them, sensing that I was struggling for more than my own survival. A sense of fulfilment eluded me, although I glimpsed it through various religions and techniques; I did not want a structured community, religion or philosophy, but rather, an embodied feeling. The thirst for a transcendent, unified experience of self remained my unswerving focus.

Eventually I found a teacher, method and a simple practice that I could commit to daily³⁷. When I first began this practice in 2000, I wrote of its impact:

I have not written for many months, I sit here drawing thin lines across the white emptiness. The sun is a warm comfort on my skin, the mountains blue-green and silent, the sky a soft mist of white over azure. A faint wind tickles the unfurling tree ferns and they shiver a little. I stop, sip my tea and watch the ever-changing display that holds a restful constancy. Within me, grown from a seedling over the past year, the peace is mirrored. Slow and deep movement, the current of a river in endless flow, the warmth and dance of sunlight and the magnificent space of night, exists within my body. This body, the same one that has been ravaged and shaped by the stories of my life, holds the Infinite. I can feel it. When I remember, my breath carries me on the ocean of blissful completeness, I want for nothing at these times and, I'm overwhelmed with gratitude for a gift that reveals this vista and fulfils the longing in my heart.

There are many access points in my life, where I am spontaneously filled with a deep sense of peace, contentment and joy, including being immersed in nature or creative flow and delighting in time spent with those I love deeply (both human and non-human). I have also experienced this feeling in the therapy room, witnessing people at their most surrendered and most wise. The glimpses of the Self, achieved through a committed daily practice of mindfulness and meditation, require discipline. Continuing to practise these techniques daily fills me with a quiet joy and offers an anchor beyond the many internal self-narratives that clamour for my attention.

As 21st century human beings, our nature may be to forget our capacity for a unified sense of Self; instead we can be drawn like a moth to the flame of our lives' many distractions. Self-stories can become so absorbing that we may forget we are actually witnessing them; to be reminded of this, through whatever means, we can remember and be informed by the Self's compassionate presence. It seems most pertinent to conclude this practice-led section as I did in my film:

³⁷ I found the guidance of Prem Rawat and the techniques of Knowledge to be a means of accessing the Unified Self, or the Heart.

...I started off wanting to explore what it means to know the self. I discovered many selves or many layers of the self. Can I answer what it means to know the Self? I don't know, I *can* say is that every self is important, all the stories that make us who we are. I've also learned that there is an aspect of us that illuminates all of the stories, a place that we can return to, a feeling of 'coming home'. (*Returning Home*, 2017, excerpt of voice-over)

A feeling of peace and comfort that is centred in one's own body can change a human life; it can sustain us through the darkest of terrains; it is beyond time and something that needs to be returned to, rather than a destination to be arrived at.

Returning home – An Exhibition

Exhibition Invitation Images (left – right) Bardsley 2016, *Call to the desert*, oil and gold size on canvas, 102 x 76 cm; Bardsley 2016, *Kata Tjuta dusk*, digital print; Bardsley 2016, *Untitled*, digital print.

In this section, I document the exhibition and the works as they appeared in the gallery space³⁸.

The final exhibition for this investigation took place at *Kinross Arts and Spirituality Centre*, in Melbourne, with over one hundred people attending the opening night on October 12th, 2017, and a further one hundred people accessing the works throughout the duration of the exhibition. The film played on a loop in the gallery during the exhibition and had four more formal screenings when I attended to introduce it and to answer questions. The art novel *Returning home* (Bardsley 2017) was launched and the premiere of the short film *Returning Home* (2017) was held on opening night. I was at the gallery over four Sundays during exhibition, to give public addresses, engage with audiences and offer tours. Throughout the exhibition period, the art novel and many of the artworks were available for sale.

³⁸ The artist acknowledges that this was completed with the assistance of a *La Trobe University Social Research Platform Grant* and wishes to thank *Kinross Arts and Spirituality Centre* for their consent to documenting the event.

Returning home opening night I, still image from *Returning Home Exhibition Opening Night*, 2017, short film, Vimeo, Melbourne, created by Darcy Gooding.

An independent filmmaker³⁹ was commissioned to create a documentary piece about the exhibition; my opening address is the voice-over for this film. This atmospheric documentary reveals the unique beauty of the venue (a quality that influenced my choice of the gallery) and how the artworks interacted with the ambience of the setting. It can be viewed via the link below:

Returning Home Opening Night and Exhibition: <https://vimeo.com/257396157>

In addition to the documentary film of the exhibition and opening night, photo documentation of the opening night⁴⁰ and the hang of the show⁴¹, as well as professional archives of the fine art images⁴² were gathered. These can be accessed on the links below:⁴³

Photo-documentation of the show and opening night:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=199QuCi1K-t4McMbw0_KUsHEy9jWJk3-W

³⁹ Credit Darcy Gooding

⁴⁰ Credit Xavier Fennell

⁴¹ Credit Dean Whitby

⁴² Credit Dean Whitby

⁴³ The artist acknowledges the assistance of a *La Trobe University Social Research Platform Grant* and also wishes to thank *Kinross Arts and Spirituality Centre* for their consent to documenting the event.

Returning home II (Bardsley, 2017, exhibition), Opening night, digital image, credit Xavier Fennell.

Fine detailed photo-documentation of the paintings:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1l1cL73yjZc2f54_Xyn7RASq4IJXcD9ah

Returning home III (Bardsley, 2017, exhibition), Opening night, digital image, credit Xavier Fennell.

Additional material created for the exhibition including the exhibition invitation, media release⁴⁴, opening address, running sheet, catalogue as well as the artist's statement and bio, can be accessed here:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1kc7Q8HtZEd0mw1SnJQURBDSY-4rCAMTy>

Returning home IV (Bardsley, 2017, exhibition), Opening night, digital image, credit Xavier Fennell.

As I discuss in detail later⁴⁵, a key aspect was the investigation's capacity to transform both the researcher and the audience. The exhibition process provided a

⁴⁴ The artist acknowledges the curatorial advice from Lyndel Wischer, manager of the Kinross Arts and Spirituality Centre.

⁴⁵ Refer the section of this investigation titled *Research Outcomes and Transformative Validity*.

particularly salient means of assessing the transformative impact of this creative research; my reflections, as well as those of the audience, are discussed in the next section.

Bardsley 2017, *Landscape in gold*, mixed media and gold size on canvas, 92cm x 120cm, image credit: Dean Whitby

Responses to the Exhibition (and Creative Works)

This section discusses some of the audience responses to the work on the opening night, during the investigation and after the exhibition. It also includes my auto-ethnographic reflections on exhibiting the works and the feedback received. I have structured this material into the following areas: a) audience feedback regarding *A Message from Your Daughter* (Bardsley 2016); b) vox-pop interviews on the opening night of *Returning Home* (Bardsley 2017, exhibition); and c) my auto-ethnographic reflections regarding the exhibition process and the feedback I received, refer *Appendix 2*.

a) Audience Responses to A message from your Daughter

I was surprised and delighted by responses to the film *A Message from your Daughter* (Bardsley, 2016); many people were visibly overcome by their feelings and shared stories about their own relationships, particularly with their parents. Unfortunately, I did not document the responses that occurred after film screenings either in my own home or after conference presentations where I screened *A Message*. I have, however, included some of the responses that I received on social media and Vimeo⁴⁶.

‘I could sense the hours you spend in meditation in the spaces between your commentary. For me the spaces were profound, the natural humble element was beautiful. I think you have a great future in this field’.

‘I watched your video and it was pertinent and timely, and I felt connections from my own perspective, while appreciating the vulnerability and honesty of yours. I could feel and see the myriad of emotions towards your dad, stemming from a lifetime of events and it was beautiful and hurtful. If you know what I mean!’

⁴⁶ Any feedback I have included has been with the permission of the authors; personal material has been removed to preserve their privacy.

'It made me think, yet again, how to be the stronger person in our relationship.
Thanks again for sharing'

'Very brave and very beautiful. I'd imagine showing him would be the most
confronting part'.

'Powerful. Loved the video, the effect of black and white, is hauntingly beautiful. It
made me cry'.

'Such timely realizations about your feelings about your Dad. It's brave and beautiful
I think, to 'love fiercely' and to resolve to savor the moments and seize the
remaining days'.

'This is so powerful, Lara. It had to wait a day before I could compose myself to
respond to this video. I wish I could have said some of these things to my father.
But I still can to my daughter.....well done!'

b) Interviews on opening night

A number of interviewees chose to give their responses to the exhibition, film
premiere and book launch on opening night to a roving cameraman and interviewer
on the night⁴⁷.

⁴⁷ All responses are shared with the informed consent of the participants.

Returning home opening night II, still image from *Returning Home Exhibition Opening Night*, 2017, short film, Vimeo, Melbourne, created by Darcy Gooding.

These vox-pop interviews⁴⁸ can be viewed on the link below:

Vox Pop interviews, 'Returning home', Exhibition Opening Night, October 12th, 2017:

<https://vimeo.com/257371843>

⁴⁸ Credit filmmaker, Darcy Gooding, 2018; Interviewer, Robert Caldwell.

Outcomes and Transformative Validity

Summary of investigative findings

The findings of this investigation suggest the following: we have many selves, or many stories of the self, and many possible answers to the question: *Who are we?* Consciousness is possibly multiple in nature; self-narratives are be layered with some stories being more conscious and others unconscious, hidden or exiled. I have identified three categories of self in this investigation: 1) biographical selves (childhood and life memories), 2) liminal selves (including ancestral, inherited, trauma and illness narratives, mythic or archetypal aspects of the self), and 3) a unified self (an aspect of consciousness that can inform and guide the process of healing or transformation).

Transformational impact - Overview

As indicated in *A unique methodology*, Clements (2011, p. 153) suggests that one of the key outcomes of an investigation utilising *Organic Inquiry* is transformational change for the researcher across three areas: 1) self awareness, 2) connection with spirit, and 3) service to all life. Another outcome is the impact of the investigation on others, their reflections and responses to the work produced, as well as the potential for community and cultural change. This section will explore the transformational impact and validity as well as address the investigative challenges and limitations. The outcomes are discussed in terms of pedagogy and healing in later sections.

Personal Outcomes

I began this investigation with a twofold purpose: 1) to explore the many narratives that may be attributed to our sense of who we are, and 2) to reflect upon the transformative potential of the emergent narratives. In retrospect, I discovered a

third purpose, one that was less obvious to me at the beginning of the research—I sought to heal the sense of fragmentation that I was experiencing when I began this research, by deeply engaging with my personal narratives, and move toward a greater sense of well-being.

Clements (2011, p. 132) suggests the researcher write a synopsis before commencing the data collection—a short story that sets the baseline for the researcher’s state of being, reflecting upon her personality, abilities, experiences, resources and how they relate to developing the research question and commencing the investigation. At the time I wrote my baseline narrative my illness had hijacked my life: I was in chronic pain, distressed at having no choice but to retire from a senior psychologist role in a tertiary education institution, which although stressful, had offered me a strong sense of purpose and belonging. In this baseline narrative, I describe myself as feeling restless, anxious about the future, and ‘burnt out like a forest blackened by a slow consuming fire.’ The decision to undertake this investigation and the choice of my research topic emerged from the liminal space as I walked through the Australian coastal rainforest, in 2014. Having decided that I needed time away from my work, I was seriously considering a change of career, and amongst the fresh budding growth of the eucalypts and tree ferns, I intuitively felt that my next step was to study stories of the self, using an intuitive and transpersonal methodology, one that involved my own creative voice. I sensed that I needed to take the time to listen to my own stories and reflect on them in a manner that would also be of value in the area of transformative healing.

Since completing the investigation, my state of self-acceptance, quality of life, and psychological and physical wellbeing, have dramatically improved. There are many factors that may have contributed to this outcome, including the opportunity to move according to my own rhythms, and to remove myself from an organisational culture that had become unhealthy. This investigation allowed me to set my own pace, have the time to digest my experiences, make art, write stories, and reflect on the narratives that I had long converted or set aside. While this was, at times, distressing and re-stimulating, it was ultimately liberating. The process of engaging in an organic, transpersonal methodology, using a creative language, revealed inherited patterns in my ways of thinking and being in the world and these insights subsequently offered me the opportunity to choose alternate ways of living. Periods

of intensive research were interspersed with rest, time in nature and a simplified lifestyle. At times, I felt overwhelmed by the solitude and introspection; however, as an introvert in a culture and profession that I find extremely extroverted, this introspection was ultimately nourishing.

As the researcher, the most important personal outcome was that I was able to develop a sense of completion with many of my narratives and identify with them less intensely. As Chodron (2008, p. 19) suggests, it is when we learn to see our patterns of thoughts as 'thinking', that we can de-identify with thoughts, slip beneath their story line and access the energy that lies beneath them. In doing so, we can witness the 'awakened heart' (Chodron 2008, p. 19). This felt-experience of Self, both expansive and profound, was one that I began to access more frequently through this investigation, and one I hope to take with me into the future. Paradoxically, by immersing myself in the self-narratives that have shaped my life to this point, I have been able to loosen their grip. I understand that there will be many other stories that will arise in the unfolding of my life; however, I intend to practice witnessing them, tempered by a clarity that accessing the Self in its most expanded form can provide.

My auto-ethnographic reflections throughout this research speak to the transformative impact of this investigation in terms of my self-awareness and spiritual development. I have addressed the third transformative component, 'service' (Clements 2011, p. 153), through the opportunities to engage with a wider community and share the creative outcomes of this investigation (refer *Appendix 1*).

Transformational impact of the creative products on wider audience

The transformative impact on a wider audience has been discussed in *Responses to the Exhibition (and Creative works)* and *Appendix 2*. In summary, I was struck by heart-felt responses from the audience, expressing gratitude for the opportunity to reflect on the creative outcomes and their relevance for particular members. I find audiences to be highly engaged in any conference presentations where I utilise the creative findings, and people who want to share personal stories and insights stimulated by the film, writing or artworks frequently approach me afterwards. There is evidence of the transformative impact of the creative outcomes

in the feedback I receive, requests to use the film in training, spiritual, and personal development programs, or for me to provide keynote addresses at art, spirituality and wellbeing forums.

Addressing Investigative Challenges & Limitations

There are many challenges when researching the self and utilising one's own psyche as a vehicle of investigation; the act of searching through one's life is both subjective and, in many ways, inconclusive. There are many narrative threads that I have discussed that could have been unpacked further and others I have overlooked completely. Memory is selective, rewritten through our own perceptual lens, modified by our self-concepts, which change throughout the developmental phases of our lives (see Mc Adams 2001). Our brain is evolving until the last moments of our life; our capacity to re-interpret our experience is equally plastic (Park and Bischof 2013, pp. 109-119)⁴⁹. In twenty years' time, I may reconsider what I believe to be true now. In addition to being highly subjective, organic and auto-ethnographic research is inseparable from the personal, economic, gender and cultural experience of the researcher. I write as a woman, with the time to ponder on meaning-making and the human condition; I am confident about having my basic survival needs being met and I have a sense of connection and belonging to community and time to spend in deep reflective practice. My observations are informed by access to education, adequate health care, intellectual curiosity, emotional sensitivity, and an attention to detail. I have had the privilege of many years of personal and professional development, which have evolved my capacity to digest and contain what could be an unravelling process of self-reflection.

It is not possible to reach a definitive answer to the question of what it means to know the self. I am, and will continue to be 'a work in progress'; even when I die, the story of who I was can change, depending on which aspects people attend to. The generalisations are limited, in regard to what it means to know the self; however, I can hypothesise about the nature of the human psyche, the layers and complexity of stories that reside within us, and how these stories may shape us. My hypotheses will be bound by my own limitations and blind spots, as well as enhanced by my skills and talents. Although I am privileged in some areas of my life, I have also

⁴⁹ Also see Rossouw 2014

known intense psychological and physical distress, and experienced trauma; all these qualities contribute to my unique worldview.

According to Custer (2014, p. 7), an evocative personal voice embedded in the lived experience of culture makes auto-ethnographic research valid, accessible, applicable and useable to the world-at-large. In the light of these arguments, the self-reflexivity and creative output of this investigation contribute to its validity, and heuristic value. The language is narrative and its merit does not lie in whether it depicts an independent truth, but rather in its capacity to convey meaning and provide transformative opportunities, which it appears to do effectively. Both auto-ethnography and Organic Inquiry have the capacity to use narrative as a method of honouring the meaning and significance of life events, while acknowledging memory and truth as incomplete, tentative, and revisable (Bochner 2012, p. 157).

Ethical issues arise in auto-ethnographic writing and Organic Inquiry research; these include a duty of care for the participants as they share their stories, which was addressed in this investigation, in part, through an informed consent process created with considerable input from the university ethics committee. Professional counselling for participants was also provided in case sharing their personal stories necessitated further support; they were also offered the right to withdraw their stories at any stage. One must consider the impact of writing about loved ones and family members as well as our on-going relationships with them. The auto-ethnographic accounts that referenced my family members or friends (who were living), were shared with the people concerned, who had the opportunity to review the draft manuscripts, give their consent, or suggest any changes. The person who was most impacted (other than myself) was my father; he became integral to the research and writing process, reading all my drafts and offering me feedback regarding their accuracy as well as his recollection of events. As I have noted, while my father's memories of events were not always the same, he felt that this gave him insight into my experience and how it had shaped me. I found that I was able to respond to his recollections with a greater maturity, respect and compassion than I have previously accessed. The deepening of my relationship with my father through this investigation is further testimony of its transformative potential.

For much of my life, the stories hidden in my mother's ancestral past were inaccessible and only came to light in the last months of this research. This

investigation offered me a profoundly transformative opportunity, creating the space to unravel the threads of stories broken by the holocaust, suicide, neglect and post-traumatic stress. As one of the few survivors of that lineage, I have begun to digest these stories for the benefit of many who could not. Had this information emerged earlier, it might have more consciously influenced my film and artworks; however, I can see the presence of these narratives in my creative output, even though at the time the works were created, they were still hidden.

Another limitation I encountered was loss of data. There were times when responses to the rough-cuts of the film, my community talks, or exhibitions, were not recorded. Performing an empirical or thematic analysis of audience responses was not within the parameters of this research; this feedback, however, shaped the investigation, deepening my relationship with the material and confirming that the creative works were reaching people in a way that was felt and embodied. Future research could further explore the transformative impact of the creative works for a wider audience.

There are additional challenges inherent in transpersonal research that draws from liminal and personal sources; for example, such research may be considered to be less accurate, replicable, or generalisable in comparison to evidence-based reductionist methods, which utilise statistical data and analyses. Transpersonal stories, however, may converge toward collective meaning—as myths and fables suggest (irrespective of their temporal and cultural origins) (Campbell 2008); experiential accounts in Holotropic states of consciousness also converge along thematic axes (Grof 2012, pp. 29 - 77). This indicates that individually orientated transpersonal and liminal research may inform collective experience. While creative and transpersonal research may be limited in regard to replicable and controllable experimental outcomes, it does generate innovative and creative findings that offer potent opportunities for self-reflection and personal insight, as well as profound spiritual and psychological development. This investigation has been personally transformative; I hope that a wider audience can continue to benefit from the creative works born from it.

Discussion.

Jung described individuation as the process of 'becoming human', one that consists of 'the putting together of many scattered units so as to reveal and clarify something that was always there' (Jung 1958, p. 262). The perception that wisdom comes from a process of moving inward is consistent with eastern and indigenous philosophies, as well as with theories that suggest there is a universal aspect to our consciousness (see Laszlo 2014, p. 29). In many indigenous cultures, including shamanism, healing is an inner process with an external manifestation⁵⁰. Modern psychology has, on the whole, moved away from models of thinking that emphasise our interconnectedness with all life, encompassing stories of death, rebirth, spirit and transcendence. Jung (2001, p. 173) writes of the arts as the means by which we can reference the ineffable and give voice to our liminal stories, as well as the healing potential of doing so (Jung 1989, p. 195)

When engaging with liminal or collective material, images, feelings and body sensations that emerge can be referenced by a fluid, visual, symbolic and subjective language. Transpersonal, embodied and creative research can lead to a different kind of knowledge, valid because it touches an individual and an audience deeply, allowing for the integration of past and inherited material as well as contributing to a greater self-awareness. Such research invites a felt, embodied experience, a potent opportunity for transformation (Knox 2003, p. 10)⁵¹.

The study of emergent liminal material is central to Jungian psychology and forms the transformative pathway—individuation—that is both circular and progressive (Jung 1989, p. 196). Unconscious material within our psyche is the central core around which we repeatedly cycle, as if on a spiral staircase. We return to the same material but from another vantage point, perhaps able to see further

⁵⁰ It is the respected role of the shaman to travel into the collective unconscious to reckon with the spirits on behalf of his or her tribe to heal by repairing the bonds between the natural and spiritual worlds (for further information on shamanism see Abram 1997; Prechtel 1999 or 2015). In acknowledgement for this act, the Earth and the spirits show their kindness in providing game for hunting, healthy crops and livestock, allowing new life to be born and in guiding the community to harmonious and healthy lives. Like any relationship, there must be intimacy and respect for it to flourish.

⁵¹ Knox (2003, p. 10) concludes it is not enough to discover parts of our selves, we must learn to relate to them in new ways, informed by empathy and compassion, embodied, rather than conceptual qualities.

than we did before. Individuation is less about removing or repressing symptoms, than expanding our insight so we can hold our stories with greater clarity and compassion. Integrating liminal and mythic narratives can guide our understanding of who we are.

Grof's transpersonal framework of the human psyche has, at its centre, a wisdom and healing potential that orientates an individual toward wholeness, one he referred to as the 'inner healer' (Grof 2009, p.42). In my oceanic experience of the unconscious, the *inner healer* became the rudder and captain in the stormy or sublime liminal spaces through which I travelled. Within a transpersonal framework, wholeness comes from finding the space to hold salient personal and ancestral stories, compassionately witnessing and integrating these stories, so they no longer shape our actions, causing further harm to ourselves and others.

In his model of Internal Family Systems Therapy, Schwartz (2004, p. 1-9) suggests that a dialogue between parts of us, mediated and contained by a unified Self, can lead to previously unprecedented healing in therapy. Psychologist and Buddhist practitioner Brach (2018), describes four stages that mirror the emergent findings of this investigation of self: the first stage is to accept the presence of multiple narratives or selves; next, is to embrace these selves (some of which are vulnerable or wounded), allowing their presence in our consciousness; then, to investigate the narratives of these parts of us, including where they have originated and what they may be trying to protect us from; finally, to facilitate transformative healing by integrating these self-narratives with an attitude of deep compassion and acceptance⁵², utilising a part of us which is orientated toward wholeness⁵³.

From fifty decades of consciousness research, Grof (1998) gathered experiential evidence which indicates that trauma, mythic and archetypal material as well as collective human history remain in our unconscious. He proposed that the roots of human violence lie in the unresolved unconscious material of the human psyche as collective wounds that if not consciously addressed, will continue to motivate destructive actions (Grof 2012, pp. 159-164). Grof proposed that acting out unconscious impulses—whether in self-destructive behaviour, in interpersonal

⁵² See Brach 2004.

⁵³ (Called the 'Self' by Jung and Schwartz, 'Bodhichitta' in Buddhism)

conflict, or through wars and revolutions— will not result in healing. Instead, it becomes a further source of wounding; transformation is only possible if such narratives are brought to consciousness in an insightful and therapeutic environment (Grof 2012, pp. 159-164). Jung also considered that by committing to inner healing we bring about a shift in the collective unconscious and its manifestation in the external world:

Our existence as separate beings, our former ego nature is abolished, the circle of consciousness is widened, and because the paradoxes have been made conscious, the sources of conflict are dried up. (Jung 1958, p. 265)

The Buddhist philosophy of practising *maitri* (self compassion) and *tonglen* (the courageous act of bringing our compassionate awareness to suffering), also imply that we can weave the threads of our own and the collective story toward cohesion and wholeness (Chodron 2008, pp. 208 -209).

Circumambulation around a unified Self, moving toward wholeness through integrating parts, were a key aspect of this investigation. Through bearing witness to what I carry within, in a deeply embodied way, I experience suffering, but also a deep and lasting joy, one that remains constant and unchanging. By witnessing our selves with humility and courage, we may complete an honest review of our lives to this point and move forward to a more integrated presence in our later years. This process can be confronting, toxins in the stories we carry may surface and we can be overcome with grief as identities that have previously defined us, change. When there is an internal reckoning, there can be a death of sorts, a letting go that can take many forms; courage is required to disrobe the layers of ideas and behaviours that we have used to protect our more vulnerable selves, so that we may become unencumbered and permeable to life. What awaits us in this surrendered space is an experience of the Self that is unified, compassionate and creative, a self that can embrace our many aspects, facilitate an internal harmony, and allow us to live in a mutually enhancing relationship with the earth and all that live upon it (Berry 1997, pp. 191-203).

Some authors argue that rapid human population growth and its impact on the environment will dramatically influence the future of our species, and that of

every other living thing⁵⁴. As Rawat (2013, p. 20) reminds us, now more than ever 'we need to make peace with the world by making peace with our selves'. To know who we are, to live in a manner that allows us to act with compassion and insight is no longer desirable, it is necessary; if we do so, it is possible that our self-knowledge may inform and transform our actions, for the benefit of all.

⁵⁴ It is uncertain how we will adapt to the growing challenges of climate change, food, water shortages and the depletion of the planet's finite resources through energy exploitation, deforestation and over-population (Collins 2014, p. xix). The impact of choices made now and their outcome for the quality of life for future generations will be dramatic over the next three decades (Harvey 2013, pp. 36-41).

Conclusion

There are many answers to the question: *Who are we?* We have multiple selves; some parts of us are more easily accessible, such as memories, life-stories or events that shape our identity, which are altered by the lens through which we view them and change over our lifespan⁵⁵. Stories of the self may be rewritten⁵⁶, shaped by culture, time⁵⁷, gender, and the extent to which our narratives are influenced by unresolved, traumatic or blocked memories⁵⁸. This investigation indicates that the self is layered; parts of us are buried beneath the limen of our consciousness and may be exiled or hidden because of their vulnerability⁵⁹, while others reflect mythic or archetypal drives of the unconscious⁶⁰. Bringing liminal selves to our conscious awareness, integrating painful, inherited or previously unconscious narratives, can be personally transformative⁶¹; sharing transpersonal and creative outcomes can also inspire an audience.

The creative arts are a potent means of investigating embodied, felt and transpersonal aspects of self. A methodology that utilises a creative voice, valuing intuitive, emergent wisdom, is particularly effective in exploring the human psyche⁶². This research reveals that a creative investigation of self can be transformative for the researcher; findings presented in a creative, multi-media language are accessible to a wider audience and have the potential to elicit an embodied, felt experience, evoking deeply reflective responses. The validity of this investigation's unique and creative voice has been anecdotally established; further research could determine the transformative impact of the creative outcomes for a wider audience.

There is significant heuristic merit to this investigation in terms of consciousness research, therapy, healing and transformation. If we have many selves, some less seen, buried beneath our consciousness (as various practitioners and

⁵⁵ Refer McAdams (2001, pp. 106-107)

⁵⁶ Refer White & Denborough (2011, pp. 123 - 135)

⁵⁷ Refer Vattimo (2002, pp. 8-9).

⁵⁸ Refer Ricoeur (2004, pp. 3-4).

⁵⁹ Schwartz and Falconer (2017, pp. 61-62)

⁶⁰ Refer Jung (1989, p. 336).

⁶¹ Refer Jung (1976, pp. 460-461).

⁶² For example, Jung (1963, pp. 530 - 531) and Grof (2015, pp. 68-69)

theorists suggest⁶³) then bringing these parts of us to our awareness, within a safe and nurturing environment, can be profoundly healing and transformative. There are multiple ways to facilitate the emergence and integration of previously unconscious material. As the outcomes of this investigation suggest, a creative, organic and transpersonal investigation into an individual's self-understanding can contribute to personal and collective transformation. Further research into the Self in its most expansive form would be of considerable merit. This Self can guide human consciousness toward integration and provide a safe, compassionate container for transformative healing; it is a remarkable resource, residing within us, and communicating through symbols, art and the body⁶⁴. One of the most effective methods of exploring the Self is a methodology that is organic, transpersonal and practice-led allowing an inherent wisdom to emerge.

⁶³ For instance, refer Jung (1976, pp. 460-461); Grof (2012, pp. 38-41); Schwartz and Falconer (2017, p. 94).

⁶⁴ Refer Jung (2001, p. 173)

Appendix 1 - Service to all life

It has been my hope that this research and its creative products may become an act of service, a tool that can enhance the transformation of many. Spiritual traditions use the term 'service' to mean an act of helping imbued with compassion and kindness (Loue 2017). My intention has been to create something that could promote transformative change for a wider audience. During this research, I participated in a number of communities both spiritual and academic, in order to share the research and its outcomes so that it may provide an opportunity for reflection, inspiration and transformation. I have accepted opportunities to speak on the transformative potential of the arts and narrative to inform compassionate action. I have presented in academic and community settings on the arts and how they may speak to the deepest stories within us. These included national and international conference presentations, panel discussions, keynote addresses and talks to community groups with interests in creativity, spirituality, ecology and wellbeing. I have exhibited in group exhibitions aimed at raising the awareness of arts and narrative as agents to promote mental health and wellbeing. I was interviewed in a four-part community radio program regarding my research findings, my understanding of the Self and the importance of knowing who we are. As Clements (2011) predicts, I have found that this Organic Inquiry investigation has been a powerful agent for personal growth as well as offering a wider audience the possibility to reflect deeply on its emergent themes through the investigation's creative output. It has been a gift to see how this heart-centered and creative research is able to touch people in a deep and authentic way and stimulate felt responses from audiences across a wide variety of settings. I have listed some of the opportunities I have had for service as publications in the opening pages of this exegesis.

Appendix 2 – Reflections after the exhibition.

2nd November 2017

I am attempting to digest what has happened (and continues to happen) inside me in response to the many experiences I have had while exhibiting these works. I will start with the memories that I have in sharp relief. The first is of my aunt (my mother's sister) seeing my work for the first time—the images that represent her mother—stories that she hasn't shared with me, but exist within us both. She is 81, very slim and birdlike with white blond hair. I remember her eyes filled with tears, the tremor of her thin hand clasped in mine, but most significantly, her speechlessness. I can picture my cousin (her daughter), the verbal, busy energy that she has, and my sense that while I dig deeply into the wet sand to allow the stories to seep through, she rapidly builds sandcastles on top of them. I can see in my mind's eye the room where the film was screened filled with at least one hundred people; I am reminded of the pin drop silence except for the sounds of people crying and giggling. I remember the long line of people waiting for me to sign their copy of my art novel, thanking me for the gift of being immersed in 'my world', and those who recognise that it was also 'their world'. Then... my memories of my father, his vulnerability and pride on opening night, his enthusiasm and engagement throughout the whole process of creating and exhibiting the work, and my concern for him in the cinema space as so many people viewed the part of the film where I declare my fierce love for him despite the challenges of our relationship. At the end of the night he had a quiet word with me about how different it was to see the film on the big screen. 'Good different', he assured me. It has been the evolution of my relationship with Dad through the telling of these stories that is my most treasured testimony of the transformative quality of this investigation.

I have been so tired over these past weeks while the artworks and film have been available to the public. I am frequently stopped in my neighbourhood by people who attended the exhibition wanting to share with me stories of their loved ones, now deceased, their explorations in the central desert, or to discuss their experience of 'returning home'. I have come to realise the profound sense of community that has

evolved while I have completing this research; it is as if the robust psychic barriers we tend to erect in our modern culture have become permeable through the stories that I have shared in this exhibition.

Last Sunday, three friends came into the gallery, women whom I hadn't seen for twenty-five years (a testimony to the wonders of social media to reunite us). One of these was a friend who has a brain tumor and wasn't expected to live beyond a few months of receiving her diagnosis (now almost a year ago). She came with her sister, walking with a frame and negotiating stairs, both amazing achievements after being confined to her bed, then a wheelchair, after her surgery. The tumor is still present, and the diagnosis is terminal, yet her stability and improvement are unexplained medically but perhaps better understood spiritually: she inspires great love and care and there is no doubt she is nourished by it; she is a remarkable woman. We first met in the early days of my self-exploration and I often assisted on her workshops, which were orientated toward an embodied, empowered experience of femininity. During my first 'spiritual emergency', while I was studying clinical psychology, she was a guiding presence, providing a soothing juxtaposition of an alternative healing model to balance the pathology-focused diagnostic model that I was studying—one that provided me with no end of labels toward my own experience! She advised me to avoid the medical mental health system and may well have obviated my career as a psychiatric patient; instead, with kindness and care from my friends, I was able to integrate the non-ordinary experiences that were overwhelming me at the time, complete my clinical psychology masters, and begin my training as a transpersonal psychologist with Stanislav Grof. A paradigm shift ensued, one that has led me to this investigation and back to my Self. Now twenty-five years later, I can offer some support to her in a time of vulnerability and great courage. She bought my painting 'Ancient oceans' and I gave her a copy of my art novel 'Returning home'. Two days later she texted me:

The other paintings that I have sold at this point went home with both of my supervisors, each of whom resonated deeply with the artworks and shared with me how the paintings they acquired have become woven into their own lives and homes.

I was delighted to receive some poetry from a man who was in Melbourne to attend the funeral of a fellow glider pilot (who had recently died in an accident). He was instantly drawn to one of my photographs, 'As Above, So Below', and asked me, on opening night, whether he could share the poem he wrote to his wife about their new purchase.

As above, so below, 2017, digital print.

He wrote:

'We now own another work of art.

As soon as I saw it, it went Ding!

And later I sorted through the various elements of attraction and relevance.

Here is the very soft

Reflected in the very hard.

A bit of heaven in earth,

Ephemeral in rock solid,

Temporal against near eternal

Evaporation,

And lichen,

As water becomes air

And rock returns to life.

It also helps that the pool is aerodynamic

And all this as we bury a fellow glider pilot.'

I received another written reflection from a woman and psychologist, via email:

Dear Lara

You are still at your art show (sorry I needed to dash off)...but I wanted to email while the experience was still fresh in my mind. I was very moved by your work. It was so tender and full of love and grace. The word that was in my mind as I left the room was 'courage'. Expressing yourself and saying and showing what is on your mind and in your heart are acts of courage, and an honour to witness. I was particularly moved when you reflected on your father. I sensed (or perhaps projected!) there has been a complex relationship, requiring deep forgiveness, acceptance and surrender, to be present with your father, and yet I also sensed a distance that perhaps was never going to be crossed; a space between you, maybe time, maybe something else, that persists. And it has me thinking of the spaces I have in my relationships, and the sadness that evokes in me.

As I drove home, I put on two of my favourite songs by my favourite artist, Gillian Welch; she is an American singer and songwriter, with a country vibe, who I sense is utterly herself. I love her voice and the humanity of her songs that reach me in a way that is hard to put into words. One of the songs "I dream a highway" has a beautiful line: "I dream a highway back to you, Love, a winding ribbon with a band of gold." It evokes for me longing for home, the twisting and turning of the path, and also the promise of connection with a band of gold.

Here's the song in a clip I found:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KDZDEltdQw>

I hope you are feeling very pleased and proud and inspired by your wonderful exhibition. I am so glad to know you.

A couple who also attended the opening has been following my art since they came across a collection of my portraits in a café gallery in Southern Highlands NSW, and wrote to me afterwards:

Hi Lara, It was certainly a special night, thank you for sharing your story of love, peace and harmony with us. It's people like you that will help create a new World of Peace and understanding into the future. Keep on going with your amazing journey.

A colleague of Rob's with whom I was not acquainted, wrote the following:

Hello Lara,

Firstly I wanted to say a huge congratulation for the Art exhibition, novel and film, I can't even imagine how much of yourself you have put into creating it, it was truly inspiring! Just a quick note to say how much the film resonated with me at this time in our lives. Rob may have mentioned I am returning to NZ to be closer to my Dad and although we had made the decision, it was made clear to me after watching the film that we had made the right decision, so I wanted to thank you for that. All my love, A

A close friend of mine (also a Social Worker) responded to the film and book that I sent to him in Tasmania:

Your book came to me and I watched your film at the time I needed to. With [my workplace] I have been considering doing a group on self-esteem (I have been told I can't do a group on self-compassion as it is too complex for our clients). I don't, however, like the concept of 'self-esteem', it's like we have to fix something that is broken, or work at changing something in our selves to make us 'worthy' or 'worthwhile'. So I have been pondering this and reading and thinking.

I receive your book (thank you) and it brings up in me a voice, a question 'what have I achieved?' I seem to start things with a new hope—this will be a new chapter or story... I read your book and there is another voice: 'maybe I have to trust and use what I have learnt, to honour my journey and story, what I have learnt and what I read'.

I watched your film and a thought speaks within me - I want to listen to who I am... as I listen to who I am... the pain and the joy... see where I resist life and close down

and hide, to approach this with curiosity, openness and love, it just may change (or not), but it is okay to have these stories, to talk to these stories... because this is who I am, and that is okay.

So I am shaping a group session/s with a tip of my hat to the politics of the work place I may call it 'self-esteem', and in doing this, I will trust and embrace my story, who I am, and what I have learnt.

A girlfriend from yoga who has travelled a similar path to mine through her own health crisis responded:

Wow.

I just left your exhibition.

It's hard to say how it made me feel, my thoughts ect in a message. So much resonated with me. I LOVED the Hope piece and it almost made me teary as I reflected on my own path of returning home and how good it feels to be the

truest version of myself that I've been for as long as I can remember.

There's so much courage and creativity that has gone into your work.

Thank you for giving me the privilege to be able to view it xxx

Recently, I received another email from an acquaintance that beautifully and succinctly distilled the essence of the film:

Lara,

What a beautiful journey your film took me on. A gentle awakening (or re-awakening) to the untold worth of knowing, really knowing, that all that we are for eternity is complete and whole within us. What a promise!

Finally, the reflections of another friend:

Your beautiful book arrived today and it so naturally touches the heart. Holding it in my hands and being able to turn the pages is very different from seeing it on the computer screen.

Thank you very much for it and also for the copy of your excellent speech. They say that all scholarship is autobiography and you have turned that around, shaping your creative and heartfelt self-expression into scholarship with your gentle words and stunning images.

I am struck by the potential of the arts to reach through the fabric of our selves, slip beneath the masks we wear to touch the authentic Self, the space you and I know as the Heart. The feeling in peoples' responses to my creative narratives has been palpable; there was such trust granted in what they have shared and I have honored this trust by only including those responses that I have permission to publish.

A balanced account of the exhibition process would acknowledge that it has not been smooth sailing. I needed to be a lot more involved than I anticipated (or was comfortable with) in the marketing, media liaison, promotion and sale of the works, as well as the associated event management, including catering and recruitment of gallery volunteers; in short, there were many disappointments, as well as a number of generous surprises. Having what I came to refer to as 'a launch trifecta' on one night provided a significant challenge, with considerable energy and organisation required to manage a book launch, a film premiere, and an exhibition opening (all occurring within a three-hour period), as well as moving more than one hundred people from one building to another. I had a panic attack a few hours prior to my opening speech and was convinced that I would pass out, vomit, or lose control of my bodily functions (or a combination of all three)! When it came to the time to speak, though, I was filled with a deep, grounded sense of peace and a passion for the research, one that has held the reins of my life for the past three years.

There were limitations associated with the venue: it was not a commercial gallery; the manager was part-time, with many competing demands for her attention, staff were volunteers and, understandably, not consistently available; these factors, I considered to be less significant in comparison with the beauty and presence of the venue itself. 'Kinross Arts and Spirituality Centre' is situated in a mansion (originally the church rectory) with stained glass windows, soaring ceilings and expansive light-filled rooms overlooking a cottage garden budding with spring growth, crowned by a

Luculia tree shedding confetti of scented pink petals. There was a symbiosis between the works and the space.

When the exhibition ended, and the remaining works returned to my studio, I was overwhelmed by what I have only recently understood to be a grieving process, one that seems to manifest in my preoccupation with how elderly my canine soul companion is becoming, with the grey hairs spreading from her muzzle, to now circle her eyes. She has been with me constantly through this investigation and certainly has earned her prominence in my acknowledgments. We are psychically conjoined; I cannot begin to imagine life without her. I also feel agitated when I think of how the majority of the works have not yet sold. I will certainly break even; however, this is largely due to the financial grants I received from the University and a friend's generous support toward the publication of the art novel, as well as the art novel sales. Despite the overwhelming response of the public to the artworks, many works still remain in my possession. I have fretted about this and have come up with many theories as to why, including the gallery being relatively unknown in the art scene, and that the vast majority of the people who attended the exhibition were from my networks many of whom are struggling financially, as fellow artists and students, or have already purchased some of my work. There is no doubt that I have more to learn about marketing to networks outside my social media or friendship circles; I do wonder, though whether post-colonial Australia is conditioned toward acquiring original artworks or more oriented toward consumable goods, designer clothing, shoes, handbags, jewelry and new cars!

...

It has taken me some time to realise that my distress regarding lack of sales during my exhibition may be a ruse to hide a deeper process, one that is concerned with the opportunity this investigation has provided for me to live deeply, make art and have the space I crave away from the pace of the everyday world. Bringing the majority of the works home leaves me with a sense of being clogged, and challenges my justification for making new works. As the days pass, I realise that I need to continue making work to stay connected to my own 'aliveness' and that despite my current

financial problems, there are many who will welcome the art into their homes and treasure them.

The primary process that has hijacked my psychological state, for a few weeks now, has centered on a void; a part of me screams: 'what next? Will I be able to live with my sensitivity, vulnerability and fragile health, in a manner that continues this transformative process while still paying my bills?' I find myself caring deeply about healing and transformation, but there has been a significant shift in my orientation: I am less human-centric, my sense of self and my engagement with the future is permeated by a deep concern for the Earth. I am grieving the impact of our behaviour on this beautiful planet's fragile ecology; my empathy toward animal welfare has been amplified even beyond what it was; when passed by a truck packed with animals on their way to the abattoir, I am overwhelmed, as the animals' suffering resonates through my body. I am now vegan and am trying to do what I can to minimise my reliance on packaged and non-locally grown foods. The aggression and carelessness I experience from other drivers on the roads, feed my concern for the general mental state of human beings; the frantic pace of the lives we live seems to breed narcissism and a dislocation from our selves. I do recognise that I am still in the liminal space; maybe I'm a little too skinless and at risk of drowning in my own compassion (and art)!

(A few weeks later)

This reflective process has taken some time to edit and my consciousness continues to shift. I have sought advice on distributing the film and have published my art novel on Amazon; I've made it available for sale in hard copy and on Kindle. Today, I am clearing out my front room, and have advertised myself as available to supervise clinicians or therapists who wish for a safe place to reflect on their practice and learn to work more deeply with their clients. I have begun to make myself available for public speaking, currently voluntarily—I ran a community workshop on storytelling last Friday and screened my film 'Returning Home'—it was beautifully received. I have also compiled a catalogue of the artworks that are still available and people are expressing an interest in purchasing some of them with viewings scheduled in the next few weeks. Most significantly, I have taken myself in hand and decided to ardently

work on my own limiting narratives that minimise my perception of what I have to contribute to the world; they are long out of date.

Glossary of terms

This section consists of quotations, my own notes and reflections to further clarify the terms that I have used in the research.

Active Imagination: Sharp (1991, p.3) describes ‘active imagination’ as a method of assimilating unconscious contents (dreams, fantasies etc.) through some form of self-expression. The object of active imagination is to give a voice to sides of the personality that are normally not heard, thereby establishing a line of communication between consciousness and the unconscious. Jung (1989) refers to ‘active imagination’ as creative play, dream or symbolic analysis whereby moods, images and body sensations are explored, and unconscious material is made conscious. Active imagination is one of the means by which the Self (or Transcendent Function) communicates in the individuation process. Alluding to the playful, curious and surrendered process of active imagination, Jung writes:

I had no choice but to . . .take up that child's life with his childish games. (Jung 1989, p. 174)

To the extent that I managed to translate the emotions into images-that is to say, to find the images which were concealed in the emotions – I was inwardly calmed and reassured. Had I left those images hidden in the emotions, I might have been torn to pieces by them...

As a result of my experiment I learned how helpful it can be, from the therapeutic point of view, to find the particular images which lie behind the emotions. (Jung 1989, p. 177)

Anthropocene: The term used by some authors to refer to the current ecological era, when human beings are perceived to have the most influence on planetary life support processes, thereby shaping the future survival of their species and that of all life on the planet (Harvey, 2013).

Archetype: In Jungian Psychology the term is used to refer to a collectively inherited primordial structural element of the human psyche. Jung writes:

The archetypes...are not intellectually invented. They are always there and they produce certain processes in the unconscious one could best compare with myths. That's the origin of mythology. (Jung 1978, p. 348)

Psychologically ... the archetype as an image of instinct is a spiritual goal toward which the whole nature of man strives; it is the sea to which all rivers wend their way, the prize which the hero wrests from the fight with the dragon. (Jung 1981, p. 206)

There is good reason for supposing that the archetypes are the unconscious images of the instincts themselves, in other words, that they are patterns of instinctual behaviour. (Jung 1981, p. 44)

The archetype is an irrepresentable factor, a 'disposition' which starts functioning at a given moment in the development of the human mind and arranges the material of consciousness in definite patterns. (Jung 1958, p. 148)

Bodhichitta: a Sanskrit word meaning 'noble or awakened heart' - considered, in Buddhism, to be the central core of humanity (also referred to as 'Buddha nature'); it is equated with human beings' ability to love, to be kind, and to be selfless. Chodron (2008) writes:

Mindfulness in its full form awakens *bodhichitta*, the tenderness for life and when we no longer shield ourselves from the vulnerability of our existence, it awakens our awareness of the kinship with the suffering of other living things. It makes us open, so that we may take in the pain of the world, let it touch our hearts and to see things as they are. As the curtain of indifference parts, our compassion is awakened and with it, our action and responsibility to care and respond to what we see. (Chodron 2008, p. 207)

Bodhichitta has two aspects: absolute and relative (Sell 2008, p. xv). Absolute bodhichitta links us to all life and encompasses unfathomable compassion, openness and intelligence without any perception of 'self' and 'other'. Relative bodhichitta refers to the courage to investigate our tender heart and gradually expands our capacity to be with suffering, surrender to vulnerability, and explore the limitless quality of love and joy, of which all human beings are capable (Sell 2008, p. xv).

Circumambulation: a term Jung used to describe the interpretation of psychic material by reflecting on it from different points of view. It is not a linear process, rather it is more circular or spiral in nature. Through an evolving awareness we may return again and again to a memory, experience or dream, but each time, see it from a different and deeper perspective.

I began to understand that the goal of psychic development is the self. There is no linear evolution; there is only a circumambulation of the self. (Jung 1989, p. 196)

Collective Unconscious: Jung developed Freud's model of the unconscious to include 'collective material'; he writes:

The collective unconscious contains the whole spiritual heritage of mankind's evolution, born anew in the brain structure of every individual. (Jung 1981, p. 158)

The collective unconscious—so far as we can say anything about it at all—appears to consist of mythological motifs or primordial images, for which reason the myths of all nations are its real exponents. In fact, the whole of mythology could be taken as a sort of projection of the collective unconscious . . . We can therefore study the collective unconscious in two ways, either in mythology or in the analysis of the individual. (Jung 1981, p. 150)

Consciousness: a term equated with sentience, awareness and selfhood, but the state and quality of that awareness.

Depth Psychology: the branch of psychology developed by Sigmund Freud and Carl Jung in the early 20th century, that gave primacy to the unconscious. Freud referred

to the unconscious as a receptacle of the aspects of the human consciousness that were disowned, hidden, or too painful to be owned by the conscious mind (Freud 1920, p. 18; also refer Freud, 2012). Jung considered that while the unconscious may contain repressed material, it was also the source of the ultimate intelligence beyond the conscious mind and the vessel of knowledge that was both unfathomable and profound (Jung 1963, p. 384). Despite their differences, both considered wholeness and transformation within the human psyche to be possible only through the integration of the unconscious material by the conscious mind.

Divine: a term used interchangeably to refer to absolute consciousness, the Transcendent Self, God, the creative principle that underlies all life, both manifest and potential (Grof 1998, p. 42).

(see also **God**)

Ego: Freud's theory of multiple layers of human consciousness, the 'ego' refers to the self that deals with reality, attempting to navigate the tension between instinctual drives and the idealised aspects of the psyche (see Freud, 1963, 116-151; also refer Freud, 2012). Jung (1963, p. 107) refers to the ego's relationship with the unconscious as 'the...mirror in which the unconscious becomes aware of its own face'

Kornfield (2009, p. 293) clarifies the use of the term in western psychology: the 'ego' is equated with resilience and strong boundaries; it is the means by which our instinctual drives can be contained and our desires moderated.

In Buddhism 'ego' refers to less desirable qualities such as arrogance, delusion and self-centredness (Kornfield 2009, p. 67).

In this research, the 'ego' is the 'viewer', the means by which unconscious material as well as internalised cultural, temporal, moral and idealised beliefs can be contained, observed and explored.

Embodiment: a term used to refer to visceral, intuitive and felt experience, that is, felt within the body (Knox 2003, p. 9; Freidman & Moon, 1997).

God: The use of the term 'God' in the current research has been aptly defined by the artist and poet, Leunig (2014):

[God] is a lyrical word, a poetic word, in fact, it is a one-word poem; a peaceful mysterious poem which I might also call the deep self. This 'God' I have been talking to and wondering about seems to lie within and around the lost original self; the innocent true self that is not of this time stricken, divided material world. This is my sense of God that, in quietness and stillness, confirms the wholeness of self and connects it to the wholeness of life. Something like that. *Dear God*.

(Leunig 2014, p.13)

Holotropic: a term devised by Grof (1998, p. 11) to describe an expanded state of awareness, one that reflects the full potential of human consciousness and may include mythic, collective, embodied and spiritual states of awareness. It is a composite word meaning 'oriented or moving towards wholeness'.

Holotropic Breathwork: devised by Grof and Grof (refer Grof 2012, pp. 115-110), *Holotropic Breathwork* is a technique to access non-ordinary states of consciousness, utilising rapid, connected breath (Pranayama breathing), evocative music and movement.

Individuation: Sharp (1991, p. 38) describes individuation as the movement toward wholeness through facilitating a relationship between the ego and the unconscious; the aim of individuation is not to become perfect, but to become familiar with one's own psychological make up, one's strengths, limitations and uniqueness. Jung writes:

Self-reflection, or—what comes to the same thing—the urge to individuation, gathers together what is scattered and multifarious and exalts it to the original of the One, the Primordial Man. (Jung 1958, p. 5149)

On the integration of unconscious material through individuation, he writes:

The images of the unconscious place a great responsibility upon a man. Failure to understand them, or shirking of ethical responsibility, deprives him of his wholeness and imposes a painful fragmentariness on his life. (Jung 1989, p.192)

Liminal: The word 'limen' is Latin for 'threshold' and refers to the transition from an ordinary state of consciousness where one is bound to concepts of identity, time, bodily and egoic definition, to the realm of the spiritual or transpersonal state of consciousness including unconscious, numinous and non-ordinary states of human consciousness. Liminal material may include symbolic, mythic and archetypal experiences; it is frequently explored by transpersonal research methods, and rarely acknowledged in traditional scientific methodologies (refer Turner 1966, pp. 94-95; van Gennep 1960, p. 189).

Mandala: A mandala is a circular symbol traditionally used in indigenous and eastern religions. The circular pattern or image is a representation of cosmic or universal consciousness—without beginning or end. It is frequently used in meditation, ritual or spiritual practice. It may also be used as a means of containing a visual story that has emerged from the psyche in deep personal and spiritual reflection (Jung 1989, p. 188)

Mindfulness: Mindfulness is a term used in Buddhist philosophy to refer to the practice of observing the contents of one's mind without attachment or judgment (Hahn 1998, pp. 9-12). Buddhist mindfulness aims to include, integrate and transcend all aspects of the self (Chodron 2008, p. 207)

Maitri: A Sanskrit term:

(Sanskrit) 'Unconditional loving kindness'. A direct, unconditional relationship with all aspects of ourselves and others. (Chodron 2008, p.208)

Narrative: for the purpose of this research, the term refers to a story told in order to make meaning of a life event or convey symbolic meaning.

Narrative selves/self: a platform through which the concept of the self is understood; our stories are a means of attributing meaning to our experiences and defining who we are.

Non-ordinary states of consciousness (NOSC): contrasted with everyday consciousness, the state of consensus reality where the everyday world is experienced as bound by time, interpreted through personal and cultural frameworks—‘ordinary consciousness’; conversely, states of awareness that are not usually experienced in everyday consciousness are ‘non-ordinary states of consciousness’ (NOSC) (refer Grof & Grof 1992, pp.145-149). NOSC are characterised by changes of sensory perception including body sensations, visions, mythic, universal and unconscious material that flood a person’s awareness (Grof & Grof 1992, pp. 145-149).

(See also **Holotropic consciousness**).

Numinous: Sharp (1991) defines Numinous in the following manner:

Numinous is a term used to describe experiences that have a deep emotional resonance with the Self [the Self as its transcendent, unitive aspect of the psyche, the Spirit]. (Sharp1991, p.54)

Ordinary Consciousness: The state of everyday consciousness bound by time and shaped by our personal and cultural frameworks (Grof 1993, pp. 145 - 149).

(See also **Non- Ordinary States of Consciousness (NOSC)**).

Projection. Sharp (1991) writes:

Projection is an automatic process whereby contents of one's own unconscious are perceived to be in others. (Sharp 1991, p.62)

Jung writes:

Just as we tend to assume that the world is as we see it, we naïvely suppose that people are as we imagine them to be... All the contents of our unconscious are constantly being projected into our surroundings, and it is only by recognizing certain properties of the objects as projections or imagos that we are able to distinguish them from the real properties of the objects...(Jung 2002, p. 52)

Psyche: In this research the term 'psyche' is used to refer to the totality of all psychological processes, both conscious and unconscious.

Repression: the unconscious suppression of psychic material.

Jung writes:

Repression causes what is called a systematic amnesia, where only specific memories or groups of ideas are withdrawn from recollection. In such cases a certain attitude or tendency can be detected on the part of the conscious mind, a deliberate intention to avoid even the bare possibility of recollection, for the very good reason that it would be painful or disagreeable. (Jung 1981, p. 109)

Self: The term 'self' has been used to describe a range of entities including 'mind, intellect, personality, character, spirit, soul, ego, witness, and sense of "I" or identity' (Oxford on-line dictionary). Jung used the term 'self' to refer to: the sense of identity; an archetypal organising principle navigating the path to wholeness through the conflicting aspects of the psyche, which he termed the 'Self archetype' (written with a capital 'S') or 'transcendent function' (Jung 1963, p. 200). Miller (2004) also alludes to the 'Self' as the concept of wholeness and the union with the Divine (refer Miller, 2004).

In this research I refer to the self (with a small 's') as part of the personality, or ego; and 'Self' (with a capital 'S') to refer to a transpersonal, unified aspect of consciousness that guides the process of individuation.

(See also **Bodhichitta**)

Shadow:

The *Shadow* is the hidden or unconscious aspects of oneself, both good and bad, which the ego has either repressed or never recognized. The shadow is composed for the most part of repressed desires and uncivilized impulses, morally inferior motives, childish fantasies and resentments, etc.--all those things about oneself one is not proud of. These unacknowledged personal characteristics are often experienced in others through the mechanism of projection. (Sharp 1991, p.75)

On integrating the shadow through therapy, Jung writes:

Good does not become better by being exaggerated, but worse, and a small evil becomes a big one through being disregarded and repressed. The Shadow is very much a part of human nature, and it is only at night that no shadows exist. (Jung 1958, p. 286)

The shadow is a moral problem that challenges the whole ego-personality, for no one can become conscious of the shadow without considerable moral effort. To become conscious of it involves recognizing the dark aspects of the personality as present and real. This act is the essential condition for any kind of self-knowledge, and it therefore, as a rule, meets with considerable resistance. Indeed self-knowledge as a psycho-therapeutic measure frequently requires much painstaking work over a long period. (Jung 1981, p 8 -10)

Spirit/Spiritual: In this research, 'spirit' refers to states of consciousness beyond everyday reality, particularly 'Holotropic consciousness'. Grof differentiates spirituality from religion:

Spirituality is based on direct experiences of non-ordinary dimensions of reality and does not necessarily require a special place or an officially appointed person mediating contact with the Divine. It involves a special kind of relationship between the individual and the cosmos and is, in its essence, a personal and private affair. (Grof 1998, p. 248)

Transformation: In this research, ‘transformation’ refers to a healing process where a person learns to live with a past trauma, memory, wound or life experience in a manner that allows new information, or new ways of relating that enable a greater capacity for equilibrium, comfort and growth. Transformation is individual, collective and transpersonal, as Jung suggests:

It is my own transformation—not a personal transformation, but the transformation of what is mortal in me into what is immortal. It shakes off the mortal husk that I am and awakens to a life of its own. (Jung 1981, p. 79)

Tonglen:

(Tibetan) “Sending and Receiving.” Also described as exchanging Self for other. In the practice of tonglen we breathe in whatever feels bad and send out whatever feels good. (Chodron 2008, p. 209)

Transpersonal: (*trans* personal—beyond the personal). Transpersonal psychology and research are oriented toward states of consciousness beyond the limits of the ego and personality. The term is concerned with transformational experiences, the study of humanity’s highest potential, intuitive, transcendent experiences and focuses on inter-connectedness and compassionate inclusion of experience for the benefit of all life (Anderson & Braud 2011, p. 8).

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